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DiscardLess

Strategies for the gradual elimination of discards in European fisheries

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Synthesis of Discards Mitigation Strategies by Case Study

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Executive summary

This deliverable provides an overview of the various Discard Mitigation Strategies (DMS) that have been analysed and investigated in the various case studies. The DMSs are proposed and examined as case specific approaches to support the implementation of the European Landing Obligation (LO). The DMSs represent potential approaches to reduce unwanted catches through fishing gear technology (WP3) changes in fishing patterns (WP4), by finding efficient solutions for handling unavoidable unwanted onboard (WP5), and through identifying existing and novel ways to utilize unwanted catches (WP6).

This deliverable represents thus a synthesis of the work developed in these four “innovation” Work Packages, summarised by region. The technical details of the various approaches can be found in the corresponding deliverables from these WPs and where applicable, in scientific publications.

The work has been diverse, and not all tasks / work package have been performed in each case study. But in every case studies, significant amounts of new knowledge have been developed about the possible technical and tactical approaches to reduce discards and/or to best utilise them in the value chain. A number of approaches are specific to a given issue in a given case study, but there are also many commonalities and some developments are of interest at a much wider scale than the case study.

In the Azores case study, several mitigation measures to the Landing Obligation were assessed for the bottom hook-and-line fisheries. The main technical measures analysed hook size and hook shape. Fishing experiments performed by the DiscardLess team proved that the J-hooks, currently used in the fishery, are better than circle hooks to limit deep-water shark bycatch. The main tactical measures included spatial and vertical/depth avoidance strategies. Spatial avoidance strategies appear of limited potential for blackspot seabream. For deep-water sharks, habitat suitability models showed large distribution, mostly influenced by depth, of most species, and some areas with high number of deep-water sharks. Some areas of high conflict (high number of zero TAC species and high fishing effort) could be identified. The large number of species included within the zero TAC limitation, and the high mobility of some species, render spatial avoidance measures difficult to implement. However, depth avoidance strategies could be more promising. The most promising measure to avoid unwanted catch appears to be the conversion of bottom longlining to handlining, which has also been ongoing for some years. Data collected as part of the DiscardLess project in the Azores were used to support requests for exemptions asked by the Regional Government of the Azores, which were granted in 2018.

In the Eastern Mediterranean Sea (Aegean Sea) case study, selectivity analyses have shown that both 40mm square and 50mm diamond meshes, compared to the 40mm diamond, would increase escapement and reduce discards. There seems to be little scope for avoidance strategies. Some feasibility analyses were performed for the use of discards at shore. Investigating options for small quantities of unwanted landings in small harbours. Two options were suggested: fishmeal/fishoil and silage, using

small mobile production plants. However, the initial investments costs are important and the expected returns are limited.

In the Western Mediterranean Sea (Balearic Islands / Gulf of Lions), the problem of small-sized fish is mainly related to hake, and discard rates for all other species under the LO are low, except for horse mackerel. Most trawlers from the Balearic Islands have already changed to 40 mm square mesh cod-end, but there is still scope for improving the fishery selectivity and avoid juveniles of hake and mackerel by changing the mesh size and shape or introducing other devices such as panels and grids. Spatial management is widely used and supported in the Mediterranean as a strategy to reduce unwanted catches. Fishers highly support the mapping of juvenile hotspots based on scientific knowledge. DiscardLess developed a number of spatial models in this area, and made them available through Apps consultable via Internet. However, forecasting the impact of discard avoidance management on the sustainability of trawler fisheries is challenging, requiring data, time and trained human-resources.

In the Bay of Biscaye case study, most of the work performed by DiscardLess dealt with the use of unwanted catches in the value chain. A catalogue of more than 30 different utilisations was published online, and a systematic approach was developed for a rapid appraisal of which of the possible utilisations might be preferable in a case-by-case approach, depending on the quantity, quality and variability of the expected volumes of unwanted catches, of the existing and required infrastructures and logistics, and of the potential market demand. Some trials were conducted, producing e.g. fish pulp and hydrolysates out of unwanted mackerel and juvenile hake brought to land. Different options for the adequate handling of unwanted catches onboard were proposed, and an automatic system at shore for the identification and classification of unwanted fish that would be landed iced and preserved as normal catches was developed and successfully tested. Some cost-efficient DNA tests for the rapid detection of the presence/absence of a species in a mix were also developed.

The mixed nature of the species targeted by demersal fisheries **in the Celtic Sea case study** results in numerous challenges with the introduction of the Landing Obligation. It is likely that a combination of improved gear selectivity and the adoption of alternative fishing strategies will be required to avoid some of the unwanted catches, and to maximise on fishing opportunities under the LO. There is certainly no one-size fits all solution, and it is likely that gear and behaviour adaptations will mitigate some, but not all problems with choke species and <MCRS fish. DiscardLess provided resources in the form of the selectivity manual and mapping apps for the Celtic Sea, but further collaborations with industry will be required to ensure that future developments of mapping applications meet the needs of interested stakeholders in appropriate formats and time frames. By sharing information on occurrences of undersize fish or spawning aggregations for example, coupled with the information provided in the maps developed in this project, fishers should be much better equipped to avoid choke species and juvenile fish. A major problem in the Celtic Sea remains that due to quota allocation rules as well as stock status, all Member States encounter choke issues, while TAC is globally undershot for a number of species. There is thus some potential for management measures to help mitigate the impacts of the LO.

In the **Eastern English Channel case study** as well, the mixed nature of the fisheries results in numerous challenges with the introduction of the Landing Obligation. One of the main obstacle to gear selectivity improvement is the diversity of species (with large differences in size, shape, market value and management regime), which have made attempts to improve gear selectivity little conclusive in the

area. Some „challenge“ experiments to test the Landing Obligation in real conditions showed issues in increasing workload and storage capacity onboard. DiscardLess performed numerous interviews and studies dedicated to the mapping of unwanted catches including some user-friendly maps apps. Fishermen engaged in collaboration for designing adequate knowledge platforms and scenarios given their limited sets of options for changing fishing zones, given the large amount of other usages of the maritime space in the area.

In the **North Sea/West of Scotland case study**, many different DMS analyses were conducted, but mainly involving desk studies and laboratory experiments rather than actual trials at sea. Major progresses in knowledge on gear selectivity was brought together and shared, including the publication of numerous factsheets on selective devices and some in-depth analyses of how and why the various elements of a trawls modify selectivity by affecting fish behaviour. Extensive experiments of the use of light were conducted, in order to test the avoidance/attraction reactions of fish to different types of light (color, intensity, flash etc). The results demonstrate some differences in behaviour between different species of fish, which could be a promising avenue for improving catch composition. Several studies were published advancing knowledge on the spatial distribution of choke species and unwanted catches, not least using fine-scale fisheries data coming from different previous Danish pilot trials involving Electronic Monitoring and weighting-packing at sea. Regarding the valoriation of unwanted catches in the value chain, a project was run in collaboration with the harbour of Hanstholm (DK), which established new facilities for the storage and delivery of fish in 2017. At present, most unwanted catches and rest raw products are used for feed in the mink farms. The project also foresaw initially the rebuilding of the processing deck of a trawler, but the discard levels in that fishery remain limited and not worth the investment. Finally, a large part of the work performed by DiscardLess in this case study related to the issue of Monitoring, Control and Surveillance. This included both the publication of various studies on experiences and progresses with Fully Documented Fisheries and Electronic Monitoring, and major progresses achieved on the use of DNA technology for the characterisation of species in a mix (e.g. bulk or silage) and the quantification of the relative biomass of each species. This represents a promising break-through for the control and traceability of unwanted catches in the value chain.

Alltogether, important progresses in scientific knowledge has been achieved in a number of topics, including e.g. fish behaviour (swimming, escapement and reaction to light), fish mortality and survival, fine-scale spatial distribution of key species, handling and flesh properties of a number of different fish species, DNA characterisation etc. As such, it must be recognised that the landing Obligation has triggered significant advances in fundamental biological, ecological and technological knowledge, way beyond the state of the art at the time of the reform of the Common Fishery Policy in 2013. It is certain that this research activity would not have taken place without the political pressure to reduce discards.

However, in spite of these intense scientific and technical analyses, it is obvious that the discarding issue has not been solved yet. The complexity of the issue is immense, and there are still many technical, economic, social, cultural, psychological, institutional and political barriers that hinder the achievement of the objectives of the landing obligation. There are thus no simple and unique „one-size-fits-all“

technical solutions that would solve all issues and without economic impact. But there are many small steps that can be taken, which individually can contribute to reducing discards.

Box 1: Highlights

- In all case studies, new knowledge have been developed about the possible technical and tactical approaches to reduce discards and/or to best utilise them in the value chain
- There is no simple and unique technical solutions that would solve all issues and without economic impact. But there are many small steps that can be taken, which individually can contribute to reducing discards
- A number of approaches are specific to a given issue in a given case study, but there are also many commonalities and some developments are of interest at a much wider scale than the case study
- The landing Obligation has triggered significant progresses in scientific knowledge on a number of topics, including e.g. fish behaviour (swimming, escapement and reaction to light), fine-scale spatial distribution of key species, handling and flesh properties of a number of different fish species, DNA characterisation etc
- Important efforts have been made to make all this new knowledge easily available, easily understandable and easily shareable, through the public sharing of information via the DiscardLess website, including popular documents such as Discard Mitigation Toolbox, short reports, videos and powerpoint presentations.

Box 2: The Methods/Approaches followed

- Synthesis of deliverables from Work Packages 3 (Gear Technology), 4 (Fishing strategies), 5 (onboard handling) and 6 (products to the value chain) compiled by case studies
- Additional references where appropriate

Box 3: How these results can be used and by whom

These sections by case studies will be made as individual chapters and published on <http://www.discardless.eu/where-do-we-work>, allowing for a regional synthetic overview of the knowledge available.

This is of interest for all actors in a region, stakeholders and policy makers, in the frame of the regionalisation of the CFP, to

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1 Introduction

1.1 Objective of this deliverable and link with other deliverables

This deliverable provides an overview of the various Discard Mitigation Strategies (DMS) that have been analysed and investigated in the various case studies. The DMSs are proposed and examined as case specific approaches to support the implementation of the European Landing Obligation (LO). They represent potential approaches to reduce unwanted catches through fishing gear technology (WP3) and changes in fishing strategies (WP4), and to use unavoidable unwanted catches by finding efficient solutions for onboard handling (WP5) and market uses (WP6).

This deliverable represents a synthesis of the work developed in these four “innovation” Work Packages, summarised by region. The technical details of the various approaches can thus be found in the corresponding deliverables from these WPs² and where applicable, in scientific publications³. Annual updates of the progresses by case studies were also reported.⁴

² <http://www.discardless.eu/deliverables>

³ http://www.discardless.eu/scientific_publications

⁴ <http://www.discardless.eu/where-do-we-work>.

This overview by case study covering WPs 3 to 6 is complemented by other cross-case synthesis deliverables. The changes actually observed in the fisheries between 2015 and 2018 are described in D1.4 in terms of stocks and ecosystems (WP1), and in D2.4 in terms of fishers' perceptions and management developments (WP2). The potential impacts of alternative management scenarios and of some of the DMS summarised here have been modelled and described in D1.3 (ecosystem impacts) and D2.3 (bioeconomic impacts).

The various meetings with stakeholders are reported in D8.7. Finally, important management aspects of the LO by regions have been reported in a number of Policy Briefs (D7.1, D7.2, D7.5 and D7.7)⁵ and in Deliverable D4.4.

1.2 Overviews of case studies

The DiscardLess project built on nine cases studies, that were selected based on a number of criteria. Importantly, they had good records of accomplishment of collaboration between fishers, managers and scientists. This was fundamental to the participatory approach of the project, since the only route to long-lasting discard reductions is through such collaboration. A further condition for EU cases was that there are substantial unwanted catches, which means that the landing obligation is likely to have a major impact on such fisheries. Together, the chosen cases provide a diverse panel of challenges and specificities across métiers, geographical regions and scale (industrial to artisanal/small scale). With this in mind, the case studies selected were the Azores, eastern Mediterranean, western Mediterranean, Bay of Biscay, the Celtic Sea, the eastern Channel, North Sea and West of Scotland, Iceland and the Barents Sea (Figure 1.1). Obviously, many of the case studies include substantial focus on trawl fisheries, since mixed demersal fisheries with towed gears are usually little selective and have traditionally had a higher record of discards and unwanted catches. However, most of the case studies also include important fleet segments catching the same species with other types of gears than trawls. These were monitored and analysed as well in the project, offering interesting bases for comparison. Additionally, the first case study is entirely dedicated to a fishing region without trawls.

Figure 1.1. Geographical coverage of DiscardLess case studies (in color) and partner countries (dark grey).

⁵ <http://www.discardless.eu/home/presentation/policy-briefs-and-mitigation-toolbox>

The case studies did not contribute equally to all WPs, as relevant issues and the state of knowledge differs widely across regions. Rather, these contrasted case studies were used to study a diversity of approaches. The two non-EU cases (Iceland and Barents Sea) were mainly addressed as references for comparing with the ongoing developments in the EU CFP, in particular to draw on the experiences and approaches these countries have developed in the course of the four decades with a discard ban. This experience has been important for us and has been described in many DiscardLess outcomes. These countries are not subjected to the European LO but to national legislation with relevance for discard management, and which is not directly comparable to that of the LO. The work pursued in relation to these case studies have been reported elsewhere⁶ and will not be addressed further in this report.

All EU case studies performed assessment analyses in WP1-2 and governance analyses in WP7, following the same timeframe (see corresponding deliverables). They also all contributed to providing selectivity data and analyses in WP3. But their contribution to other aspects of the DMS toolbox varied. During the first year of *DiscardLess* (in 2015), priority was given to develop the generic aspects of the DMS toolbox and populate it with initial results, before the 2016 entry into force of the landing obligation in the first demersal Atlantic and North Sea fisheries. This implied that the kick-off development work for the different WPs took primary place where data and knowledge were best advanced and, for EU cases, where policy needs were the most urgent (Table 1.1). During the rest of the project, these initial developments were consolidated through application and feedback testing on other case studies following the implementation steps of the landing obligation. The toolbox evolved continuously, building progressively on experiences across fisheries.

*Table 1.1 Case Studies type and contributions to initial DMS toolbox development (M1-24). *: includes important small scale fisheries.*

Area	Fisheries type	Contribution to <i>initial</i> toolbox
Azores	Deep Sea Hooks and lines *	WP3 + WP4
Eastern Med.	Mixed *	WP3 + WP4
Western Med.	Mixed demersal *	WP3 + WP4
Bay of Biscay	Mixed demersal *	WP3 + WP4 + WP5 + WP6
Celtic Sea	Mixed demersal	WP3 + WP4
Eastern Channel	Mixed demersal *	WP4
North Sea-West of Scotland	Mixed demersal	WP3 + WP4 + WP5 + WP6

In the following sections the DMS strategies are presented for each European case study, providing a overview of the case study and its objectives, current discard reduction practices suggested by stakeholders, adaptation of gear technology, adaptation of fishing strategies, best use of unwanted catches where relevant and summary and conclusions by case study. A discussion integrates the main findings in terms of DMSs across the European case studies and concludes the report.

⁶ Various aspects of the Icelandic case is described in deliverables 5.1, 5.2, 5.3, 5.4; 6.1, 6.2, 6.3, 6.5 and in 7.2. Similarly, various aspects of the Norwegian case study is addressed in deliverables 5.1, 5.2, 5.3, and 7.2.

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2 Discards Mitigation Strategies in the Azores case study

2.1 Overview of the case study and initial work objectives

The **Azores case study** focused on deep sea bottom and drifting hook-and-line fisheries and represented a non-trawl fisheries example in the project. Trawling is forbidden throughout most of the region's EEZ (EU regulation) and hook-and-line is the most important fishery, both in terms of landed value, number of boats and jobs. The drifting bottom longline targeting black scabbard fish is a very recent fishery, still in an experimental phase in the Azores with limited activity and requiring further discard baseline knowledge. Discards from these fisheries include significant volumes of at least ten species of deep-water sharks, many of which are listed in the IUCN Red List of vulnerable, endangered and critically endangered species and with zero-quota under the CFP. In addition to avoiding catching these species (e.g. through fishing tactics), adverse fishing effects on these stocks can be minimized by improved handling of caught sharks to ensure their increased survival upon release. In the Azores case study, DiscardLess intended to evaluate the efficacy of technical and spatial management measures to reduce unwanted by-catch of deep-water sharks, increase survival of released sharks, and meet the requirements of the landing obligation and the CFP. Specific activities include improved fisheries data collection and availability (WP1-2), deployment of fisheries observers (WP1), ecosystem and species distribution modeling (WP1-4), circle hooks fishing experiments (WP3), biotelemetry (WP4), and a guide for the easy identification and good handling practices of deep-sea sharks (WP3).

This deliverable reports on the outcomes of WP3 and WP4 for this case study.

2.2 The Fishers story – documenting discard reduction practices suggested by stakeholders

Twenty-one fisheries stakeholders from the Portugal-Azores were interviewed (Bottom deep-water longliners and handliners), regarding their own ideas of why they discard and what they currently think about it and do to avoid unwanted catch. The results are described in Deliverable D4.1, finalised in April 2017 (Reid et al., 2017), including also an analysis of the commonalities in responses across various regions and fisheries and, conversely, those that are more specific to a given case. The results of this task have also been brought online into a visual display on http://www.discardless.eu/fishermen_story.

The answers received from the Azorean stakeholders were as follows:

2.2.1 Causes and levels of discarding:

- The fishing gears are very selective, especially the handline, and discard amounts are generally very low.
- Discarding mostly happens because of regulations: catch of undersized (<MCRS) individuals being the first reason, followed by low market value and quota.
- Given that the fishing gears are selective and the market is diversified, discarding due to lack of commercial value occurs in relatively low proportions.
- Most fishers use part of the unwanted catch for bait or for the crew's own consumption.
- The potential choke species are alfonsinos (*Beryx spp.*) and blackspot seabream (*Pagellus bogaraveo*).

- the implementation of the LO on zero TAC species such as deep-water sharks, that are a common bycatch of these fisheries, that long remained uncertain, raised concerns of choke species.
- Most fishers return all alive fish to the water. Survivability is assumed to be high for several species, especially in the handline fishery.

2.2.2 Current methods used to avoid unwanted catch

Technical (Gear)

- The hook size is believed by fishers to be the most effective way to reduce the amount of small individuals in the catch. The legal hook size (n^o9 – 12mm gap size) is already large, and some fishers even use larger hooks.
- Some fishers also use Spanish hooks (slightly curved J-hooks) to reduce unwanted catch, with unproved efficacy.
- Several fishers have recently changed fishing gears from bottom longlining to handlining, which is a more selective and cost-effective fishery, that also offers more time to carefully handle the catch.

Tactical (Strategies)

- Some fishers avoid specific areas because they know there are high concentrations of small fishes. However, most fishers argue that it is very difficult to identify such areas, as in most areas the small and large fishes are mixed.
- Whenever they catch small individuals, the large majority of fishers change fishing grounds. This change can occur within the same day for the handliners because the fishing gear is more flexible, while it is undertaken within the following days by the longliners.
- Fishers adapt their fishing depth according to what they are targeting. When fishing deeper, they would usually catch less but larger individuals of blackspot seabreams. When fishing deeper, they would also catch more alfonosinos and deep-water sharks.
- Some fishers avoid fishing at night because there is more predation on the catch.
- In the islands where fishers have an individual quota for blackspot seabream, it is common that fishers change target species for some months in order to keep their quota for the end of the year when the price for blackspot seabream is higher

2.2.3 Interest expressed in additional methods to avoid unwanted catch

Technical (Gear)

- Few fishers would agree to increase the hook size even more, but they do not believe it would make a significantly reduce unwanted catch.
- Most handliners promote the use of this type of fishing gear, and believed the longliners should convert to handlining.

Tactical (Strategies)

- Most fishers agree with the biological closure that has been implemented since 2015 for the blackspot seabream, even if this measure does not contribute to avoidance of unwanted catch but rather to their own quota management. Yet many fishers argue that the closure is not at the

appropriate time and should be changed to when the fish actually spawn. Some further argue that the closure should be expanded to all species, as otherwise they keep fishing and catch blackspot seabream anyway, but for such a closure they would need financial compensation..

Management changes

- Fishers in São Miguel, the only island where the quota for blackspot seabream is collective, would like to change for ITQ. In the other islands, fishers mostly agree with the current quota system even if the sharing is considered by most as unfair.
- A multi-species (for blackspot seabream and splendid alfonsino) and multi-annual (2-3 years) quota that would allow them to deal with the stock natural variability could help [supported by 1 fisher].
- Some fishers are in favour of controlling the number of vessels. They argue that the deep-water fisheries are already at their maximum, and that the number of fishing vessels should be distributed according to the resource capacities, eventually by developing new fisheries.

2.2.4 No support for the following proposed methods to avoid unwanted catch

Technical (Gear)

- There is no support for a reduction of the total number of hooks for longliners because it would result in a decrease of the commercial catch, and because they consider that the only efficient measure to reduce the amount of small fish in the catch is the hook size.
- Fishers were not interested in using circular hooks or shark repellents to avoid the catch of deep-water sharks. They do not see the point as, for most of them, the catch of deep-water sharks is only occasional and most sharks are released alive.

Tactical (Strategies)

- A reduction of the soak time is not supported by the bottom deep-water longliners as it would result in a decrease in the catch amount, and as it is a lot of work to deploy and haul back the gear, it does not worth the effort.
- Fishers believe that real time closures would not be efficient in the Azores as the fish populations are too short-term and variable “the whole EEZ would have to be closed”.
- Most fishers consider that there is already enough closed areas and they do not want more, as it would result in more fishing effort on the other already limited fishing grounds, and it would not be efficient to avoid the unwanted catch as the populations and ages are mixed and their distribution is highly variable.
- Information sharing only occasionally occur between close friends and family members. But, in general there is little trust among fishers and they are not willing to share information even on where the small fishes are, because that would result in increased competition on the good fishing grounds.

2.3 Adaptation of gear technology

2.3.1 survivability of discard species in relation to handling practices

The main focus of the Azores case study on this topic is to evaluate the survivability of discard species in relation to handling practices.

An observer program was launched in January/February 2017 to collect detailed information on the condition of the fishes when they come onboard (including barotrauma), the position of the hook (mouth hooked versus gut hooked) and the condition of the fishes upon release (e.g. vigorous swimming versus dead or moribund). This observer program lasted 12 months, with the data providing some information allowing comparison of survivability of discards in handline versus longline fishing. The data was used in 2018 to support exemptions for blackspot seabream at the Regional Government of the Azores request. Data analysis to be finished and published during year 4.

The data from the standard tagging programme carried out during the annual demersal scientific surveys and from the electronic tagging performed on dedicated experiments has been used during year 2 to look at potential survivability of released fishes. Preliminary results show a surprisingly high survivability (>2/3) of released individuals caught with handlines including quota species (e.g. *P. bogaraveo*) and deep-sea sharks such as *D. licha* (Table 2.1). In 2018, complementary telemetric experiments were conducted in conjunction with the hook selectivity experiments (task 3.4 below) in order to have some information allowing comparison of survivability on other deep-water sharks. This analysis will be complemented with survivability analysis on the standard tagging database.

A best handling practices manual is being finalized and is expected to be fully finished during year 4. The objective is to provide fishers with tools towards achieving increased survival of the released discard species, specifically for vulnerable / zero quota deep-sea sharks. This manual is being developed in conjunction with the deep-water shark ID manual that aims to help fishers easily identify deep-water shark at the species level.

Table 2.1 – Summary of survivability per species as inferred from acoustic tagging experiments in the Azores; survival reports acoustically ‘recaptured’ tagged animals after a minimum 8 days after release (Afonso and Fontes, unpublished data).

Species	Scientific name	Tagged Survival		
		n	n	%
Blackspot seabream	<i>Pagellus bogaraveo</i>	155	105	67
Kitefin shark	<i>Dalathias licha</i>	25	24	96
Wreckfish	<i>Poyprion americanus</i>	2	1	50
Bueshark	<i>Prionace gauca</i>	37	37	100
Tope shark	<i>Galeorhinus galeus</i>	2	2	100
Hammerhead shark	<i>Sphyrna zygaena</i>	17	15	88
Porgy	<i>Pagrus pagrus</i>	27	26	96
Dusky grouper	<i>Epinephelus marginatus</i>	11	11	100
White trevally	<i>Pseudocaranx dentex</i>	32	29	90
Parrotfish	<i>Sparisoma cretense</i>	22	22	100

2.3.2 Circle hook experiments

Circle hook experiments carried out in a number of pelagic longline fisheries around the world received promising results for bycatch mitigation. While their effect on the catchability differ among species, the

closed shape of the circle hooks results in shallower, less internal hooking than the J-hooks commonly used by commercial longliners (Carruthers et al., 2009; Godin et al., 2012; Pacheco et al., 2011). Individuals caught on circle hooks would then have a higher probability of post-release survival (Kerstetter and Graves, 2006).

To our knowledge, circle hooks had however never been tested on deep-water sharks. A study was thus carried out in the Azores using circle hooks vs J-hooks to test how hook type affect: i) the catchability of deep-water sharks, ii) the hooking position, and iii) the condition of the individuals.

The materials, methods and results are presented in details in deliverable D 3.4 (O'Neill et al., 2018).

Six fishing sets were performed onboard a commercial fishing vessel in January and February 2018, on a depth ranging from 882 to 1368 meters. Data collected on the catch included species, hook type and hooking position, vitality of the individual when the gear is hauled back (0 = dead, 1 = moribund, 2 = stunned, 3 = vigorous), lesions, handling by crew. All sharks were measured, sexed, and maturity stage was recorded and DNA samples were taken whenever the species identification was uncertain.

A total of 267 sharks belonging to 11 different species were caught during the fishing experiments. A high variability in CPUE (number of individuals caught per 1000 hooks) of deep-water sharks was observed but in average CPUE were significantly higher with circle hooks than with J-hooks (Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1 Effect of hook type (C =circle; J-hooks) on shark catch

No significant differences were thus observed between circle and J hooks, regarding either hooking position (mainly in the mouth in both cases) or vitality index.

In conclusion, while circle hooks received promising results for the mitigation of sharks in the pelagic longline fisheries in other fisheries worldwide, our experiments of circle hooks on deep-water sharks suggest that the J-hook currently in use in the deep-sea bottom longline fisheries in the Azores are the most suitable to limit deep-water shark bycatch.

Our results suggested as well that the probability of post-release survival of deep-water sharks could be high, with around 20% of the individuals considered vigorous and around 40% considered stunned upon release.

2.4 Adaptation of fishing strategies: The Scientists story – identification of locations, times and practices to fish to avoid unwanted catch

The results for the Azores are documented in details in the Chapter 12 of Deliverable D4.3 (Reid et al., 2018).

Habitat Suitability Models of 15 species of deep-water sharks and rays were developed based on survey and observer data for the Azores case study. Maps predicting occurrence by species and combined occurrence of all species at the range of the whole Azores EEZ were developed to help fishers identify areas they should avoid to limit the risks of catching those species (Figure 2.2).

For 6 species with the highest amount of available data, models of abundance were also developed. The resulting maps of abundance complement the previous information with areas of higher shark abundance that fishers should avoid.

Figure 2.2. Deep-water elasmobranchs richness, based on predicted suitable habitats of the 10 modelled species.

Composite maps combining the predicted suitable habitats of the main zero TAC shark species caught by the bottom longliners on one side, and by the deep-water drifting longliners on the other side were

created to better highlight for those two specific groups of fishers the main areas to be avoided (Figure 2.3 and Figure 2.4).

Figure 2.3. Overlap of predicted suitable habitats of the main zero TAC species caught by drifting deep-water longliners (DLL).

Figure 2.4. Overlap of predicted suitable habitats of the main zero TAC species caught by deep-water bottom longliners (BLL).

Those maps were further overlapped with map of the distribution of fishing effort of the bottom longliners and handliners based on VMS data. Using Jenks breaks, we classified both fishing effort and richness (number of zero TAC species in the example below) as low or high. We could then identify areas of high conflict (high fishing and high richness) that should be avoided, and areas to monitor (low fishing but high richness; Figure 2.5).

Figure 2.5. Spatial classification of the overlap between number of zero TAC species (derived from presence/absence models) and fishing effort of bottom longliners and handliners, in the Azores EEZ.

This information was completed by fine-scale information on shark spatial and vertical movements derived from acoustic and satellite telemetry data from 2 species: kitefin shark *Dalatias licha*, and bluntnose sixgill shark *Hexanchus griseus*. The telemetry data was completed in 2018 with 6 individuals of leafscale gulper shark *Centrophorus squamosus* tagged with miniPat satellite tags. Preliminary results suggest that, contrary to kitefin and sixgill sharks that are highly resident and stay around island slopes and surrounding seamounts, leafscale gulper sharks travel very long distances (Figure 2.6). Telemetry data help identify potential essential habitats for those species. Our study highlights that areas to avoid fishing and limits in fishing depths at some time of the day, due to marked diel migrations for most species, could be promising mitigation measures for some species of deep-water elasmobranchs but not for all.

Figure 2.6. ARGOS data on the locations of the deployments and pop-up of satellite tags deployed on the six individuals of leascale gulper sharks (XAR 01-06) tagged in 2018.

2.5 Summary- conclusions

The studies performed by the DiscardLess team for the Azores case study assessed the potential of several mitigation measures to the Landing Obligation for the bottom hook-and-line fisheries.

The main technical measures included hook size and hook shape. The legal hook size (n⁹, gap width 12 mm) already implemented in the fishery helps to avoid catching juveniles but the recent increase in MLS (from 25 cm since 2005 to 30 cm since 2010, and up to 33 cm since 2016) without other incentives to increase fishing selectivity, has led to higher proportion of <MLS individuals in the catch, and hook selectivity has turned maladjusted. An increase of the legal hook size to size n⁸ is currently under discussion. Fishing experiments performed by the DiscardLess team proved that the J-hooks, currently used in the fishery, are better than circle hooks to limit deep-water shark bycatch since they have lower catchability and give similar results for hooking position or at-vessel mortality (O'Neill et al., 2018: DiscardLess deliverable D3.4).

The main tactical measures included spatial and vertical/depth avoidance strategies. Spatial avoidance strategies appear of limited potential for blackspot seabream as this species perform ontogenic migrations with juveniles in coastal and shallowest areas, while the medium/large-sized individuals occur in deeper areas (Menezes 1996, Afonso et al 2012). The avoidance of areas with more unwanted catch (juveniles) is difficult because of limited alternative fishing grounds at suitable fishing depths. For deep-water sharks, habitat suitability models showed large distribution, mostly influenced by depth, of most species, and some areas with high number of deep-water sharks (Reid et al 2018: DiscardLess deliverable D4.3). Some areas of high conflict (high number of zero TAC species and high fishing effort) could be identified. The large number of species included within the zero TAC limitation, and the high mobility of some species, render spatial avoidance measures difficult to implement. Depth avoidance

strategies could be more promising as the most species of deep-water sharks occur in depths greater than the ones commonly fished; and as a matter of fact fishers already use this knowledge and fish shallower to avoid deep-water sharks. They also do to avoid *Beryx* when the quota is reached/closed while keeping fishing for blackspot seabream (Reid et al 2017: DiscardLess deliverable D4.1).

The most promising measure to avoid unwanted catch appears to be the conversion of bottom longlining to handlining. In recent years, many longliners have converted to handlining. This conversion was mainly driven by regulatory and economic incentives, but it also turns highly suitable in the context of the Landing Obligation. Indeed, as a more active fishing technique (shorter soak times, greater flexibility, higher potential for survival, etc.) handlining appears better suited to avoid unwanted catch and improve post-release survival. The catch of deep-water sharks is also nearly inexistent using handlines as: i) the handline is a weaker fishing gear, more likely to break if a shark get caught, ii) handlines usually fish shallower than bottom longlines, iii) soak times are much shorter with handlines.

Data collected as part of the DiscardLess project in the Azores were used to support requests of exemptions asked by the Regional Government of the Azores for: i) blackspot seabream (*Pagellus bogaraveo*), a survival exemption was asked and granted (EC 2018/2033), ii) alfonsinos (*Beryx spp.*) and greater forkbeard (*Phycis blennoides*), *de minimis* exemptions were asked and granted (EC 2018/2033).

2.6 Published references and presentations in conferences

Papers

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- Fauconnet L., Pham C., Batista Aguiar R., Canha A., Afonso P., Das D., Machete M., Reis D., Morato T. O by-catch de tubarões de profundidade nos Açores: impacto e medidas de mitigação. Fórum internacional das pescas dos Açores, 7th June 2016, Horta (Portugal).
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- Fauconnet L., Das D., Catarino D., Giacomello E., Fontes J., Morato T., Afonso P. At-vessel mortality and post-release survival of deep-water sharks: insights from the Azores hook-and-line fisheries. Oral presentation at "ICES ASC", 24-28 September 2018, Hamburg (Germany).
- Fauconnet L., Das D., Catarino D., Giacomello E., Fontes J., Morato T., Afonso P. Is it possible to avoid deep-water sharks in the Azores hook-and-line fisheries? Oral presentation at DiscardLess Science-Policy conference, Copenhagen (Denmark), 30/01/2019.

3 Discards Mitigation Strategies in the Eastern Mediterranean case study

3.1 Overview of the case study and initial work objectives

The **Eastern Mediterranean Sea** case study covers the NW Aegean Sea mixed demersal trawl fishery targeting a multitude of species. Discard ratios are high (>40%) as is fishing pressure on juveniles. High grading also occurs. The approach in DiscardLess builds on existing knowledge of unwanted catches in the studied marine ecosystem (WP1) by: i) working closely with stakeholders and local fishers to develop bio-economic scenarios to cope with the socio-economic consequences of the landing obligation (WP2), ii) reviewing and appraising existing solutions in terms of selectivity (WP3). Initially it was envisaged to disclose essential fish habitats and grounds with high concentrations of unwanted catches in collaboration with fishers and couple that with scientific information to minimise discards (WP4), however this was not possible to be done due to lack of time series data. The most reliable source of information for Greece is the fisheries data collection scheme under data collection regulation / data collection framework (DCR/DCF) (EU 2000, 2008), but these EU regulations have only been implemented sporadically (from 2003 to 2006, 2008 and 2014). An important consequence is that the impact of each fleet segment is unknown, and the state of the Greek stocks is not assessed by the relevant bodies (Machias et al., 2016)⁷.

In addition to the above initial objectives, the Eastern Mediterranean Case study was chosen as a text case for transferring and applying some of the findings of WP5 ("Optimal use of unwanted catches" cluster). The solutions for dealing with unwanted catches should be based on, in order of priority: avoidance, selection and utilization. The Eastern Mediterranean Sea case study focused also on the last priority, the utilization of Unavoidable Unwanted Catches (UUC) and Rest Raw Material (RRM) and contributed to WP5 with input in the form of transferring knowledge, experiences and solution/product development in regards to utilisation of unavoidable unwanted catches. The above involvement in WPs 1-5 aimed to advance good practice and more efficient regional discard mitigation strategies (WP7) and transfer the acquired knowledge of discard mitigation strategies to Greek Stakeholders (WP8).

This deliverable reports thus on the outcomes of WPs 3 to 5 for this case study.

3.1.1 Peculiarities of the LO in the Mediterranean Sea

If someone would like to summarise in a paragraph which species are subject to the LO in the Mediterranean, from approximately 17,000 species occurring in the Mediterranean Sea (of which 714 are fish species⁸, 2,239 are crustaceans and 2,113 molluscs⁹), only up to 200 fish and shellfish species present commercial interest and are targeted by the fishing fleets¹⁰. The LO concerns 20 fish species, 4

⁷ Machias Athanassios, Konstantinos Tsagarakis and Manos Matsaganis (2016). Greek fisheries and the economic crisis: structural analogies. *Ethics Sci Environ Polit*, Vol. 16: 19–23, doi: 10.3354/esep00170

⁸ Dimarchopoulou D, Stergiou KI, Tsikliras AC (2017). Gap analysis on the biology of Mediterranean marine fishes. *PLoS ONE* 12(4): e0175949. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0175949>

⁹ Coll M, Piroddi C, Steenbeek J, Kaschner K, Ben Rais Lasram F, et al. (2010). The Biodiversity of the Mediterranean Sea: Estimates, Patterns, and Threats. *PLoS ONE* 5(8): e11842. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0011842.

¹⁰ Stergiou KI, Somarakis S, Triantafyllou G, Tsiaras KP, Giannoulaki M, Petihakis G, Machias A, Tsikliras AC (2016). Trends in productivity and biomass yields in the Mediterranean Sea large marine ecosystem during climate change. *Environmental Development* 17 (Suppl. 1): 57-74.

crustaceans and 3 bivalve molluscs (as they have a minimum landing size in Annex III of [Council Regulation \(EC\) No.1967/2006](#)), Since 1st January 2015, the LO applies to small pelagics i.e. anchovy (*Engraulis encrasicolus*), sardine (*Sardina pilchardus*), mackerels (*Scomber* spp.), horse mackerels (*Trachurus* spp.). It also applies to a single large pelagic species, i.e. the bluefin tuna (*Thunnus thynnus*), as it is subject to a catch limit – quota. Currently (from 1st January 2017) it applies to the species that define a fishery, i.e. 4 species in the Eastern Mediterranean case study¹¹. Since 1st January 2019 the LO applies to all other species in the fishery which have a minimum size in Reg.1967/2006.

With the Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2018/161 of 23 October 2017¹², in the small pelagic mid-water trawl and purse seines fisheries set out in the Western Mediterranean Sea, small pelagic fisheries in the South Eastern Mediterranean Sea (GFCM Geographical Sub-Areas (GSA) 15, 16, 19, 20, 22 23 and 25 for mid-water pelagic trawls and GFCM GSA 25 for purse seines targeting anchovy, sardine, mackerel and horse mackerel) and small pelagic fisheries in the Adriatic Sea, up to 5 % of the total annual catches of any species subject to a minimum size may be discarded. In the small pelagic purse seines fisheries of small pelagic fisheries in the Malta Island and South of Sicily, small pelagic fisheries in the Aegean Sea and Crete Island (GFCM GSAs 22 and 23 for purse seines targeting anchovy, sardine, mackerel and horse mackerel) and small pelagic fisheries in the Southern Adriatic and Ionian Sea (GFCM GSAs 18, 19 and 20 for purse seines targeting anchovy, sardine, mackerel and horse mackerel), up to 3 % of the total annual catches of any species subject to a minimum size may be discarded. This Regulation has entered into force on 1st January 2018 and shall apply until 31st December 2020. Paragraphs 1 and 2 of the Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2018/161 of 23 October 2017 shall apply by way of derogation from Article 15(1) of Regulation (EU) No 1380/2013.

Before the LO, in the Mediterranean, a marine organism which was smaller than the minimum size specified in Annex III ("undersized marine organisms") of Council Regulation (EC) No 1967/2006 of 21 December 2006 concerning management measures for the sustainable exploitation of fishery resources in the Mediterranean Sea, it was forbidden to be caught, retained on board, transhipped, landed, transferred, stored, sold, displayed or offered for sale. So management efforts and fishing activities in the Mediterranean, before and after the application of the LO, should be regulated in order to ensure that catches of species mentioned in Annex III are minimal. From the discard data presented in Table 3.1, it is evident that in the Mediterranean, apart from species that are included in Annex III of Council Regulation (EC) No. 1967/2006, there are numerous other species that are also discarded but are not included in the LO (all species that are not in bold characters).

¹¹ Species with a minimum landing size in the Mediterranean that are subject to the landing obligation from January 1, 2017, pursuant to art. 15 point 1b are:

- All the geographical areas: hake (*Merluccius merluccius*) - red mullets (*Mullus* spp.).
- GSA 17- GSA 18: hake (*Merluccius merluccius*) - red mullets (*Mullus* spp.) - common sole (*Solea solea*).
- GSAs 15, 16, 19, 20, 22, 23, 25: hake (*Merluccius merluccius*) - red mullets (*Mullus* spp.) - deep rose shrimp (*Parapenaeus longirostris*).

¹² See: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018R0161&from=EN>

Table 3.1. Discard data for Greece from the Data Collection Framework programme for the year 2015. The ratio Rd/c is the ratio of discards (d) to the total catch (c), the 95% confidence level of the estimate CI and the relative estimation errors ER at the 95% confidence level per fishing gear and GFCM Geographical Sub-Area. GSA-20: Eastern Ionian Sea, GSA-22: Aegean Sea (includes Case study area), GSA-23: Crete. Species with bold characters are the ones included in Annex III ("undersized marine organisms") of Council Regulation (EC) No 1967/2006 of 21 December 2006.

Fishing gear	Area	Species	Rd/c	CI	RE
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Aspitrigla cuculus</i>	0.68	0.13	0.19
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Boops boops</i>	0.32	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Citharus linguatula</i>	0.82	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Diplodus annularis</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Eutrigla gurnardus</i>	0.16	0.01	0.03
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Galeus melastomus</i>	0.85	0.13	0.15
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Helicolenus dactylopterus</i>	0.44	0.09	0.21
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Lepidorhombus boscii</i>	0.18	0.28	1.61
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Lophius budegassa</i>	0.05	0.00	0.09
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>	0.03	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Micromesistius poutassou</i>	0.00	0.00	0.39
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	0.02	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Mullus surmuletus</i>	0.06	0.01	0.22
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Pagellus acarne</i>	0.81	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Pagellus bogaraveo</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	0.09	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Phycis blennoides</i>	0.22	0.08	0.36
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	0.98	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Sardinella aurita</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Scomber colias</i>	0.09	0.01	0.08
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	0.53	0.49	0.92
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Trigla lucerna</i>	0.13	0.00	0.03
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Loligo vulgaris</i>	0.00	0.00	0.03
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Aspitrigla cuculus</i>	0.29	0.01	0.02
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Galeus melastomus</i>	0.99	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Micromesistius poutassou</i>	0.07	0.00	0.03
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Raja clavata</i>	0.01	0.00	0.07
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Solea solea</i>	0.00	0.00	0.05
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	0.69	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Eledone moschata</i>	0.03	0.00	0.05
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Parapenaeus longirostris</i>	0.15	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Helicolenus dactylopterus</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>	0.13	0.00	0.02
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Raja clavata</i>	0.30	0.41	1.37
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Trigla lucerna</i>	0.35	0.06	0.18
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Solea solea</i>	0.01	0.00	0.05
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Sparus aurata</i>	0.19	0.01	0.03
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Spicara smaris</i>	0.89	0.03	0.04

OTB	GSA-20	Trachurus mediterraneus	0.65	0.01	0.02
OTB	GSA-20	Trachurus trachurus	0.69	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Trigloporus lastoviza</i>	0.07	0.00	0.05
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Trisopterus minutus</i>	0.09	0.00	0.03
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Zeusfaber</i>	0.09	0.00	0.04
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Sepia officinalis</i>	0.03	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Illex coindetii</i>	0.03	0.00	0.12
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Eidone spp</i>	0.08	0.00	0.02
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Squilla mantis</i>	0.64	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-20	Trachurus spp	0.50	0.49	0.98
OTB	GSA-20	Parapenaeus longirostris	0.09	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-20	<i>Melicertus kerathurus</i>	0.01	0.00	0.02
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Boops boops</i>	0.30	0.01	0.03
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Citharus linguatula</i>	0.55	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-22	Diplodus annularis	0.63	0.04	0.07
OTB	GSA-22	Diplodus vulgaris	0.13	0.06	0.46
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Eutrigla gurnardus</i>	0.37	0.01	0.04
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Helicolenus dactylopterus</i>	0.25	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Lepidorhombus boscii</i>	0.22	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Lophius budegassa</i>	0.03	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Lophius piscatorius</i>	0.03	0.00	0.09
OTB	GSA-22	Merluccius merluccius	0.04	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-22	Mullus barbatus	0.01	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-22	Pagellus acarne	0.76	0.01	0.01
OTB	GSA-22	Pagellus bogaraveo	0.66	0.01	0.01
OTB	GSA-22	Pagellus erythrinus	0.15	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Phycis blennoides</i>	0.23	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-22	Sardina pilchardus	0.98	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Sardinella aurita</i>	0.23	0.04	0.16
OTB	GSA-22	Scomber colias	0.52	0.01	0.02
OTB	GSA-22	Scomber scombrus	0.03	0.00	0.06
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	0.25	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-22	Sparus aurata	0.15	0.14	0.92
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Spicara maena</i>	0.90	0.09	0.10
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Spicara smarts</i>	0.18	0.01	0.07
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Squalus acantbias</i>	0.02	0.01	0.59
OTB	GSA-22	Trachurus mediterraneus	0.99	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Trigloporus lastoviza</i>	0.03	0.00	0.14
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Trisopterus minutus</i>	0.25	0.01	0.03
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Zeus faber</i>	0.04	0.00	0.02
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Sepia officinalis</i>	0.01	0.00	0.02
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Octopus vulgaris</i>	0.00	0.00	0.05
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Eidone cirrhosa</i>	0.03	0.02	0.58
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Loligo vulgaris</i>	0.01	0.00	0.01
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Illex coindetii</i>	0.04	0.00	0.00
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Squilla mantis</i>	0.08	0.00	0.02

OTB	GSA-22	<i>Nephrops norvegicus</i>	0.01	0.00	0.04
OTB	GSA-22	<i>Melicertus kerathurus</i>	0.00	0.00	0.03
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Aspitrigla cuculus</i>	0.55	0.03	0.05
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Boops boops</i>	0.02	0.00	0.03
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Citharus linguatula</i>	0.98	0.01	0.01
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i>	0.75	0.07	0.10
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Lophius budegassa</i>	0.03	0.00	0.14
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	0.01	0.00	0.04
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Pagellus acarne</i>	0.96	0.01	0.01
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	0.03	0.00	0.05
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Pagrus pagrus</i>	0.77	0.02	0.02
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Phycis blermoides</i>	0.54	0.07	0.13
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	0.35	0.08	0.23
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Scorpaena scrofa</i>	0.38	0.05	0.12
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	0.25	0.04	0.16
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Spicara smaris</i>	0.02	0.00	0.03
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	0.82	0.02	0.03
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Trigloporus lastoviza</i>	0.67	0.11	0.17
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Zeus faber</i>	0.00	0.00	0.29
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Eledone moschata</i>	0.00	0.00	0.09
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Illex coindetii</i>	0.07	0.01	0.08
OTB	GSA-23	<i>Parapenaeus longirostris</i>	0.03	0.00	0.09
PS	GSA-20	<i>Boops boops</i>	0.07	0.01	0.08
PS	GSA-20	<i>Citharus lingua tula</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
PS	GSA-20	<i>Diplodus annularis</i>	0.82	0.03	0.04
PS	GSA-20	<i>Diplodus vulgaris</i>	0.53	0.12	0.24
PS	GSA-20	<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i>	0.01	0.00	0.52
PS	GSA-20	<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	0.01	0.00	0.15
PS	GSA-20	<i>Mullus surmuletus</i>	0.03	0.01	0.29
PS	GSA-20	<i>Pagellus acarne</i>	0.56	0.48	0.87
PS	GSA-20	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	0.05	0.00	0.07
PS	GSA-20	<i>Sardinella aurita</i>	0.46	0.02	0.04
PS	GSA-20	<i>Scomber colias</i>	0.00	0.00	0.18
PS	GSA-20	<i>Trachurus mediterraneus</i>	0.55	0.07	0.13
PS	GSA-20	<i>Trigloporus lastoviza</i>	0.05	0.03	0.63
PS	GSA-22	<i>Boops boops</i>	0.00	0.00	0.55
PS	GSA-22	<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i>	0.01	0.00	0.09
PS	GSA-22	<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	0.09	0.09	0.99
PS	GSA-22	<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	0.02	0.01	0.78
PS	GSA-22	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	0.01	0.00	0.06
PS	GSA-22	<i>Sardinella aurita</i>	0.01	0.00	0.18
PS	GSA-22	<i>Scomber colias</i>	0.06	0.01	0.09
PS	GSA-22	<i>Scomber scombrus</i>	0.17	0.02	0.14
PS	GSA-22	<i>Spicara smaris</i>	0.11	0.19	1.75
PS	GSA-22	<i>Trachurus mediterraneus</i>	0.00	0.00	0.30
PS	GSA-22	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	0.91	0.02	0.03

PS	GSA-22	<i>Loligo vulgaris</i>	0.48	0.17	0.35
PS	GSA-22	<i>Illex coindetii</i>	0.14	0.03	0.19
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Aspitrigla cuculus</i>	0.02	0.00	0.10
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Boops boops</i>	0.02	0.01	0.36
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Citharus linguatula</i>	0.34	0.03	0.08
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Diplodus annularis</i>	0.56	0.10	0.19
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Eutrigla gurnardus</i>	0.06	0.07	1.18
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>	0.10	0.01	0.08
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	0.03	0.00	0.10
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Pagellus acarne</i>	0.27	0.13	0.49
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	0.48	0.04	0.09
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Raja clavata</i>	0.20	0.04	0.19
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Sarda sarda</i>	0.09	0.02	0.25
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Sardinella aurita</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Scomber colias</i>	0.03	0.01	0.15
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Solea solea</i>	0.04	0.02	0.40
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	0.19	0.02	0.11
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Trisopterus minutus</i>	0.05	0.03	0.70
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Sepia officinalis</i>	0.45	0.48	1.08
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Loligo vulgaris</i>	0.43	0.24	0.56
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Squilla mantis</i>	0.34	0.03	0.08
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Parapenaeus longirostris</i>	0.03	0.03	0.99
GNS	GSA-20	<i>Melicertus kerathurus</i>	0.03	0.02	0.65
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Boops boops</i>	0.01	0.00	0.07
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Citharus linguatula</i>	0.08	0.06	0.73
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Diplodus annularis</i>	0.12	0.02	0.19
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Diplodus vulgaris</i>	0.52	0.07	0.14
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Eutrigla gurnardus</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Lophius budegassa</i>	0.01	0.00	0.57
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>	0.01	0.00	0.19
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	0.01	0.00	0.07
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Mullus surmuletus</i>	0.01	0.00	0.05
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Pagellus acarne</i>	0.86	0.02	0.02
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Pagellus bogaraveo</i>	0.01	0.01	1.05
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	0.21	0.01	0.06
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	0.42	0.16	0.38
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Sardinella aurita</i>	0.02	0.00	0.29
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Scomber colias</i>	0.04	0.03	0.68
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Trachurus mediterraneus</i>	0.13	0.04	0.29
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Illex coindetii</i>	0.35	0.22	0.63
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Sparus aurata</i>	0.05	0.03	0.61
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Spicara smaris</i>	0.00	0.00	0.29
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	0.12	0.01	0.12

GNS	GSA-22	<i>Trigloporus lastoviza</i>	0.16	0.04	0.24
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Trisopterus minutus</i>	0.32	0.09	0.28
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Sepia officinalis</i>	0.05	0.01	0.22
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Octopus vulgaris</i>	0.00	0.00	0.70
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Squilla mantis</i>	0.37	0.06	0.16
GNS	GSA-22	<i>Nephrops norvegicus</i>	0.02	0.01	0.64
GNS	GSA-23	<i>Diplodus annularis</i>	0.44	0.00	0.01
GNS	GSA-23	<i>Solea solea</i>	0.43	0.01	0.03
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Boops boops</i>	0.11	0.02	0.17
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Diplodus annularis</i>	0.19	0.01	0.04
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Diplodus vulgaris</i>	0.02	0.00	0.11
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Lophius budegassa</i>	0.02	0.01	0.57
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>	0.09	0.09	1.02
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	0.06	0.00	0.05
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Pagellus acarne</i>	0.76	0.03	0.04
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Pagellus bogaraveo</i>	1.00	0.00	0.00
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	0.03	0.00	0.07
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Pagrus pagrus</i>	0.13	0.06	0.50
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	0.43	0.11	0.25
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Sardinella aurita</i>	0.49	0.27	0.55
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Scorpaena scrofa</i>	0.14	0.03	0.20
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Solea solea</i>	0.00	0.00	0.14
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Sparus aurata</i>	0.00	0.00	0.12
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Loligo vulgaris</i>	0.02	0.01	0.39
GTR	GSA-20	<i>Squilla mantis</i>	0.81	0.02	0.03
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Boops boops</i>	0.07	0.00	0.04
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Citharus linguatula</i>	0.14	0.02	0.16
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Diplodus annularis</i>	0.22	0.01	0.03
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Diplodus sargus</i>	0.34	0.07	0.22
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Diplodus vulgaris</i>	0.05	0.00	0.02
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Eutrigla gurnardus</i>	0.41	0.24	0.60
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Lepidorhombus boscii</i>	0.01	0.00	0.06
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Lophius budegassa</i>	0.03	0.00	0.08
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Lophius piscatorius</i>	0.02	0.01	0.48
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Mullus surmuletus</i>	0.03	0.00	0.02
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Pagellus acarne</i>	0.11	0.01	0.06
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Pagellus bogaraveo</i>	0.11	0.19	1.75
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	0.05	0.00	0.02
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Pagrus pagrus</i>	0.09	0.04	0.51
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Sardinella aurita</i>	0.11	0.04	0.38
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	0.01	0.01	0.64
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Octopus vulgaris</i>	0.02	0.00	0.04
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	0.04	0.00	0.04
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Trigloporus lastoviza</i>	0.24	0.06	0.24
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Phycis blennoides</i>	0.04	0.01	0.32

GTR	GSA-22	<i>Sarda sarda</i>	0.04	0.04	0.82
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	0.34	0.07	0.21
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Scomber scombrus</i>	0.59	0.47	0.80
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Scorpaena scrofa</i>	0.06	0.01	0.09
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	0.06	0.07	1.01
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Solea solea</i>	0.01	0.00	0.09
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Spicara maena</i>	0.02	0.00	0.07
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Trachurus mediterraneus</i>	0.25	0.08	0.32
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Trigloporus lastoviza</i>	0.11	0.02	0.23
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Trisopterus minutus</i>	0.45	0.25	0.56
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Zeus faber</i>	0.10	0.01	0.12
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Sepia officinalis</i>	0.00	0.00	0.04
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Eledone moschata</i>	0.42	0.10	0.24
GTR	GSA-22	<i>Squilla mantis</i>	0.01	0.00	0.20
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Boops boops</i>	0.22	0.01	0.06
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Diplodus annularis</i>	0.74	0.01	0.01
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Diplodus sargus</i>	0.11	0.04	0.34
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Diplodus vulgaris</i>	0.17	0.01	0.08
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Mullus surmuletus</i>	0.03	0.00	0.05
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Pagellus acarne</i>	0.29	0.02	0.06
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	0.27	0.02	0.07
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Pagrus pagrus</i>	0.15	0.01	0.09
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Scorpaena scrofa</i>	0.08	0.02	0.24
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Squilla mantis</i>	0.96	0.02	0.02
GTR	GSA-23	<i>Parapenaeus longirostris</i>	0.63	0.23	0.37

Source: Greek DCF data of 2015

Table 3.2. List of the undersized marine organisms (Annex III) of Council Regulation (EC) No. 1967/2006 of 21 December 2006 concerning management measures for the sustainable exploitation of fishery resources in the Mediterranean Sea.

Scientific name	Minimum size	Common name
1. Fish		
<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i>	25 cm	Sea-bass
<i>Diplodus annularis</i>	12 cm	Annular sea-bream
<i>Diplodus puntazzo</i>	18 cm	Sharpsnout sea-bream
<i>Diplodus sargus</i>	23 cm	White sea-bream
<i>Diplodus vulgaris</i>	18 cm	Two-banded sea-bream
<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i> *	9 cm	European anchovy
<i>Epinephelus</i> spp.	45 cm	Groupers
<i>Lithognathus mormyrus</i>	20 cm	Stripped sea-bream
<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>	20 cm	Hake
<i>Mullus</i> spp.	11 cm	Red mullets
<i>Pagellus acarne</i>	17 cm	Spanish sea-bream

<i>Pagellus bogaraveo</i>	33 cm	Red sea-bream
<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	15 cm	Common pandora
<i>Pagrus pagrus</i>	18 cm	Common sea-bream
<i>Polyprion americanus</i>	45 cm	Wreckfish
<i>Sardina pilchardus</i> **	11 cm	European sardine
<i>Scomber</i> spp	18 cm	Mackerel
<i>Solea vulgaris</i> or <i>Solea solea</i>	20 cm	Common sole
<i>Sparus aurata</i>	20 cm	Gilt-head sea-bream
<i>Trachurus</i> spp.	15 cm	Horse mackerel, Scad
2. Crustaceans		
<i>Homarus gammarus</i>	300 mm TL 105 mm CL	Lobster
<i>Nephrops norvegicus</i>	20 mm CL 70 mm TL	Norway lobster
Palinuridae	90 mm CL	Crawfish
<i>Parapenaeus longirostris</i>	20 mm CL	Deep water rose shrimp
3. Mollusc bivalves		
<i>Pecten jacobeus</i>	10 cm	Scallop
<i>Venerupis</i> spp.	25 mm	Carpet-clams
<i>Venus</i> spp.	25 mm	Venus-shells

For the Mediterranean Sea, there is a notable difference between the “discards” reported under the DCF programmes and the LO. The LO considers in the Mediterranean as discards only those species that are listed on Table 3.2 i.e. those listed in Annex III of Council Regulation (EC) No. 1967/2006 of 21 December 2006 concerning management measures for the sustainable exploitation of fishery resources in the Mediterranean Sea. However, these are only about 30 species (the main commercial ones) and are only a small fraction of the Mediterranean high species diversity with approximately 714 fish, 2,239 crustacean and 2,113 mollusc species¹³. In Table 3.1, species in bold characters are the ones listed in Annex III of Council Regulation (EC) No. 1967/2006 whereas all the others that are discarded are not included in Annex III.

3.1.2 The bottom trawlers and purse seiners segment

To date, in the Eastern Mediterranean case study, owners of bottom trawlers and purse seiners from North Aegean Sea have been interviewed. Bottom trawlers have multi-species characteristics, captures numerous fish species, such as red mullets, hake and shrimps. The purse seine fishery is the only gear which targets small pelagic species and especially anchovy (*Engraulis encrasicolus*) and sardines

¹³ See: Fitzpatrick, et al., 2017. DiscardLess Policy Brief No 2: Year 2 of the Landing Obligation: Key Issues in Mediterranean Fisheries, <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.573666>

(*Sardina pilchardus*) (70-80% of the catch) but also *Trachurus* spp, *Boops boops*, *Spicara* spp, *Sardinella aurita*, *Scomber japonicus* και *Scomber scomber*.

Trawling within the Hellenic territorial waters (6 nautical miles) is practising since 1959 between 1st of October and 31st May. It is forbidden in many geographical areas mainly gulfs, bays, estuaries, river mouth and near the coast. Small bays are fully closed to trawling and larger gulfs are partially and that regime of spatial and time management measures are enforced before the adhesion of Greece in the EU.

Purse seines are working with the use of light and according to the law it is forbidden to operate during full moon (two days before and two days after) and that since the 1950'ies. According to the same law, purse seines are subject of seasonal stop of activity between mid-December till the end of February. The peak season of this fishing is between May and September when trawlers are not allowed to fish. It is during this period that sardines and anchovy are mostly consumed and get the best price as few whitefish is sold. Few Hellenic vessels are in possession of the special license to harvest blue-fin tuna and these boats share the 250tons of quota given to Hellas by ICCAT.

Boat owners are active on board of fishing vessels. In terms of employment, in the purse seiners, depending on the size of the vessel, beside the captain/owner that is Greek, the crew comprises of 5-6 sailors in the 12-18m segment, 8-9 sailors in the 18-24m segment and 11-12 people in the 24-40m segment. In the trawlers, the crew consists of 5 to 6 persons and beside the captain (usually the Greek owner of the vessel), as a general rule comprises of 4-5 people. The majority of the crews employed by purse seines are immigrants that originate mainly from Egypt. A bilateral agreement between these two countries allows the employment of foreigners' crew. On trawlers there are also Egyptian crew but we can find more Hellenic citizens as the income provided by trawler is higher than those of purse seines. The Hellenic fishing fleet often practices the share system as salary. All foreigner crews are declared to the agriculture social security system and they are seasonal workers.

3.2 The Fishers story – documenting discard reduction practices suggested by stakeholders

According to the majority of fishers in the Aegean Sea, landing discarded products will lead to technical and operational problems for them for various reasons, the most important of which are related to increased economic costs and the lack of potential economic benefits.

In more detail, twelve fishermen representatives (fisheries stakeholders) from Greece-North Aegean Sea were interviewed, regarding their own ideas of why they discard and what they currently do and think about it. The results are described in Deliverable D4.1, finalised in April 2017 (Reid et al., 2017). The results of this task have also been brought online into a visual display on http://www.discardless.eu/fishermen_story.

Interviews with Greek fishers were realised in July 2015 and in September 2016 mainly in Nea Michaniona harbours which is the most important harbour in North Aegean Sea. The interviews addressed a range of issues relating to fishers acceptability of LO, causes of discards, adaptive and mitigation strategies. The use of discards for other purposes was also discussed. The interviews were carried out following a semi-structured design. The interviewer had a core list of issues that they wished to address. However, the interview was based on asking very broad questions, and allowing the

interviewee to talk first about what they wanted to discuss, and following up to obtain the more specific responses sought in the outline (Annex in Deliverable D4.1). Solutions proposed by fishermen were separated into technical (gear changes) and tactical (fishing behaviour changes).

The answers received from the Greek stakeholders were as follows:

3.2.1 Causes and levels of discarding:

Greece-North Aegean Sea	Sector
We discard only if our catches are mixed but this happen rarely.	All purse seines
Only undersized fish and damaged fish is discarded.	All trawlers interviewees
During some months we discard anchovy and sardines.	Trawlers
We don't discard fish because we feed birds.	Trawler and purse seines
We bring all fish without commercial value to offer it to poor people and orphanage.	All Trawlers
During October and April our discards are higher.	2 trawlers
In some areas undersized fish is important.	All trawlers
In April near the coast there an important number of undersized fish but we are not allowed to fish there.	Trawlers

3.2.2 Current methods used to avoid unwanted catch

Technical (Gear)

Greece-North Aegean Sea	Sector
We just introduced bigger mesh to our trawlers.	All trawlers
With the new mesh (40 mm square) less discards are taken.	Trawlers

Tactical (Strategies)

Greece-North Aegean Sea	Sector
Knowledge of location of spawning grounds allows for the avoidance of undersize fish at certain times of year in some locations.	All trawlers

Vessels are constantly moving between fishing grounds to try and avoid small hake. Trawlers

Information about areas to be avoided is shared between family members and friends. Trawlers

3.2.3 Interest expressed in additional methods to avoid unwanted catch

Technical (Gear)

Greece-North Aegean Sea	Sector
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Ready to test bigger mesh if a second boat is fishing near to them to evaluate the loss. 2 Trawlers

Tactical (Strategies)

Greece-North Aegean Sea	Sector
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The new mesh used by trawlers (40 mm square) permits to save petrol and reduce their consumption Trawl fisher

Management

Greece-North Aegean Sea	Sector
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Ask for real time closures to avoid undersized hake. Trawlers and purse seiners

Look for a legal frame to allow real time closures. Trawlers

Afraid that if the real time closures are not valid legally and monitor "some fishers will continue fishing these areas". Trawler

Real-time closures can work if the ministry is able to act fast. Trawlers

Fishers consider that they have enough knowledge to avoid areas producing high discards during some seasons. Their knowledge, often not share with others fishers, is considered better than those of scientists. Trawlers

3.2.4 No support for the following proposed methods to avoid unwanted catch

Technical (Gear)

Greece-North Aegean Sea	Sector
Scientists were working to improve trawl selectivity but fishers made their own nets before the results of the scientific project.	Shrimp fishery (trawlers)
They imported nets from Spain but they were not so good for the area, each area has its own characteristics so we prefer to make our nets. And is also cheaper.	Bottom trawlers

Tactical (Strategies)

Greece-North Aegean Sea	Sector
Against new permanent closures of fishing areas, preferences for real time closures because presence of undersized fish is seasonal.	Trawlers

3.2.5 Conclusions from the Fishers story in Eastern Mediterranean

The conclusions from the surveys in Greece with fishers are as follows:

Firstly, the storage of the -low economic value- discards onboard will reduce the vessel's capacity to store products of higher economic value, and the costs (mainly work load) associated with the manipulation and storage of discards on board will be increased. The same holds for the infrastructure, facilities, capacity and staff availability at the landing port, which for the majority of landings ports in Greece, are completely insufficient to accommodate and handle even a small increase in landed quantities.

Secondly, the fishers have no or low economic incentives to land discards (that, as mentioned above, have low market value), given the technical and operational issues discussed above. As a consequence, with no or low economic incentive, the enforcement of the discard ban and the associated monitoring and controlling costs may be problematic, at least for the eastern Mediterranean where the compliance to fisheries regulations is generally low (Sarda et al. 2015).

An important disadvantage is the lack of infrastructure and facilities in the majority of landing ports in Greece. There are eleven landing ports in Greece, three of which in northern Aegean Sea (Thessaloniki, Kavala and Alexandroupoli), including the one in Thermaikos Gulf (NW Aegean Sea), that of Thessaloniki. Contrary to the majority of landing ports that are small and lack infrastructure and facilities, the landing port of Thessaloniki is relatively new and large enough to accommodate the landings of the largest fleet in northern Aegean Sea, including a large amount of imports.

3.3 The scientists story

Scientists in the Eastern Mediterranean and in the Mediterranean Sea in general, tend to highlight the fact that there is largely an apparent fisheries mismanagement in this area^{14,15,16}. Overall, the Mediterranean is among the most overfished European seas, well beyond EU overfishing rates in the Atlantic or in the Baltic Sea. Between 1994 and 2014, Mediterranean catches declined from 1.020.000 to 800.000 tons, an impressive 20% reduction in just 20 years. All recent scientific reports in the Mediterranean present alarming data for the status of fish stocks:

- On average, 85% of assessed stocks are overexploited¹⁷ (96% of EU stocks and 91% for stocks shared with non EU countries¹⁸).
- The General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean (GFCM) and the EU Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STECF) regularly assess the status of fish stocks in the Mediterranean. **Out of 440 assessments published between 2007 and 2015, as much as 400 revealed fishing exploitation rates well beyond sustainable levels**, 128 of which with rates five times higher than biologically sustainable limits.

Discard management plans for the EU Mediterranean fisheries under the reformed Common Fisheries Policy seems to be a mission impossible².

The MEDAC recommendation that has been adopted by the European Commission on 20.10.2016 with the Commission Delegated Regulation C(2016) 6606 final¹⁹, establishing a discard plan for certain demersal fisheries in the Mediterranean Sea, has been criticized in numerous meetings and open discussions. Many fisheries scientists caught in surprise and despite the fact that the competent authority for reviewing the Mediterranean JRs (STECF) concluded that none of them can be assessed, due to lack of information regarding the volumes of landings and discards, the European Commission adopted the plan. For many fisheries scientists, going through the text of the submitted JRs it becomes obvious that the essence of the regulation has been misrepresented by fishers who perceived the exemptions provided, as an escape-way from the obligation to land all catches and continue business as usual².

Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 1392/2014 established a discard plan for certain small pelagic fisheries in the Mediterranean Sea. That discard plan applies to small pelagic fisheries using pelagic mid-water trawl and/or purse seines (fisheries for anchovy, sardine, mackerel and horse mackerel). In order to avoid disproportionate costs of handling unwanted catches, it allows the discarding of a small percentage of catches of species subject to minimum sizes as referred to in Annex III to Council Regulation (EC) No 1967/2006 (*de minimis* exemption'). Delegated Regulation (EU) No 1392/2014 expired on 31 December 2017 and was replaced by Delegated Regulation (EU) 2018/161 of

¹⁴ Tsikliras AC, Fish Aquac J 2014, 5:4 DOI: 10.4172/ 2150-3508.1000e113

¹⁵ Damalas, D., 2015. Mission impossible: discard management plans for the EU Mediterranean fisheries under the reformed Common Fisheries Policy. Fisheries Research 165, 96-99.

¹⁶ Vasilakopoulos, P., C.D. Maravelias and G. Tserpes, 2014. The Alarming Decline of Mediterranean Fish Stocks. Current Biology 24, 1643–1648, July 21, 2014 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2014.05.070>

¹⁷ FAO/GFCM. [The state of Mediterranean and Black sea Fisheries \(SoMFi 2016\)](#).

¹⁸ [Communication of the European Commission on fishing opportunities for 2016](#).

¹⁹ See: <http://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regdoc/rep/3/2016/EN/C-2016-6606-F1-EN-MAIN-PART-1.PDF>

23 October 2017 establishing a *de minimis* exemption to the landing obligation (LO) for certain small pelagic fisheries in the Mediterranean Sea.

In addition, Scientists express concerns for the new CFP and the LO in the Mediterranean^{20, 21, 22}. For many Med based scientists, the CFP was designed based on characteristics and needs of the Atlantic and North Sea fisheries, not considering the peculiarities of the Mediterranean fisheries²³. The main differentiation of the Mediterranean fisheries are:

1. The Mediterranean EU fisheries production represents about 10,5% of the total fisheries production of the EU. However, this production derives from the 46% of the EU fishing vessels and more than 50% of the EU fishers. This is due to the fact that more than 80% of the Mediterranean fisheries fleet are less than 12 m LOA²⁴.
2. The Mediterranean has an extensive coast line (more than 16.000 Km in Greece alone). This means, in combination with the above fleet characteristics and the market, that every spot in the coastline is a potential landing site. On the contrary in the Atlantic, there are defined places for landing fish and markets. This fact has as a result, in the Mediterranean the logistics of gathering the discards from numerous places difficult and with a high cost.
3. The Mediterranean has a small fisheries production but a rich biodiversity (catches are composed of numerous species many of which are not edible). These species are mainly of small size, with small life duration and usual high commercial values (Vassilopoulou et al., 2007)²⁵. On the contrary, in North Europe are targeted relatively fewer species and their larger sizes, as fisheries management is through Total Allowable Catches (TACs) or fishing opportunities, i.e. catch limits (expressed in tonnes or numbers) that are set for most commercial fish stocks. TACs are shared between EU countries in the form of national quotas. Quotas promote high grading which is a practice of selectively harvesting fish (i.e. the larger ones) so that only the best quality fish are brought ashore.
4. In the Mediterranean there is a big differentiation in the types of the various fishing vessels, activities and metiers. This often results in acute competition between fishers and between fisheries activities.

²⁰ Bellido, J., Santos, M., Pennino, M., Valeiras, X., Pierce, G., 2011. Fishery discards and bycatch: solutions for an ecosystem approach to fisheries management? *Hydrobiologia* 670 (1), 317-333. DOI 10.1007/s10750-011-0721-5

²¹ Sarda, F., Coll, M., Heymans, J.J., Stergiou, K.I., 2015. Overlooked impacts and challenges of the new European impacts and challenges of the new European discard ban. *Fish and Fisheries* 16, 17-180.

²² Damalas, D., 2015. Mission impossible: discard management plans for the EU Mediterranean fisheries under the reformed Common Fisheries Policy. *Fisheries Research* 165, 96-99.

²³ Machias A., Stergiou K. and Tsagarakis K., 2017. New Common Fisheries Policy: Obligatory landing of discards. *Fishing News*, Vol. 417, pp. 60-68.

²⁴ Machias A., Tsagarakis, K. and Matsaganis, M. 2016. Greek fisheries and the economic crisis: structural analogies. *Ethics in Science and Environmental Politics* 16, 19-23.

²⁵ Vassilopoulou, V., Machias, A., Tsagarakis, K., 2007. By-catch and discards in multi-species fisheries and their impact in the Hellenic waters. In *State of Hellenic Fisheries (SoHelFi)*, pp. 251-260. Ed. By Papaconstantinou, C., Zenetos, A., Vassilopoulou, V., Tserpes, G. HCMR Publications Athens.

5. The larger fisheries production in the Atlantic and the North Sea is due to the fact that the waters there are mesotrophic and the continental shelf is extended. On the contrary in the Mediterranean the waters are in general oligotrophic and the continental shelf is limited¹⁴.
6. Despite the fact that in the EU Member States the participation of the fisheries in the GDP ranges between 0.01-0.2% without having a distinct differentiation between North Europe and the Mediterranean, many scientists consider that the socioeconomic importance of fisheries is higher in Greece and perhaps in the Mediterranean¹².
7. In the Mediterranean, fisheries management is done with technical measures (prohibition of using certain fishing gears in some areas, depths and seasons closures (e.g. in Greece), minimum conservation size) that often do not have a sound scientific basis²⁶.

Many scientists believe that for the same reasons the LO is rather irrational for the Med (see Machias et al., 2017). They believe that the discards LO will not affect the quantities fished as in the Med there are no quotas (with the exception of Blue Fin Tuna and from now on for swordfish). Moreover, dietary habits in the Med, are different compared to North Europe and small (even undersized fish) is considered as a delicacy (gourmet). It is well known that there is an illegal market of fish below MLS. With the previous CFP it was considered illegal to have on board undersized fish (in order to prohibit to enter in the markets), an enforcement measure that is well adapted to the characteristics of the Med fisheries. There are fears that the discards LO will further increase this illegal market of undersized fish as now it will be allowed to the vessels to have the undersized fish on board (Machias et al., 2017)²⁷.

Most scientists, agree and share the fishers' story and the technical difficulties that a landing obligation is about to bring. In brief, these difficulties mainly refer to the reduction of the vessel's storage capacity, the increase of handling costs and the lack of incentive to land discards. The first two conditions also hold for the infrastructure, facilities, capacity and staff availability at the landing port, which at the moment are completely insufficient to accommodate and handle increased amounts of landed quantities (Sarda et al. 2015)²⁸.

For Mediterranean fisheries, the LO has the advantage of providing information for the actual quantities of unwanted catch that has been removed from the sea to fisheries and ecosystem models. In other words the once missing information of discards, which could have led to underestimation of total catch, is no longer missing. This will improve accuracy and predictive ability of stock assessment and will benefit fisheries management and marine policy but could have been acquired if a better system of monitoring fishing activities (mainly catches and discards) existed. The LO could also potentially benefit the aquaculture industry as large amounts of unwanted biomass would now be landed and be available at relatively lower cost to the fish farms.

²⁶ Stergiou, K.I., Christou, E.D., Georgopoulos, D., Zenetos, A., Souvermezoglou, C., 1997. The Hellenic seas: physics, chemistry, biology and fisheries. *Oceanography marine biology: an annual review*, 35: 415-538.

²⁷ Machias A., Stergiou K. and Tsagarakis K., 2017. New Common Fisheries Policy: Obligatory landing of discards. *Fishing News*, Vol. 417, pp. 60-68.

²⁸ Sarda F, Coll M, Heymans JJ, Stergiou KI (2015) Overlooked impacts and challenges of the new European discard ban. *Fish and Fisheries* 16: 175-180.

The ecological disadvantage of the LO is that it does not provide any solution to the actual removal of undersized fish from the sea²⁹. One of the main issues in fisheries science and the targets of fisheries management has never been “what to do with the unwanted catch” but rather “how to avoid unwanted catch” and “select what we need from the sea” with respect to fish species and sizes within stocks. In a way, the LO provides an alibi for never resolving the unwanted catch issue and does not benefit the fisher or the marine ecosystem. It also serves the concept of “balanced” harvesting³⁰, which has generated a serious debate in fisheries management (for a critique see Froese et al. 2016³¹). Most scientists in the Mediterranean have been fighting for more selective fishing gears for decades and are rather skeptical with respect to enforcing the LO in the multi-specific Mediterranean fisheries.

Finally, eliminating discards may cause ecological cascading effects³² because the discarded catches are a food source for scavenging species. Landing the entire catch may affect the populations of seabirds, marine mammals and seabed fauna, and has absolutely no benefit to fish stocks because fishing continues as usual¹⁷. In contrast, if landing obligations are enforced together with regulations in fishing practices to limit the capture of unwanted fish the populations of seabirds, mammals and most fish stocks will be benefited¹⁷.

Concluding, Scientists believe that the CFP has not succeeded in improving the state of European Mediterranean commercial fish stocks over the past two decades, in contrast to the European NE Atlantic stocks³³. The increasing trend of exploitation rate observed in the Mediterranean, is particularly alarming because it is probably affecting many more stocks and species than the ones examined in this meta-analysis, due to the multispecies nature of the Mediterranean fisheries.

Conclusively, it has been identified that the current long-standing legislative framework (COM 1626/1994, COM 1967/2006), tailored to deal with the ‘peculiarities’ of Mediterranean fisheries by establishing an effort-based management scheme, has now become an immovable obstacle towards dealing with unwanted catches. Mediterranean stakeholders will have to decide if it is worth moving from an effort-based to a catch-based management system, or if the benefits realized by the former would be difficult to be counterbalanced under any other system³⁴.

²⁹ Sarda F, Coll M, Heymans JJ, Stergiou KI (2015) Overlooked impacts and challenges of the new European discard ban. *Fish and Fisheries* 16: 175-180.

³⁰ Garcia SM, Kolding J, Rice J, Rochet MJ, Zhou S, Arimoto T, Beyer JE, et al. (2012) Reconsidering the Consequences of Selective Fisheries. *Science* 335: 1045–1047.

³¹ Froese R, Walters C, Pauly D, Winker H, Weyl OLF, Demirel N, Tsikliras AC, Holt SJ (2016) A critique of the balanced harvesting approach to fishing. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 73: 1640-1650

³² Heath MR et al. (2014) Cascading ecological effects of eliminating fishery discards. *Nature Communications* 5: 3893 doi: 10.1038/ncomms4893.

³³ Vasilakopoulos, P., C.D. Maravelias and G. Tserpes, 2014. The Alarming Decline of Mediterranean Fish Stocks. *Current Biology* 24, 1643–1648, July 21, 2014 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2014.05.070>

³⁴ Damalas, D., 2015. Mission impossible: discard management plans for the EU Mediterranean fisheries under the reformed Common Fisheries Policy. *Fisheries Research* 165, 96-99.

3.4 The Managers' story

The Common Fishery Policy (CFP) and its legislation, including the Regulation (EU) No 1380/2013 of the EP and the Council on the CFP (Article 15) (from now on the Basic Regulation), is directly applicable as Greece is a member of the European Union. Besides the Community law there is a variety of national measures aiming at regulating fishing effort in conjunction with appropriate technical measures, which include minimum landing size of commercial species, mesh size regulations, closed areas and seasons, and minimum depths and distances from shore for fishing.

3.4.1 The Fisheries management in Greece

In Greece, the mandated Authority that is responsible for developing and implementing fisheries policy is the **Directorate General for Sustainable Fisheries** (DGSF) of the Ministry of Rural Development and Food. It is also responsible for the scientific assessment of fish stocks of key commercial species as well as for analysing the sector's economic situation and for data collection³⁵. In this aim, it is supported by two national research institutes, the Greek Fisheries Research Institute (FRI³⁶) and the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR³⁷), which are responsible for the implementation of the national Data Collection Framework (DCF) programme and the collection of related data. With regard to fishery control activities and responsibilities, the DGSF is supported by the competent services of the Hellenic Coast Guard.

3.4.2 International Regional Initiatives for Fisheries Management in the Mediterranean.

3.4.2.1 The General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean

The **General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean**; **GFCM**) is the main fishery management organization in the Mediterranean. Consisting of 23 Member countries along with the European Union, the GFCM's objectives are to promote the development, conservation, rational management and best utilization of living marine resources, as well as the sustainable development of aquaculture in the Mediterranean, Black Sea and connecting waters. The GFCM has the authority to adopt binding recommendations for fisheries conservation and management in its Convention Area and plays a critical role in fisheries governance in the Region. The GFCM has established 30 management areas in the Mediterranean based on political and statistical considerations rather than biological or economic factors.

Apart from the GFCM, the European Union, through the STECF, established in 2008 a **working group specifically focused to the assessment of Mediterranean and Black Sea stocks** (known as SG-MED up to 2011). The SG-MED was born as a request to the STECF to set up an operational work-programme to update the status of the main demersal stocks and evaluate the exploitation levels with respect to their biological and economic production potentials and the sustainability of the stocks by using both trawl

³⁵ See: http://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/cfp/emff/doc/op-greece-fact-sheet_en.pdf

³⁶ See: <http://www.inale.gr/>

³⁷ See: <http://www.hcmr.gr/en/>

surveys and commercial catch/landing data as collected through the Community Data Collection regulation N° 1543/2000 as well as other scientific information collected at national level.

Each year, the GFCM and the STECF assess the exploitation status of the main target stocks and the results of these assessments (both inputs and outputs) are publicly available on their websites: i) GFCM (<http://www.fao.org/gfcm/reports/statutory-meetings/en/>); and ii) STECF (<https://stecf.jrc.ec.europa.eu/reports/medbs>). Apart from stock assessments, additional data and information relevant to fisheries management is also available. For instance, the STECF has set up a working group dealing specifically with the LO, which first meeting took place in October 2016 (<https://stecf.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ewg1514>).

3.4.2.2 The Mediterranean Advisory Council

The **Mediterranean Advisory Council (MEDAC)**, is made up of European and national organizations representing the fisheries sector (including the industrial fleet, small-scale fisheries, the processing sector and trade unions) and other interest groups (such as environmental organizations, consumer groups and sports/recreational fishery associations) which operate in the Mediterranean area in the framework of the CFP. Among other activities, the MEDAC is organising meetings related to the LO (<http://en.med-ac.eu/events.php>).

3.4.2.3 The South Eastern Mediterranean Sea Forum (SudEstMed)

The Greek Directorate General for Sustainable Fisheries participates in **SudEstMed (South Eastern Mediterranean Sea Forum)** a newly established body with the participation of Cyprus, Greece, Italy and Malta. **SudEstMed** is a structured form of cooperation in the fisheries sector and acts as a forum for exchanging ideas, views and information and a forum that can facilitate joint efforts in various concrete projects aiming at achieving sustainable fisheries in the Eastern Mediterranean Sea Region. A similar initiative (PESCAMED) exists for western Mediterranean between Spain, France and Italy.

This initiative is under Articles 9,10 and 18 of the Regulation (EU) 1380/2013 referring to shared stocks and the relevant long-term management plans should be developed taking into account the provisions of Art. 18 on regionalisation in order to contribute to the stocks' sustainable exploitation and the protection of the marine ecosystems.

SudEstMed is organised into a High Level Group (HLG) and a Technical Group (TG). The HLG is the Ministries of Fisheries that will meet annually. The Presidency of the Forum is cyclical with Italy chairing on 2016 and Greece in 2017.

In the Mediterranean Sea, three High Level Groups (HLGs) of EU Member States were established to develop regional management measures in the Mediterranean: the PESCAMED group (France, Italy & Spain); the Adriatica group (Croatia, Italy & Slovenia); and the **SudEstMed** group (Cyprus, Greece, Italy and Malta). The HLGs make Joint Recommendations (JRs) for discard plans following consultations with the Mediterranean Advisory Council (MEDAC).

The Mediterranean pelagic discard plan was largely based on MEDAC proposals rather than on a JR from the HLGs. Similarly, in 2016 the 3 HLGs endorsed the MEDAC proposal for a JR in its entirety (MEDAC

Ref.: 190/2016, June 8, 2016). This reflects a much higher level of devolution of competence to the MEDAC than is the case in other regions. However, the MEDAC position on the JR was not unanimous as two member organizations were dissatisfied that the proposal did not contain clear mechanisms for reducing unwanted catches, nor for discouraging their possible illegal commercialization and because *de minimis* percentages were not based on data.

The first SudEstMed meeting, held in Brussels on April 26 2016, identified the target species characterising the fisheries in the Southeastern Mediterranean Sea as a starting point for a discards joint management plan³⁸. In this meeting, each Member State announced the intention to adopt management measures that may affect the selectivity of the gears, the space-time closures of sensitive maritime areas for certain fish stocks, the reduction of mortality and fishing effort. The HLG based on scientific advice and reports, identified that rose shrimp (*Parapenaeus longirostris*), red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*), surmullet (striped red mullet; *Mullus surmuletus*³⁹) and hake (*Merluccius merluccius*) in the Ionian Sea are the target species which define fisheries in the area⁴.

Soon after the first **SudEstMed** meeting, **MEDAC** prepared a proposal of **joint recommendations on discards management plans for species defining the fisheries**⁴⁰ submitted to Member States and EU as it is foreseen in Article 18 of the Basic Regulation. Article 15 envisages the gradual introduction of the LO for all catches, according to a clearly identified schedule. According to MEDAC, the LO for small pelagic fish species caught with purse seine and pelagic trawl nets was already in force and the next deadline was the 1st January 2017 "**for species defining the fisheries**". The identification of these species proved very complicated and was resolved thanks to the Member States whose General Directors of the relevant Ministries prepared letters to communicate the target species which identify the fisheries. No changes in the management structure took place until February 2019.

3.5 Adaptation of gear technology

In Greece, the national institute HCMR recently accomplished the gear selectivity project EPILEXIS (see <http://epilexis.hcmr.gr/>) in the Aegean Sea. The project compared 3 types of the trawl codend (40 mm diamond, 40mm square and 50mm diamond) and made selectivity studies for the 5 most commercial species.

The results show that square mesh size has the better selectivity and reduces discards. In most cases, commercial catch was not significantly altered. The ratio of discards/commercial catch was reduced from 0.57 (40D), to 0.49 (40S) and 0.51 (50D). Square mesh size of 40S had the best selectivity curve, shifted to larger lengths and larger L50. Diamond 40D mesh size has the lower selectivity, Diamond 50D mesh size withholds more young fish compared to 40S and allows escapees of larger size, especially for

³⁸ See letter 07818/5-5-2016 of Riccardo Rigillo, Director General for Maritime Fisheries and Aquaculture at the Italian Ministry of Agriculture to MEDAC: http://www.med-ac.eu/files/do_documento/documentazione_parietti/lettere/2016/05/1617_nota_inpsaf_piano_scurti_sudestmed.pdf Accessed on 19/7/2016.

³⁹ The SudEstMed meeting used the term "red mullet" to describe two distinct species, namely *Mullus barbatus* and *M. surmuletus*.

⁴⁰ See MEDAC Ref.: 190/2016 of June 8, 2016: http://en.med-ac.eu/files/documentazione_parietti/lettere/2016/06/190_medac_jr_lo_demersal_8june.pdf Accessed on 20/7/2016.

striped red mullet. The square 40S mesh size allows the escapees of a significant part of young hake. Despite that, the largest part of the hake catch is below the minimum landing size of 20 cm in the codend.

These trials have been reported into two factsheets into the DiscardLess selectivity manual (http://www.discardless.eu/selectivity_manual).

3.6 Optimal use of unwanted catches

NAYS (partner No. 15), in cooperation with MATIS (partner No. 19) exploited the feasibility to use unwanted catches for purposes other than direct human consumption, including fish meal and fish oil as well as silage production in Greece.

The objective of this work was to explore and evaluate possible processing solutions for excess raw materials in context of the Greek fisheries and fish markets. Two potential processing solutions were considered in the Greek case study, in the form of fishmeal/fishoil and silage production. Material choices for these two processing methods were assessed based on previous records of discarded catches and fish waste on the retail- and commercial markets in Athens, Thessaloniki (Nea Michaniona) and Kavala, which are by far the most important fishing harbours in Greece. The solutions were compared by the investment and accumulated profits along with the potential future development of marine by-products.

The alternative suggestions/solutions considered are fishmeal and fish oil production using small compact fishmeal plants, and silage production which can either be sold as raw material into a larger fishmeal factory or it can for example be used to make feed pellets or more valuable products.

Figure 3.1. Simplified Héðinn fishmeal and fish oil plants, on left on land version and on right smaller off-shore version.

The major finding of this work is that it is not profitable to gather material for either fishmeal processing or silage making as proposed in suggestions 1 and 2. The fishmeal suggestion 1 return -746.812 EUR annual loss and the silage suggestion 2 return -1.538.052 EUR annual loss. Transportation cost is considerable, and the fishing ports are scattered over large area which forces them to transport little amounts over large distances. Fresh fish or rest raw materials need frequent pick up to make sure that they don't go ruined and that quality is maintained. The second largest cost factor is raw material cost,

which is what stakeholders, fisherman or merchants get for their raw material, this is their incentive to collect this material. The raw material cost was calculated 40% of the total revenue of silage, fish oil and fishmeal or 0,14 EUR/kg raw material sold to fishmeal and 0,09 EUR/kg if sold to silage. This may seem a fair price but is however too high for the overall operation. A series of sensitivity analyses showed that this price would need to be reduced to 0,10-0.12 EUR/kg raw material sold to fishmeal and 0,03 EUR/kg for the overall operation to start running minimum profit.

Figure 3.2 The Steinsvik silage plant. (Picture: Steinsvik).

Despite the silage giving off less revenue and more loss annually it is effective material wise and easier to store and maintain quality wise before processing. In this scenario, it might prove difficult to gather fresh material from several stakeholders and be certain that the raw material qualities are maintained. With fishmeal being dependent upon various quality factors affecting the chemical properties, this might present an obstacle. The limiting factor for the silage suggestion is that the operation cost is simply too high compared to the. One alternative, as an effort to reduce the operation cost would be to narrow the reception station for silage down to one station located in middle of these three suggested stations. This would however mean much more transportation, but it would be interesting to further explore whether it's economical. There are still some unexplored possibilities in silage which can present opportunities for further process development and innovation to give off better products. The suggested silage solution in this work, anticipated that the raw silage would be sold to the fishmeal producers to ensure

stable operational conditions. Silage can however, be utilized to make a wide variety of products, such as oil, supplements and cosmetics. Furthermore, it can be used to make more commercial products such as fish feed pellets out of thickened silage blended with grain or starch. The latter processing has been steadily becoming more prominent due to lower energy consumption compared to a standard process involving fish meal as well as the material gets heated less during this process, making it gentler with regards to the overall protein composition. These factors along with others, including transportation cost of the raw material and the product itself will have to be taken into consideration when deciding best practices for a streamlined and practical process.

In the making of any business plan, regardless of whether the bases for the business are known or not, many assumptions need to be established. The above-mentioned assumptions made in this work have different sensitivities towards different external factors such as market condition or even stock size at any given time. The parameter that is the most sensitive in this case however, is the amount of raw material from markets and fishermen which can greatly affect the bases of this kind of processing. In this regard, it will be interesting to see how landing volumes of non-commercial species (i.e. UUC) will develop parallel to the discard ban (a very critical and necessary condition for Greece and the Mediterranean Sea in general) and how new technology and fishing practices can affect the composition of the catch. It is not unlikely that these volumes can be reduced in near future (through selectivity improvement) which can create more challenges for this kind of operation. The results indicated that by investing in either the fishmeal or silage industry, individual fishermen or merchants may receive some compensation for the raw material if it is sold to fishmeal processors or to silage processors. Preliminary results presented in the workshops in Athens and Nea Michaniona (January 2018) and the final ones in the Final DiscardLess Conference in the Danish (Lyngby) meeting (January 2019).

3.7 Summary- conclusions

Gear Technology and Selectivity

In Greece, the EPILEXIS project of HCMR, examined the effects of 40mm and 50mm diamond and 40mm square meshes in the trawl codend on the composition, biomass and abundance of escapees as well as the commercial and discarded catch. The number of taxa of escapees differed among the three meshes; this was not the case for biomass and abundance. Significant higher values in number of taxa, biomass and abundance of discards were found in the codend using the 40mm diamond mesh. In accordance with CFP, both 40mm square and 50mm diamond meshes, compared to the 40mm diamond, increased the quantity of escapees and reduced discards.

Initial avoidance, including tactical, strategic and gear based approaches

All fishers in Greece consider that the LO cannot be applied to the Hellenic Sea and to their fishing. Greek fishers think that they have little discards and on board handling will not be increased if they have to keep discards. The number of crew on Greek vessels is important so working time will not increase. Bottom trawlers have enough space to store discards if necessary. They all wait the approval of the exemptions asked by the national fisheries authorities. Very few are ready to declare in their logbook discards. They are against new permanent closures of fishing areas. They would prefer for real time closures because presence of undersize fish is seasonal, however, administratively this is almost impossible to be done with the current legal framework.

Discards utilisation

An important disadvantage is the lack of infrastructure and facilities in the majority of landing ports in Greece. From the two proposals suggested for fishmeal/fishoil and silage production, the investment cost in equipment for fishmeal production, is considerably higher compared to what is needed for making silage. The process requires more staff, maintenance and energy but the product, the fish powder is quite well known and returns stable revenue. The silage processing however, is slightly riskier, since the product has not yet become as commercial around the world as fishmeal powder. The current EMFF provides support for establishments of utilising discards and UUC that can even reach subsidies of 100% if the action is driven by collective fishermen initiatives and serve a collective interest and have a collective beneficiary and innovative characteristics.

It is evident that eventually someone has to pay the costs for a discard ban and real life shows that a realistic solution must engage the fishermen if one would like to have access to the raw material. So far, the private sector is unwilling to invest and our cost estimations further support this unwillingness. Therefore, it seems that only collective fishermen initiatives and EU funding could make the LO to work in Greece and in the Mediterranean Sea in general.

3.8 Published references and presentations in conferences

S. Villasante, Manel Antelo, Maria Christou, Florence Fauconnet, Katia Frangoudes et al. (2019) The implementation of Landing Obligation in Small Scale Fisheries of Southern European Union Countries, in S. S. Uhlmann et al. (eds.), The European Landing Obligation, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-03308-8_5

Mike Fitzpatrick, Katia Frangoudes, et al. (2019) Fishing Industry Perspectives on the EU Landing Obligation, in S. S. Uhlmann et al. (eds.), The European Landing Obligation, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-03308-8_4

Ayoe Hoff, Hans Frost, Peder Andersen, Raul Pallezo, Lucía Rueda, George Triantaphyllidis, Ioanna Argyrou, Athanassios Tsikliras, Arina Motova, Sigrid Lehuta, Hazel Curtis, Gonzalo Rodríguez-Rodríguez, Hugo M. Ballesteros, Julio Valeiras, and José María Bellido, 2019, Potential Economics Consequences of Landing Obligation in S. S. Uhlmann et al. (eds.), The European Landing Obligation, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-03308-8_4

Frangoudes, Katia, Toni Quetglas, George Triantaphyllidis, Mike Fitzpatrick, 2018, Stakeholders' vision on landing obligation transformation of the Mediterranean social ecological system ? in CIESM, Engaging marine scientists and fishers to share knowledge and perceptions – Early lessons. CIESM Workshop Monograph n° 50 [Frederic Briand, Ed.] CIESM Publisher, Monaco, pp. 47-53.

4 Discards Mitigation Strategies in the Western Mediterranean case study

4.1 Overview of the case study and initial work objectives

The **Western Mediterranean case study** focuses on two contrasting areas in terms of the ecosystem productivity, exploitation pattern, and types and rates of discards: the French and Spanish Gulf of Lions-Catalan coast in the one hand, and the Balearic archipelago in the other hand. In each of the two areas, two bathymetric strata, middle slope and deep shelf are used as parallel 'study systems'. At the deep shelf, European hake is the dominant species exploited by different gear types (trawlers, longliners, gillnetters), while at the middle slope, red shrimp dominate catches and is exploited exclusively by trawlers. Discard levels and species composition vary considerably among the two depth strata.

The western Mediterranean case study focuses on a revision and analysis of fishing dependent- and independent-information and process knowledge on the impacted ecosystems (WP1) with a specific focus to define sensitive habitats using environmental and mega-invertebrates data and assess the impact of potential future spatial strategies. The case contribute to the monitoring of the effects of the implementation of the landing obligation on the case study fleet (WP2) and to the comprehensive review and meta-analysis of fishing selectivity, taking advantage of data and knowledge of fish selectivity projects performed in the area (WP3). Strategies for discard avoidance are devised in tight collaboration with the fishing industry and fisheries independent and dependent data together with VMS data will be used to create maps that show zones of high discard likelihood in space and time (i.e. seasonal patterns) (WP4). The most appropriate and consensual approaches to incentives in the area will then be identified. Finally, the results will be included in the discard mitigations strategies (DMS) suggested for the case study and potentially other Mediterranean areas and policy recommendations offered on how a discard policy can be successfully implemented (WP7).

This deliverable reports on the outcomes of WP3 and WP4 for this case study.

4.2 The Fishers story – documenting discard reduction practices suggested by stakeholders

A total of 7 fisheries stakeholders from Spain- tThe Balearic Islands were interviewed (3 bottom trawl fleet, 4 small-scale fleet) regarding their own ideas of why they discard and what they currently do and think about it. The results are described in Deliverable D4.1, finalised in April 2017 (Reid et al., 2017), including also an analysis of the commonalities in responses across various regions and fisheries and, conversely, those that are more specific to a given case. The results of this task have also been brought online into a visual display on http://www.discardless.eu/fishermen_story.

The interviews were carried out at different ports situated along the island's coast. As the answers were similar in all cases, the number of interviews was considered to be sufficient. The answers received from the Balearic stakeholders were as follows:

4.2.1 Causes and levels of discarding:

Spain-the Balearics	Sector
<p>Main problem of small-sized fish is for hake (<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>).</p> <p>Hake recruitment does not seem to have a clear seasonality and large quantities of recruits can be captured almost all year round at some specific continental shelf areas and depths. These areas were not exploited routinely; they were only used when the bad weather conditions prevented working at deeper depths. Other fishers report that these hake recruits were only taken during some specific periods (February-March, May-June). After the implementation of the MCRS, fishermen do not use these areas and periods in order to avoid catching small-sized hake.</p>	Bottom Trawlers
Large catches of picarel (<i>Spicara smaris</i>) and horse mackerel (<i>Trachurus</i> spp.) which saturated the market and were sold at very low prices.	
Transparent goby (<i>Aphia minuta</i>) fishery: small amount of discards, basically recruits of other fish species (e.g. <i>Pagellus</i> spp.). Discards are believed to be released in good condition.	Small scale Fishery - monospecific boat seine
Dolphinfish (<i>Coryphaena hippurus</i>) fishery: small-sized recruits appear during late summer/early autumn and grow fast. Discards of small individuals in the first days of the fishing season.	Small scale Fishery - Trammel nets

4.2.2 Current methods used to avoid unwanted catch

Technical (Gear)

Spain-the Balearics	Sector
<p>Transparent goby (<i>Aphia minuta</i>) fishery:</p> <p>Once on board, the catch is placed in a tank to separate the transparent goby (it remains on the top) from the discards (on the bottom). After taking the transparent goby, discards are released in good condition.</p>	Bottom Trawlers
Cuttlefish (<i>Sepia officinalis</i>) fishery: in general, fishermen use larger mesh sizes than those established by law to avoid unwanted catch.	Small scale Fishery - Trammel nets
Striped red mullet (<i>Mullus surmuletus</i>) fishery: to avoid taking a lot of debris and small-sized fish, fishermen increased the mesh size as in cuttlefish.	Small scale Fishery - gillnets

Tactical (Strategies)

Spain-the Balearics	Sector
After the implementation of the MLS, fishermen avoid areas and periods where they know juvenile hake occur in order to avoid catching small-sized hake.	Bottom Trawlers

For the picarel (<i>Spicara smaris</i>) fishery, fishermen agreed to implement quotas per vessel and day (200 kg). Currently fishermen avoid taking catches over this quota to reduce the discards of picarel.	Bottom Trawlers
For horse mackerel (<i>Trachurus</i> spp.) the problem is taking more catch than the market can cope with. When fishermen see a lot of horse mackerel, they react by using shorter hauls to avoid large catches.	Bottom Trawlers
In some areas and at specific depths (220-270 m), bottom trawlers take boarfish (<i>Capros aper</i>) in large amounts and this damages the commercial catch. Fishermen do not use these areas to avoid this problem.	Bottom Trawlers
Transparent goby (<i>Aphia minuta</i>) fishery: In some cases, if the fishfinder indicates a high proportion of unwanted fish, fishermen do not fish to avoid catching discards.	Small scale Fishery - monospecific boat seine
Spiny lobster (<i>Palinurus elephas</i>) fishery: Some rocky areas in the Menorca Channel are known to concentrate juveniles of spiny lobster during the fishing season. These areas are avoided by some fishermen in order to reduce the catches of small-sized specimens.	Small scale Fishery - Trammel nets
Dolphinfish (<i>Coryphaena hippurus</i>) fishery: As with the picarel in the bottom trawl fishery, small-scale fishers also use a system of quotas per day and vessel (200 kg) for dolphinfish in Mallorca to avoid market saturation.	Small scale Fishery - Trammel nets

4.2.3 Interest expressed in additional methods to avoid unwanted catch

Technical (Gear)

Spain–the Balearics	Sector
Spiny lobster (<i>Palinurus elephas</i>) fishery: Some fishermen, in collaboration with scientists, have looked at V-notching for this species. Although V-notching has been primarily aimed at boosting egg production by protecting gravid females, V-notching of undersized individuals could be used to monitor the fulfilment of the MLS regulation.	Small scale Fishery - Trammel nets

Tactical (Strategies)

Spain–the Balearics	Sector
Implementation of quota for horse mackerel species as with Picarel quota currently used voluntarily by fishermen.	Bottom Trawlers

Management changes

Spain-the Balearics	Sector
Implementation of quota for horse mackerel species as with picarel quota currently used voluntarily by fishermen.	Bottom Trawlers

4.2.4 No support for the following proposed methods to avoid unwanted catch

Technical (Gear)

Spain-the Balearics	Sector
Bottom trawl fishers did not use gear modifications to avoid catching small-sized individuals because this is a highly multispecific fishery and the main problem is reduced to hake. For fishers, increasing the mesh size to reduce hake recruits would entail reducing the catches of small-sized species with important commercial value. Currently, with the implementation of the 40 mm square mesh cod-end this problem has been reduced because it reduces considerably the capture of individuals under the MLS.	Bottom Trawlers

Tactical (Strategies)

Spain-the Balearics	Sector
Traditionally, bottom trawlers only used northern-western Mallorca fishing grounds (Sóller) to take the red shrimp (<i>Aristeus antennatus</i>) during the summer and moved to southern grounds (Cabrera) during the winter months. This displacement was related to the individual size of the shrimp since fishermen avoided catching small-sized individuals. Nowadays, however, this migration pattern has been relaxed and both areas are exploited all the year round.	Bottom Trawlers

4.3 Adaptation of gear technology

A number of selectivity analyses have been conducted in the Balearic Islands.

1) A study by Zapata et al. compared catches and size composition, both from landings and discards, obtained by two different mesh types in the codend of bottom trawlers in the Balearic Islands (western Mediterranean) under commercial conditions. The results suggested that the 40 mm square mesh cod-end is more selective than the 50 mm diamond mesh cod-end (Figure 4.1). According to that, the current exemption of using 50 mm diamond mesh codend is not justified. Although this study reflects the potential benefits of the implementation of 40 mm square mesh in the cod-end, with a reduction of the discarded catches and an improvement of the exploitation pattern of the species, this improvement does not affect equally to all of them. In fact, most target species still have a length of first capture lower than their length of first maturity and some of them even have a length of first capture lower than their minimum landing size. Thus, additional measures should be implemented.

Figure 4.1 Yields of standardized biomass for the main taxonomic groups of the discarded fraction for the shallow shelf and for the middle slope from the Balearic Islands. 40D: 40 mm diamond mesh; 50D: 50 mm diamond mesh; 40S: 40 mm square mesh; ns: not significant; * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$.

2) A study by Guijarro et al. (2017) analyzed different measures to mitigate the direct and indirect impact of the bottom trawl fishery in the western Mediterranean, through three experiments and different technical measures: i) changing vessel operation routine and the mesh shape in the cod-end; ii) using more hydrodynamic bottom-doors, lighter gear and 40 mm square mesh in the cod-end; and iii) using mid-water doors not in contact with the seabed and 40 mm square mesh in the cod-end. Results showed that these measures can reduce the direct impact of bottom trawling on the seabed and its indirect impact on the ecosystems, through reducing discards and even the emission of CO₂ into the atmosphere. These outcomes, which allow improving the ecological efficiency of this fishery, have other direct positive consequences in the short term, as the reduction of its operation costs and hence the improvement of the economic efficiency. Reductions in the weekly activity would also improve the life conditions of the crew, an important aspect taking into account the difficulties of the fishing sector to offer attractive jobs for young people in coastal communities during the last decade, a key objective of the future Common Fisheries Policy. It is concluded that after years of studies focused on improving the sustainability of the Mediterranean bottom trawl fishery, it is about time to turn this improvement into reality.

3) A total of five different factsheets on selectivity were prepared by the IEO for the DiscardLess selectivity catalogue (http://www.discardless.eu/selectivity_manual), and contributed also to the selectivity manual (O'Neill and Mutch, 2017). These factsheets provide a brief description of catch comparison and selectivity trials that have been carried out by our scientific team in the western Mediterranean. The factsheets, which can be downloaded as a pdf from the link above, were: 1) Diamond and square mesh codends to improve the selectivity of the Mediterranean bottom trawl fishery; 2) Fitting square mesh panels to improve bottom trawl selectivity on the Mediterranean continental shelf; 3) Fitting square mesh panels to improve bottom trawl selectivity on the Mediterranean continental slope; 4) Using 50 mm diamond and 40 mm square mesh codends to improve the selectivity of the Mediterranean bottom trawl fishery; and 5) Using flexible sorting grids to improve the selectivity of the Mediterranean bottom trawl fishery.

Figure 4.2. Factsheets produced for the selectivity catalogue.

4.4 Adaptation of fishing strategies: The Scientists' story - identification of locations, times and practices to fish to avoid unwanted catch

4.4.1 Balearic Islands

The results for the Balearics are documented in details in the Chapter 6 of Deliverable D4.3 (Reid and Fauconnet 2018).

The surveys were used to model the spatial patterns of species abundance for the main commercial species. The maps showed that, in most cases, the main density areas of juveniles and adults do not overlap, which would allow defining specific areas to avoid catching hake individuals below the MLS (20 cm).

Figure 4.3. Density and hotspot persistence of hake individuals under and over the minimum landing size (MLS) in waters around the Balearic Islands.

The observer data were then used to provide a temporal dimension to this, and looked at both the catch make up, and the discarding practices. The results from this were a series of maps of species distribution, above and below MCRS, species overlaps, fishing grounds, discard hotspots etc.

Figure 4.4. Abundance of hake individuals under (discard; red) and over (legal; green) the minimum landing size in the main fishing grounds of this species in the Balearic Islands.

This was then all brought together in an on-line tool where fishermen could access: maps, from both surveys and observer data; biological data such as length distributions, maturity etc., by species and fishing ground; and discarding patterns. The app is available at http://www.discardless.eu/discard_maps

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Figure 4.5. Snapshot of the home page of the Shiny App produced as a decision support tool to assist fishers to make choices of fishing location to avoid discards.

4.4.2 Gulf of Lions

4.4.2.1 Mapping catches and discards of commercial species for spatial planning of trawler fisheries

In the Gulf of Lions, bottom-trawl fishery is multi-specific and little selective and is responsible for high discard rates and abrasion induced impacts on seabed. A spatial planning exercise was developed within the scope of Discardless and the local project Galion⁴¹ with the objective to reduce catches of commercial fish under MLS through spatio-temporal avoidance strategies. This required to solve the following three folds problem: i) where in time and space are found under-size individuals of exploited species, ii) what are important fishing grounds in terms of catches and value, iii) what spatial zoning strategies may be proposed to reduce discard and seabed impact while still maintaining trawler activities.

To answer these objectives the distribution of undersized catches of commercial species were mapped to evidence areas recurrently populated by juveniles over time. Then a spatial planning exercise was undertaken to evidence seasonal and persistent areas which should be avoided to lower discard and protect sensitive habitats while still mitigating impact on important fishery grounds use.

Several data sources were used to map spatio-temporal distribution of catches and discards. The MEDITS scientific survey data (stratified and standardised and bottom trawl catches, June 1994-2015)

⁴¹ <http://galion.amop.fr/> et <https://fr-fr.facebook.com/Projet-Galion-910339892354202/>

and PELMED scientific survey acoustic measurements (July 2003-2015) were used to obtain densities of theoretical discards. For other seasons, onboard observations of commercial catches were also used to estimate abundance ratio between theoretical discards and total catches. Finally, VMS data coupled to landing declarations and sales registers for each fishing vessel enable to localize fishing effort and georeferenced catches in weight and monetaty for each species. In total, 19 species, including two crustacians and two pelagic species were studied and included here. Survey and onboard observation were interpolated using ordinary kriging after geostatistical analysis. Catch data were aggregated monthly on a 3'x3' grid (2005-2015), then according to landing harbour of the catch. According to the quantity of available data, some maps had to aggregate several years of observations to be produced. However, the study of available yearly maps has highlighted the general stability over time of discards and catches distribution (Figure 4.6A).

Figure 4.6 A . Distribution of whiting discards 1994-2015 (MEDITS). B. Species by species distribution maps before and after 2009 (MEDITS and PELMED data)

However, onboard observation data have shown that the distribution could vary seasonally and that discard ration distribution was variable. Three «statistical seasons» were identified by clustering during which discard ratio appeared to remain stable: The first season was made of november, january, february and march, the second season April to August and the third was september, october and december. Some species are present homogeneously on a large coastal band (sardine) or over the whole study area (whiting, horse mackerel) while other are more patchy near the coast (anchovy) or offshore (red mullet, nephrops, shrimps) (Figure 4.6B). However, trawler catches are mainly located in coastal areas close to landing harbour and are remarkably stable over time (probably as the result of the fishing trip being limited to 12h).

These maps were then used to devise spatial planning of the fishery activity using the systematic conservation planning software MARXAN⁴², often used for designing MPA networks. This decision-helping tool aims to identify areas to be protected in order to meet set quantitative protection targets at a minimum cost using an optimization algorithm. It was used to identify potential seasonal or

⁴² Game E.T. & Grantham H.S. 2008 – Marxan User Manual: for Marxan version 1.8.10. University of Queensland, St. Lucia, Queensland, Australia & Pacific Marine Analysis and Research Association, Vancouver, British Columbia, Canada.
Ball I.R., Possingham H.P. & Watts M.E. 2009 – Marxan and relatives: Software for spatial conservation prioritization. – *Spatial conservation prioritisation : Quantitative methods and computational tools*, Chapter 14, p. 185-195.

permanent closure areas where juveniles or discards are abundant while avoiding limiting the use of areas of important economic interest for the trawlers' fleets. A large number of avoidance scenarios were produced to identify areas that should be closed in order to protect undersize individuals.

The protection target for individuals below MLS was set at 30%. In total, 96 management scenarios were tested with MARXAN, 2 gears, over 2 periods (before and after 2009), three seasons and permanent, taking into account existing fishery restricted area and MPAs or not. For each scenario, three degrees of fishery protection were considered to insure the viability of this activity. From this exercise, coastal areas were highlighted as particularly important to avoid discard. However, protecting trawling activities forces the selection of larger and more offshore areas to meet the same protection target. The more fishery activities are being maintained, the more it becomes difficult to find a planification scheme that would enable to meet the 30% protection target (Figure 4.7).

Figure 4.7 : Seasonal and permanent closure planning of trawler fishery. Bottom trawls (OTB), after 2009.

Catches and discards mapping as well as spatial planning approaches to fishery activities have highlighted the importance of the coastal areas in the Gulf of Lions. This area is both abundant in under size fish and an important fishing ground. Management compromise between exploitation and discard avoidance need to be found to ensure sustainable exploitation of many species. Spatial planning scenarios, including both discard avoidance objectives and elements of fishery grounds protection may constitute an interesting tool to help fishermen and scientists to elaborate future management plans and increase

their acceptability. However, forecasting the impact of discard avoidance management on the sustainability of trawler fisheries is often expected from scientist but this requires mecanistic models and dynamic approaches.

4.4.2.2 Hake trawlers spatial management in the Gulf of Lion: science-fishermen modelling efforts for realistic scenarios

For the last decade, overfishing occurred in the hake fishery of the Gulf of Lion (GSA 7), with fishing mortality assessed to be 12 times higher than F_{MSY} . About 90% of catch is harvested by French trawlers on the plateau, while Spanish trawlers and liners operate in deeper waters.

Since 2013, the PCP imposed decommissioning and effort restrictions in order to reach MSY by 2020 with no significant effects to date. (Figure 4.8). Within the Galion and Discardless projects, French trawlers organisations initiated collaborations with scientists in order to propose and evaluate management measures to reach this objective. The ISIS-Fish model was proposed to assess their impact on hake population dynamics and fleet performances.

Figure 4.8 : a) Fishing mortality estimated on the Hake fishery in the Gulf of Lion (in blue) and reference $F_{0.1} = 0.15$ (in red) , for 2015 to 2017 b) Hake catches for different fleets of the Gulf of Lion (Source : GFCM, sotck assessment form Demersal species, 2017)

Figure 4.9: Map of the study area, the species targeted and the trawlers of the gulf of lion on the left. Schematic representation of the ISIS-Fish model on the right.

The ISIS-Fish model has 3 components which interact in space and time (Figure 4.9). A biological sub-model that recreates the lifecycle of european hake; a fishery model that recreates the fishing activity in the study area, by modelling different métiers (combination of species, area, gear) and different fleets (vessels with the same technical characteristics) and their effort levels in course of the year; a management model that can constraint the fishing activity according to management in place and therefore indirectly impacts the dynamics of the species.

This model is integrative and requires several data sources. Here declarative data and VMS data were used for the spatial representation of effort and catch. Onboard observations were used to describe the age structure of catches, scientific survey (MEDITS) was used to explore hake distribution over the area. Finally stock assessment and literature were used to obtain important biological parameters for hake.

The biological model is age-structured (0 to 5+), spatially structured (figure 5.10) and emulate observed spatial and seasonal recruitment processes. The fishing model describes 24 métiers (gear x fishing areas x hake catches) and 12 fleets (Size of vessels x Landing harbor) and their strategies over time (Figure 4.11).

Figure 4.10 Parametrisation of distribution abundance of Hake with a : the plateau distribution and b : the canyon distribution

Figure 4.11 Proportion of use of 2 gears for one year of one of the strategy

Several parameters were assessed through a calibration phase. Observed catch available at various aggregation levels (month/quarter/year, country, age class of the fish) were confronted to simulated catch obtained for 20000 combinations of parameters values drawn from a Latin Hypercube Sampling. This allows us to adjust and understand the impact of the parameters on the model and select the combination that minimizes the differences between observed and simulated catch. Calibration was an iterative process which results were discussed with fishermen at each step to improve model

definition and common understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of the model at various scales. (Figure 4.12)

Figure 4.12 Representation of the participatory modelling process of the hake demersal fishery of the gulf of Lions using ISIS-Fish involving scientists and fishermen to assess the impact of management scenario

The first results of the model hindcast for the period 2015-2017 were compared to observation. At the annual scale, simulated catches fit with the trends but seasonality is not always well captured by the model (2017).

Figure 4.13 : Simulated catches of hake (blue) compared with the observed catches of hake (red) in the gulf of lion

At present this model still needs further improvement to better fit observed data but such improvement are soon to be obtained. Once appropriately calibrated, scenarios will be projected with the ISIS-Fish

model, and an uncertainty analysis will be performed on abundance, recruitment and connectivity to estimate the reliability of the different projections (Figure 4.14).

Figure 4.14: Graphical representation of expected results after the projection of the different scenarios and the uncertainty with the ISIS-Fish model

Proposed management scenarios were co-constructed with fishermen and will be assessed in the future. These were:

- Statu Quo : no change in the management of hake resource
- Closure of 100 meters zone from May to July
- Closure of FRA zone and additional zones (3 boxes in the gulf of lion)
- 10 % of reduction of Effort
- 30 % of reduction of effort
- 50 % of reduction of effort

Forecasted results will be assessed in term of distance to the main management objective (hake exploitation at MSY by 2020) and amount to effort reduction (both in number of days and in number of vessels) that will be needed to reach this objective under these different scenarios.

4.5 Summary – conclusions

The global perspectives on discards mitigation in the Mediterranean Sea are presented in the corresponding DiscardLess Policy Brief (Fitzpatrick et al., 2017, <http://www.discardless.eu/deliverables/entry/year-2-of-the-landing-obligation-key-issues-in-mediterranean-fisheries>)

According to fishermen, the main problem of small-sized fish is restricted to hake (*Merluccius merluccius*). Discard rates for all other species under the LO are low, except for horse mackerel *T. trachurus* (see D1.4). To avoid taking more catches of mackerel than the market can cope with, however, fishermen from the Balearic Islands use tactical strategies such as performing shorter hauls. For fishermen, increasing the mesh size to reduce hake and mackerel recruits would entail reducing the catches of small-sized species with important commercial value (e.g. picarel or cephalopods) that may constitute an important part of their catch value. Currently, with the implementation of the 40 mm square mesh cod-end this problem has been diminished because it reduces considerably the capture of individuals under the MLS. Although most trawlers from the Balearic Islands currently use this square mesh, it seems that its use has not been generalized along the Western Mediterranean. The square mesh, however, does not guarantee avoiding the catches of hake or mackerel under the MLS, whereby there is still scope for improving the fishery selectivity by changing the mesh size and shape or introducing other devices such as panels and grids.

Spatial management is widely used and supported in the Mediterranean as a strategy to reduce unwanted catches. Fishers highly support the mapping of juvenile hotspots, which should be based on scientific knowledge. Better identification of discards by area, by gear and by species may significantly assist with LO implementation, through enforceable temporary or permanent closures to avoid undersize hake in the trawl and purse seine fisheries. Spatial planning exercise, including both discard avoidance objectives and elements of fishery grounds protection may constitute an interesting tool to help fishermen and scientists to identify new management opportunities and increase their acceptability. However, forecasting the impact of discard avoidance management on the sustainability of trawler fisheries (which is still the primary objective of currently negotiated multi-annual management plan) demands analytically intense approaches and mechanistic models that require both time and trained human-resources to develop and run.

4.6 Published references and presentations in conferences

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5 Discards Mitigation Strategies in the Bay of Biscay case study

5.1 Overview of the case study and initial work objectives

The Bay of Biscay fisheries exploit a range of different species and a variety of fleets operate in the area, including industrial and artisanal fleets. All of these fleets have different levels, profiles and reasons for discarding. The **Bay of Biscay DiscardLess case study** focuses on bottom and pair trawlers. The selection of fleets using two different types of gear presents contrasts in how to avoid the unwanted catches given that the DMS effectiveness will likely vary from gear to gear. The costs, earnings and overall consequences of the landing obligation are evaluated by finding the appropriate(s) covariate(s) (WP2). The relevant strategies are simulated in a full-feedback process and results evaluated using economic and social indicators, integrating the work done in WP1, WP3 and WP4. The tools selected are presented to the relevant stakeholders as well as to representative vessels owners to evaluate the possible impacts and their applicability. The variables affecting the discards level are discussed, from fishers to scientists and vice versa, and the most appropriate gear changes are presented to fishers (WP3). Innovative alternatives for implementing on-board handling are evaluated with respect to their efficiency in handling and storing unwanted catches on a representative Basque trawler vessel. Implementation of control and traceability standards established in the project are evaluated on-board and at port (WP5). Costs and benefits from these standards are considered and validated. Finally, the low number of selling points offers significant opportunities in the processing of unavoidable unwanted catches to marketable products (WP6). *DiscardLess* evaluates the most suitable uses of unavoidable unwanted catches based on species specific allocation to animal feed or human consumption. Systems to classify and count the unwanted catches on land and appropriate cold storage conditions are tested. Pre-screening tests measure the consumer acceptance of the products selected for human consumption, and the valorisation alternatives are investigated. Finally, a pilot trial of the complete management cycle from landing of the unwanted species to the final destination is performed for each planned valorisation.

5.2 The Fishers story – documenting discard reduction practices suggested by stakeholders

A workshop was conducted with different skippers in order to see which were the likely measures to adapt the fleet (including fishing tactics and management) to the introduction of the landing obligation. The workshop was conducted over the end of the year 2014 (when the fleet stops for two weeks). Overall, 5 skippers were interviewed representing the 53% of the fleet studied.

In the workshop the skippers were asked about their awareness of the new (landing obligation) regulation. They answered that they only had some partial and confused information. In this context some explanations on the most relevant aspects of the new regulation affecting to their activity were given by the interviewers.

The main result obtained from the survey was the limited knowledge of the CFP and subsequent LO regulation. Skippers were asked to classify several alternatives to reduce unwanted catch in terms of the perceived utility from them. The proposed alternatives were: fishing gear bans, limits on the maximum quantity of discards (the de minimis exemption of the article 15 of CFP regulation), high

discards concentration area closures, juvenile concentration spatial area closures, seasonal area closures and improvements on selectivity to reduce unwanted species catch.

These alternatives were classified by the skippers as: useless (fishing gear ban), partial solutions (de minimis and area closures in general) and likely solutions (seasonal area closures and the improvements on selectivity).

According to the results of the workshop, the seasonal area closures could be applied when high concentrations of juvenile hake appear. The main conclusion was that improvements have to be based on increased selectivity, however they do not like to do any kind of investment without knowing that first the selectivity tool works and second that at least they not loose from applying it. In that sense the main indicator was to contrast the social gain (if there is) in terms of the value added with the private profits, with and without the improved selectivity.

5.3 Adaptation of gear technology

Three different factsheets were prepared for the DiscardLess selectivity catalogue (http://www.discardless.eu/selectivity_manual), and contributed also to the selectivity manual (O'Neill and Mutch, 2017). These factsheets provide a brief description of some catch comparison and selectivity trials that have been carried out in the Bay of Biscay: two trials by AZTI on square mesh panel (SMP) to reduce discarding of horse mackerel, mackerel, blue whiting and juvenile hake, but which showed only limited selectivity improvements; and one trial by IFREMER on using a flexible inclined grid in the lower panel of the extension to increase flat fish and anglerfish selectivity in whitefish fisheries.

5.4 Adaptation of fishing strategies

The main problem of this fleet related to the landing obligation is the choke effect caused by two pelagic species (mackerel and horse mackerel). These two species are target species in January and December, respectively. In January mackerel fishery is only accessible to bottom trawlers which implies high prices and therefore a directed fishery. The consequence of it is that quota is exhausted (by mid January). This creates the problem of bycatch of this species for the rest of the year. Currently (after year 2015), the fleet is making tactical decisions on avoiding mackerel hot spot areas, based on their knowledge. However, this does not imply that bycatches of this species are eliminated and therefore problems with the LO implementation are likely to continue in the future.

The problem with Horse Mackerel is different. This is not a directed fishery, but a none desired, or desired (depending on the market supply) fishery. Therefore, landings of this species by this fleet has been quite dependant on the market price. Again, the main effect of this species is the choke effect that it could potentially cause, when bycatches are produced.

In summary while strategic decisions on avoiding hot spot areas for these, small quota pelagic species have already been made, the main problem of choke effect has not been resolved. In the same time gear technology, identified by skippers as the option with the highest potential, has not been able to produce

results capable of reducing non desired catches of these two small pelagics for the trawl gears in the Bay of Biscay, at least without substantial losses on the catches of the main demersal target species.

5.5 Optimal use of unwanted catches

Most of the work performed in this case study has been concerning the optimal use of unavoidable unwanted catches (UUC), performed in WP5 and 6.

5.5.1 From deck to first sale

Work package 5 in the DiscardLess project has focused on providing stakeholders, such as fishermen and fishing vessel owners, with alternatives for on-board handling of the previously discarded catches.

Deliverables D5.2 (Viðarsson et al., 2016, <http://www.discardless.eu/deliverables/entry/report-containing-identification-and-recommendations>) and D5.4 (Viðarsson et al., 2017, http://www.discardless.eu/adapting_fishing_vessels) have analysed solutions on on-board handling of unwanted, unavoidable catches for four different fleet segments, of which a typical medium-size Spanish bottom trawler from the Bay of Biscay.

These bottom trawlers are typically 34 to 44 meters in length, 8 to 10-meter-wide, around 400 GT, with 800-1200 hp engines and a crew of 8-10 persons (Figure XX, photo: Jonas R. Viðarsson)

Figure 5.1: Typical medium sized mixed demersal bottom trawler fishing in the Bay of Biscay

This fleet catch a great diversity of species (>60) but many of them are unwanted and discarded and discard rates can be very high (cf Table 5.1 extracted from D5.2).

Table 5.1: Reported landings and discards of the OTD fleet in the Basque country in 2013

Species	Catch (T)	Landed (T)	Discards (T)	Discard rate
Anglerfish	205	200	5	2%
Black-bellied angler	353	343	10	3%

Blue whiting	192	1	191	99%
Hake	499	305	194	39%
Horse mackerel	903	121	782	87%
Mackerel	907	9	898	99%
Megrim	249	241	8	3%
Other	5.771	1.616	4.155	72%
Total	9.079	2.836	6.243	69%

The main challenge for the OTD Bay of Biscay fleet in regards to on-board handling will be on how to deal with catches below MCRS, which cannot be utilised for direct human consumption.

In Deliverable D5.2, the current on-board handling for a representative Basque vessel was analysed, and alternative options were proposed, together with some preliminary economic analyses of the costs and benefits of the different options.

Figure 5.2: Technical drawing of the demonstration vessel

The catching is carried out normally with an otter trawl, the trawl is hauled on to the upper deck and the fish released down to the reception on the processing deck (marked nr.1 in Figure 5.3 **Error! Reference source not found.**). There is a feed up on conveyor belt which leads to the sorting station (2). All lean whitefish is bled, gutted and washed at the sorting station but other catch is carried straight through sorting without bleeding or gutting. Discards are also sorted out at the sorting station, and then sent onwards on the conveyor belt straight into the discard chute (3). The fish is sorted into plastic*

* The Basque fleet has traditionally used wooden boxes, but in 2014 the deep sea fleet of Ondarroa swapped out all wooden boxes for plastic.

boxes and then sent to the washing station where the fish is merged in seawater and water nozzle spraying used to clean blood and viscera away (4). The boxes, with the fish in it are then transferred to a lift (5) that sends the boxes down to the hold where a crewmember puts ice on it and stacks the boxes.

Figure 5.3: Current on-board handling procedures on the processing deck

DiscardLess analysed a number of available alternatives for improving on-board handling on the demonstration vessel, both in regard to target catches and UUC. Improving bleeding, gutting, cleaning and chilling will benefit the target catches in particular, although will also contribute to better quality of UUC in cases where unwanted catches are landed for further on-land processing. Ensuring best possible quality of the UUC increases opportunities for maximising value, particularly if they are to be used for added value production such as pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, food supplements, enzymes, collagen, gelatine, pet food etc.

The simplest alternative is to store all UUC in bulk in the hold, where larger tubs can be used as opposed to the smaller boxes used for the target catches. The catch can then be sorted when during landing and consequently sent to the proper production chains. Two other options were also explored low-value non-human consumption, such as fishmeal, animal feed, fertilizer or similar: silage and hydraulic compression.

Bleeding, washing and cooling

Whatever the use of UUC, DiscardLess suggested that the current practices on the processing deck of the demonstration vessel did not meet with “best practice” on-board handling procedures, especially with regards to bleeding, cleaning and cooling of the catches, and could be improved. This does not directly address the implementation of the landing obligation, but does however have indirect impact as proper on-board handling increases the options for utilising UUC and makes it easier to cope with increased volumes that need to be handled. To ensure that the catch is bled and cleaned under optimal conditions

it is recommended to provide the crew with good facilities for bleeding and gutting, and to install a bleeding tank that ensures right throughput. It is also recommended to install a pre-cooling tank to make sure that catches are cooled down to 0 °C as soon as possible. A well organised sorting station is also needed. A possible setup for this is shown in Figure 5.4, where the catch comes from the reception through to the bleeding and gutting station (1) from where it goes to the bleeding & cleaning tank (2). It takes each fish 5-10 minutes to go through the bleeding & cleaning tank where there is a good circulation of fresh seawater. The next station is the pre-cooling tank (3) which is filled with refrigerated seawater (RSW). To ensure constant supply of RSW there is a need to fit some sort of machine with built-in heat exchanger for the production of the RSW, which should ideally be located close to the pre-cooling tank. The most economically feasible option for creating the RSW is probably to fit a slurry ice machine down in the engine room and let it manufacture slurry into a reservoir tank located on the processing deck (5). The time needed to cool the catch down to 0°C is variable, depending on throughput and size of each fish, but 20-30 minutes is usually an appropriate time. Following the pre-cooling the catch is sent to the sorting station where the catch is sorted and arranged into boxes (4). The boxes are then sent as before to the elevator that sends them to the refrigerated hold. A crewmember down in the hold adds ice to the boxes and stacks them accordingly (separating clearly between fish intended for human and non-human consumption).

Figure 5.4: Suggested reconstruction of the demonstration vessel's processing deck. (1. Sorting / bleeding and gutting - 2. Bleeding / cleaning tank - 3. Pre-cooling tank - 4. Sorting / packaging - 5. RSW tank / reservoir for slurry ice

Compressing of UUC

The possibility of compressing UUC on-board fishing vessels to reduce volume are currently being explored by scientists (Pérez-Gálvez, et al., 2015). These are not yet marketable solutions, but might in immediate future become a viable alternative. The research and pilot testing show that the volume can

be reduced by 40-45% with this method and that the product(s) can be used for fishmeal and value-added compounds. The production process is shown in Figure 5.5.

Figure 5.5: Production process for compressing UUC

The UUC is first cut into small pieces and then placed in a hydraulic press that compresses the raw material into a press cake. The liquid is filtrated to collect any proteins that would otherwise be lost. The press cake should ideally be frozen and stored in a freezer hold to maintain quality, but that is likely to present a problem on the demonstration vessel, as well as on most fishing vessels in this fleet group. The vessels are not equipped with a freezer hold or plate freezers.

Estimating costs and benefits associated with this alternative is difficult, as this is still only at a research and development phase. It is nevertheless an option well worth considering.

Silage preservation

Silage preservation and/or production of fully prepared silage can be seen as one of the more realistic potential on-board handling methods for UUC, especially for catches that cannot be used for direct human consumption, such as catches below MCRS. Silage is most commonly used for production of animal feed and is then mixed with other less expensive ingredients in order to increase fat and protein content of the feed, along with contributing other positive properties like omega3 and variety of vitamins. The silage can be added to feed in different formats i.e. wet, dried or semi-dried silage. It can also be produced into fish meal, which is then used for animal feed. Fish silage production is a big industry in some countries, like in Norway.

The production of fish silage is relatively simple, requires little energy and little extra effort for crewmembers, and all rest raw materials can be utilised for the production as well. The acidification of the silage increases the shelf life of the material which can be extended up to two years with only little reduction of quality. No temperature control is required in the storage and transportation since the acid works as a preserver of the material, which is definitely one of the big advantages of this method. When silage preservation is compared to other preservation methods such as freezing, cooling and/or

maintaining material frozen or cooled through transport and in storage, the advantages of low energy use becomes even clearer.

The silage preservation process can generally be broken into three main steps, shown in Figure 5.6.

Figure 5.6: Processing streams and setup for silage preservation

The mincing is necessary to get a uniform raw material of the correct size and to activate the enzymes in the viscera. The primary silage tank is used to blend the raw material with the acid and trigger the digestion; and the secondary silage tank is to store the silage and maintain digestion.

Additional details on the silage technology can be found in DiscardLess Deliverable D5.2 and in the book chapter (Viðarsson et al., 2019, https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-03308-8_16)

The suggested setup for silage preservation/production on-board the demonstration vessel is shown in Figure 5.7.

Figure 5.7: Suggested setup for silage preservation on-board the demonstration vessel

The UUC is separated from the target catches at the sorting/bleeding & gutting station (1), the UUC subjected to the landing obligation is then placed on a conveyor belt (2) that sends it to a mincer (3). UUC not subjected to catch limits are either discarded through the discard chute (6) or used for silage. After mincing the raw material is pumped to the primary silage tanks (5) and the acid dispenser (4) measures correct amount of formic acid to be added. The secondary silage tank is located on the deck below and the rest of the processing line is the same as shown above.

An even more advanced setup for that demonstration trawler was suggested in Deliverable D5.4, using 3D drawings. The suggested changes on the processing deck are aimed handling target catch and other valuable catch according to best-practise, where each fish is subjected to optimised bleeding, cleaning, chilling and storage. It does also enable, where appropriate, quick handling of UUC where it is separated from the target catch and sent directly to the hold.

There are three distinctive paths that lead from the bleeding station. The first handles the UUC and fish under MCRS which are not bled or gutted due to their poor value. The second is for the target catch that only needs bleeding. The last handles the target catch that needs to be bled, gutted and cooled. This makes the processing more flexible, as the target species are bled on time and directly placed in a bleeding tank. Figure 5.8 shows how two bleeding tanks are placed in front of the gutting station, one can serve as a batch related bleeding tank while the other is constantly conveyed at controlled speed. The reason for this is that some species, such as mackerel are not necessarily desired together with other more sensitive species in both the bleeding and cooling tanks.

Figure 5.8: Overview of the production deck. The deck is separated into production room at left and packaging room at right. No.1-Path for UUC/MCRS, No.2-Target catch (only bled), No.3-Target catch (bled, gutted, cooled), No.4-Rotary cooling tank, No.5-Slurry ice buffer tank, No.6-Fish buffer tank with slurry ice, No.7-Elevator down to hold, No.8-Silage unit.

In this deliverable is also produced a cost-benefit tool, which can provide a quick appraisal of the economic consequences of these alternative options for on-board handling. The tool is available from the DiscardLess website http://www.discardless.eu/adapting_fishing_vessels.

5.5.2 Products to the value chain

Most of the developments in WP6 have taken place in this case study, with a specific focus on the Basque country in Spain. There is thus extensive work to refer to in this topic.

Inventory of current facilities

Deliverable D6.1 (Viðarsson et al., 2016, <http://www.discardless.eu/deliverables/entry/diagnosis-of-the-inventory-of-the-generated-unavoidable-unwanted-catch>) made an inventory of the potential level of UUC that could be expected to be landed if the landing obligation was fully implemented and enforced, as well as of the existing logistic facilities already usable in some selected harbours.

Hake, mackerel and horse mackerel are the three main species landed, though with considerable variability of landings by species over time. Landings of previously discarded catches under LO will consist of many species and low volumes of each species, mainly small fish below MCRS. which will

require special production streams that produce products that are not intended for direct human consumption.

A review and visits of the infrastructures and facilities in the Basque country and neighbouring provinces were performed. In the Basque Country, there are eleven fishing ports, but more than 90 % of the landings are accounted in five harbours i.e. Ondarroa, Getaria, Hondarribia, Bermeo and Pasaia (Red marks in Figure 5.9). The main processing facilities are however not necessarily located in those five harbours.

Figure 5.9: Map with fishing ports (Red and Orange marks) and processing facilities (Green and Blue marks) in the Basque Country

The available landing data suggests that current capacity in the Basque country harbours can handle more than twice the average amount of fish landed there in recent years. Lack of space, facilities or management problems are therefore not foreseen with increased landings due to the implementation of the LO.

The analysis of existing infrastructures published in deliverable D6.1 revealed that there are already a lot of facilities in place in the main harbours. Current infrastructure for products intended for human consumption are for the main part likely to be sufficient to cope with changing supplies associated with the LO. However, separated channels will for example have to be set up for fish under MCRS, as those materials must be treated separately.

Suitable uses and valorisation alternatives for UUC

Most suitable uses or valorisation alternatives for the unavoidable unwanted catches (UUC) have been evaluated, gathering the most important factors that may influence the technic and economic viability of each option, to allow the correct implementation of the most suitable option. A review of existing and innovative valorisation options for fish products has been done and more than 30 valorisation products have been listed and evaluated classified as: Food applications, Bio-Products (value compounds for food, cosmetic or other uses), Feed, Industrial uses, Energy production or Agronomic. This review is described in the book chapter by Iñarra et al. (2019, https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-03308-8_17) and presented in the form of simplified and visual factsheets on http://www.discardless.eu/valorisation_module.

In a second step, a systematic and simplified methodology for the selection of the best option has been established. Main criteria have been grouped in categories to estimate the most important effects and weighted to obtain a score for each valorisation option. The methodology gives a prioritization on valorisation options that may facilitate the evaluation and establishment of UUC management systems. The approach is also described in (Iñarra et al., 2019).

The methodology has been applied to the BoB CS to determine best approach for the adaptation to the LO and the inland management of UUC. First, the qualitative suitability of the different species for the different valorisation options was estimated as follows (Table 5.2 Valorisation options for distinct species based on a case study as part of the H2020 DiscardLess project in the Bay of Biscay Table 5.2)

Table 5.2 Valorisation options for distinct species based on a case study as part of the H2020 DiscardLess project in the Bay of Biscay

		ANY FISH	Blackbellied angler (<i>Lophius budegassa</i>)	European hake (<i>Merluccius</i>)	Horse mackerel (<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>)	Atlantic mackerel (<i>Scomber scombrus</i>)	Megrim (<i>Lepidorhombus whiffiagonis</i>)	Angler (<i>Lophius piscatorius</i>)	Blue whiting (<i>Micromesistius poutassou</i>)
Food	New fish products		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Surimi		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Fish pulp		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Bio-Products	Bioactive peptides				X	X			
	Polyunsaturated fatty acids		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Enzymes								
	Chondroitin sulphate								
	Fat-soluble vitamins				X	X			
	Minerals		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Astaxanthin								
	Collagen			X		X	X		
	Gelatine			X		X	X		
	Sterols				X				
	Insulin		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Protamine								
	Hyaluronic acid								
	Chitin / Chitosan								
	Phospholipids				X	X			
Peptone	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Squalene									
Feed	Fish meal	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Fish oil	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Mink feed		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Marine beef/bait		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Direct pig feed		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Protein concentrate	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Protein hydrolysate	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Silage	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Insect growth		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Industrial uses	Leather								
	Fish oil	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Minerals		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Chitin / chitosan								
	Pearl essence			X	X	X			
	Biogas	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Agronomic uses	Compost	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Fertilisers	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Second, the quantitative suitability using the scoring methodology described in the article resulted in the following ranking (Table 5.3):

Table 5.3 Prioritisation evaluation of valorisation options for the Bay of Biscay case study. (A: Available raw material; B: Available facilities; C: Yield; D: Technology maturity; E: Value of the product; F: Potential market; G: Production costs; H: Competing companies; V_{CS} : case study score, V_{tech} : technical score; V_{eco} : economic score; V_p : priority value).

Criterion	CS dependent			Technical parameters			Economical parameters					V_p
	A	B	V_{CS}	C	D	V_{tech}	E	F	G	H	V_{eco}	
Weighting coefficient	10	7	10	7	3	7	10	10	7	1	3	
New fish products	5	5	1.00	5	5	1.00	3	5	3	1	0.73	0.96
Surimi	5	0	0.59	3	5	0.72	3	3	1	1	0.49	0.62
Fish pulp	5	5	1.00	3	5	0.72	1	5	5	5	0.71	0.86
Bioactive peptides	5	1	0.67	3	3	0.60	5	3	1	3	0.64	0.64
Polyunsaturated fatty acids	5	3	0.84	3	5	0.72	3	5	3	1	0.73	0.78
Enzymes	0	0	0.00	1	1	0.20	1	1	1	1	0.20	0.10
Chondroitin sulphate	0	3	0.25	1	3	0.32	5	3	1	1	0.63	0.33
Fat-soluble vitamins	5	0	0.59	1	3	0.32	3	5	1	1	0.63	0.50
Minerals	5	1	0.67	3	5	0.72	1	5	5	3	0.70	0.69
Astaxanthin	0	0	0.00	1	5	0.44	5	3	1	3	0.64	0.25
Collagen	5	3	0.84	1	5	0.44	3	3	3	1	0.59	0.66
Gelatine	5	3	0.84	1	5	0.44	3	3	3	1	0.59	0.66
Sterols	5	0	0.59	1	1	0.20	3	3	0	3	0.45	0.43
Insulin	5	0	0.59	3	1	0.48	3	1	0	0	0.29	0.50
Protamine	0	0	0.00	1	3	0.32	5	1	1	1	0.49	0.18
Hyaluronic acid	0	0	0.00	1	3	0.32	5	3	1	1	0.63	0.21
Chitin / Chitosan	0	0	0.00	1	5	0.44	5	3	3	1	0.73	0.26
Phospholipids	5	0	0.59	1	3	0.32	3	3	1	3	0.50	0.48
Peptone	5	1	0.67	3	5	0.72	1	1	3	1	0.30	0.63
Squalene	0	0	0.00	1	3	0.32	5	3	1	1	0.63	0.21
Fish meal	5	5	1.00	5	5	1.00	1	5	5	1	0.69	0.95
Fish oil	5	5	1.00	5	5	1.00	1	5	5	1	0.69	0.95
Mink feed	5	3	0.84	5	3	0.88	1	1	5	3	0.41	0.79
Marine beef/bait	5	1	0.67	5	3	0.88	1	1	5	3	0.41	0.71
Direct pig feed	5	1	0.67	5	3	0.88	1	3	5	3	0.56	0.73
Protein concentrate	5	3	0.84	5	5	1.00	3	5	3	3	0.74	0.88
Protein hydrolysate	5	3	0.84	5	5	1.00	3	5	3	3	0.74	0.88
Silage	5	0	0.59	5	5	1.00	1	3	5	3	0.56	0.73
Insect growth	5	0	0.59	5	1	0.76	1	3	5	5	0.57	0.65
Leather	0	3	0.25	1	5	0.44	3	1	3	5	0.47	0.35
Fish oil	5	5	1.00	5	5	1.00	0	5	5	0	0.61	0.94
Minerals	5	3	0.84	3	5	0.72	0	3	5	3	0.49	0.74
Chitin / Chitosan	0	0	0.00	3	5	0.72	1	3	3	1	0.44	0.32
Pearl essence	5	0	0.59	1	5	0.44	1	1	3	3	0.31	0.50
Biogas	5	1	0.67	1	3	0.32	1	3	3	1	0.44	0.51
Compost	5	1	0.67	3	3	0.60	0	3	5	1	0.47	0.62
Fertilisers	5	1	0.67	3	5	0.72	1	3	5	1	0.54	0.67

The valorisation options with the best scores for the main discarded species are:

- Mackerel and horse mackerel study: new food products (96%) or fish pulp (86%) have the higher score. This option can also be taken into consideration for blue whiting (~300 kg/year) if not <MCRS.
- Due to legislation, hake (<MCRS) cannot be directed to food products so the next options are: fish meal and fish oil, with a score of 95% or fish protein hydrolysate, with a score of 88%. This last option could score higher if hydrolysates were focused on human consumption as a flavouring agent.
- This option is also the main possibility when quantities of other UWC are too low for more specific solutions.

In the book chapter by Iñarra et al. (2019), a second approach is also described, based on the analysis and optimization of economic and environmental parameters. This approach was not developed as part of DiscardLess, but as part of another research project, LIFE iSEAS, and was applied to the highly mixed discards of the Galician fleet. Here, the preferred options were fish mince blocks, protein hydrolysates with bioactive peptides and chondroitin sulphate.

Pilot trials

At the end of the project, a pilot trial was performed to test the feasibility of the options selected.

More precisely the trial was done with an OTD trawler fishing in the VIIIb in a 6 day fishing trip in the BoB.

The results of pilot demonstrations are key to design an accurate road map as any potential logistic or UUC processing setbacks emerge. Hence, a better knowledge of all these potential setbacks contribute to reduce the economic risk of the adopted final UUC valorisation alternatives as well as estimating the required time to market of UUC origin final products. The validation of the Action

The results showed the feasibility of the different solution proposed (Fish pulps; Fishmeal and oil and Protein hydrolysates) both technically and economically.

In the short term, fishmeal producers are ready to receive and process all the expected UUC. However, a better payback is expected for fishermen if more valuable options, such as the production of fish pulp or fish hydrolysates, are undertaken.

Automatic system for by-catch classification

In a different topic, two new technologies were developed in the Bay of Biscay for the identification, classification and quantification of catches. These are reported in Deliverable D6.3 (Melado et al., 2018)

First, an **automatic system** has been developed **for the quantification and classification at land** of the bycatch when these are landed in mixed bulk. An innovative artificial vision technology has been designed and tested with 6 species (horse mackerel, blue whiting, small hake, mackerel, anchovy and sardine).

After proper calibration and training through machine learning technology, the software is able to process and analyse pictures of the fish passing on the band.

Figure 5.10.. Acquisition module

The results reported in D6.3 demonstrated a good performance of the software, with correct identification of the majority of the fish. The main issue identified is that a number of mackerel were misidentified as small hake.

Table 5.4. Confusion matrix of the classification

		Predicted class					
		Anchovy	Blue whiting	Black mackerel	Small hake	Sardine	Mackerel
True class	Anchovy	90 %	0 %	5 %	5 %	0 %	0 %
	Blue whiting	0 %	100 %	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %
	Horse mackerel	0 %	0 %	90 %	10 %	0 %	0 %
	Small hake	0 %	5 %	0 %	95 %	0 %	0 %
	Sardine	0 %	0 %	13 %	0 %	87 %	0 %
	Mackerel	0 %	0 %	0 %	33 %	0 %	67 %

A full design of its up-scaling and linking with conveyor belts and electrically or pneumatically activated devices for the physical separation of the catch was also performed.

A system with four parallel way was designed (**Error! Reference source not found.**). Once landed in bulk, the catches are loaded in the system by an automated container dumper. Then the catches are elevated by a dosage conveyor (1) and put in a V shaped slide that help the fish to accommodate in the correct direction. As fish is a difficult material to handle, further separation and accommodation is foreseen in a vibration belt (2). Then, discards drop in a further conveyor with higher speed to separate the pieces and make them go through the “artificial vision system” for the identification and quantification. This conveyor has to be provided with an encoder that will indicate the position of the discard once it leaves the vision system, to activate one or another selection palette (6) that will drop the catch to a final conveyor up to its storage.

With this configuration the system may be so far able to classify up to 14 kg/min of discards, but the identification speed is highly dependent on the size of the catches and its distribution, bigger fish being easier to classify than small ones.

Figure 5.11. Design of a four-way system. 1- Material reception and lifter conveyor. 2- Vibrating conveyor 3- Classification conveyor with encoder. 4- Conveyor of sorted fishes. 5- Reception boxes. 6. Mechanical Actuators. 7- Bulk fish loader.

Overall, the classification prototype has provided successful results, and the possibilities for this system in an inland custom are very interesting and can help identifying and sorting UUC landed in bulk.

Second, an **alternative use of species identity molecular methods** is developed, complementing the fully documented genetic methods developed in Deliverable D5.3 with a quicker and simpler, but slightly less accurate alternative tool with a different purpose. Based on Real Time PCR and Sequencing, this tool aims at obtaining an immediate on-site control of the presence/absence of valuable fish and/or non-compliance discards in the value chain (including in a non-identified mix such as blanded pulp or silage), which can be operated by less qualified personal in an industrial environment. The system used a methodology called RPA (recombinase polymerase amplification), which allow for rapid DNA detection. For example, for detecting the presence of cod in a mix, a discriminating gene sequence must first be identified, distinguishing cod from other gadoids. Once this has been identified (109 base pairs (bp) belong to mitochondrial cytochrome b gene in the case of cod), an RPA assay test applied on that sequence would be able to detect the presence of cod after 5 minutes, not only within a pure cod sample (top figure) but also in mixed samples where cod represented only 5 % of the biomass (bottom figure)

Figure 5.12. COD (*Gadus morhua*) specificity RPA Exo-assay. A number of individuals (n) of different gadoid species; ALK: *Theragra chalcogramma* ($n=5$); WHG: *Merlangius merlangius* ($n=3$); PCO: *Gadus macrocephalus* ($n=2$); GRC: *Gadus ogac* ($n=2$); LIN: *Molva molva* ($n=4$); HAD: *Melanogrammus aeglefinus* ($n=5$); WHB: *Micromesistius poutasou* ($n=3$); POK: *Pollachius virens* ($n=5$); BLI: *Molva dypterygia* ($n=3$); POL: *Pollachius pollachius* ($n=4$); USK: *Brosme brosme* ($n=3$). Negative Template Control (NTC). Y-axis indicates fluorescence units (mV) and X-axis the time (minutes)

Figure 5.13. COD (*Gadus morhua*) limit of detection RPA Exo-assay in six different binary samples (95 % HKK: 5 % COD) Negative Template Control (NTC). Y-axis indicates fluorescence units and X-axis the time (minutes). HKK: *Merluccius capensis*

Ultimately, the test was optimised and simplified to return a simple presence/absence signal in a lateral flow format. In the **Error! Reference source not found.A** is shown a lateral flow with a clear detectable positive test line (COD). No cross-detection was observed with the DNA isolated from other gadoid fish species. Finally, the limit of detection of this assay was also 5 % (**Error! Reference source not found.B**).

Figure 5.14. **(A)** Cod specificity RPA Nfo-assay **(B)** Cod limit of detection RPA Nfo-assay with five binary samples. COD: *Gadus morhua*. HKK: *Merluccius capensis*. Test line (T); Internal Control line (C). Negative Template Control (NTC)

5.6 Summary – conclusions

It has been obtained that the economic effects are complex to study. Landing obligation and in particular the choke effect will have a short term negative effect, while in the long-term fishing firms will improve their profitability, gaining from the increased abundance of the target stocks. Everything is mixed with the management in place, given that the top up procedure of setting TACs, has none neutral effects on the fleets.

Improving the selectivity has been signalled by the industry as the most likely measure from the industry, however, simulations show how this increased selectivity reduces the economic profitability, at least if changes in the stock abundance do not help on that.

For the trawl fleet in the Bay of Biscay, the main problem comes from the choke effect of the pelagic species. Mackerel and Horse mackerel have directed trips (based on high market prices) in different periods of the year. However, quota is small, and therefore one the directed fishery ends they become bycatch. Even if hot spot areas are currently avoided, the solution is complex, specially for the more mixed demersal métier of this fleet, given that selectivity changes proposed and scientifically tested have not been successful on that.

There is a broad range of possibilities to valorise fish and fish compounds, however, not all the solutions are able to deal with the huge variability of the expected landings.

The harbour of the Basque country, and also other harbours of the BoB have the facilities and infrastructures ready to receive the UUC if they are finally landed. However, available valorisation solutions have low profitability and more profitable ones need in most cases of investments that are not foreseen with current UUC landings.

The implementation of automatic classification systems in land, or even better on board, may boost the fully implementation of the LO limiting the increase of the manpower need on board.

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6 Discards Mitigation Strategies in the Celtic Sea case study

6.1 Overview of the case study and initial work objectives

The **Celtic Sea case study** focuses on the mixed demersal whitefish fishery. This case is particularly relevant as the fishery is multinational, catches many species together, and has a number of potential choke species that can lead to high discarding. It is particularly important at present as many of the key commercial species can produce burst of recruitment, resulting in large numbers of juveniles on the grounds. We make a comparison of the landing obligation progress, its implementation and impacts in the context of Irish, French and UK vessels operating in the area (WP2). It takes forward the decision support tool and collaborative approaches being developed in the EU-funded DEMARA project to assess the biological and economic consequences of discard avoidance (WP2 & 7). The case study is centred on collaboration between fishers and scientists to identify areas with elevated levels of unwanted species (TAC limited or undersize fish), using both tacit knowledge and scientific data from observer trips and surveys (WP4). We use this information to experimentally challenge individual fishers to minimise unwanted catch while maintaining economic viability (WP4), and to identify tools including gear (WP3) that could be included in regional discard plans (WP7). It will contrast the different outcomes in relation to economic, governance and social factors in the three Member States.

This deliverable reports thus on the outcomes of WP3 and WP4 for this case study.

6.2 The Fishers story – documenting discard reduction practices suggested by stakeholders

Twenty Fisheries stakeholders from Ireland were interviewed, regarding their own ideas of why they discard and what they currently do and think about it. The results are described in Deliverable D4.1, finalised in April 2017 (Reid et al., 2017). The results of this task have also been brought online into a visual display on http://www.discardless.eu/fishermen_story.

The answers received from the Irish stakeholders were as follows:

6.2.1 Causes and levels of discarding:

Ireland	Sector
Discarding is caused by quota restrictions. In particular, many interviewees emphasised the interactions of the Landing Obligation with Relative Stability. Specifically where they had relatively small quotas for a species, despite relatively high abundance of those fish on the grounds. A key example was for cod and haddock in the Celtic Sea, with low quota, and whiting with a high quota. This caused real issues as these species were often caught together.	All interviewees
Only undersized and damaged fish are discarded.	Single-rig whitefish trawler
Discard levels <5% are possible within the fishery.	Whitefish trawler & seiner
Discarding needs to be reduced but a certain level is inevitable.	Whitefish trawler
Discard ban should be about simultaneously forcing the landing of marketable fish and selectivity improvements.	Whitefish trawler

The mismanagement of quotas and how they are allocated throughout the year (often with little/none left for certain species in the last few months of the year) makes it impossible to avoid discarding.	Nephrops Trawler
Generally can manage to avoid exceeding quota apart from when encounter unexpected 'lightning strike' hauls with an unusually high amount of a quota species.	Whitefish trawler
There is less fishing and time at sea for small boats in winter as restricted by weather so easier to keep inside quota at this time of year.	Whitefish trawler

6.2.2 Current methods used to avoid unwanted catch

Technical (Gear)

Ireland	Sector
Square mesh panel is effective, especially in avoiding whiting, hake, megrim and monk and a lot of juveniles.	All
Quad rig significantly reduces fish catch in prawn trawler in comparison to twin rig.	Quad-rig prawn trawler
100mm mesh size across all of net (not just cod end) to avoid small unwanted catch.	Single-rig whitefish trawler

Tactical (Strategies)

Ireland	Sector
Knowledge of location of spawning grounds allows for the avoidance of <MCRS fish at certain times of year in some locations.	All except prawn trawlers
Vessels are constantly moving between fishing grounds to try and avoid cod and haddock (choke species) as much as possible. This can include moving between management units.	Whitefish trawlers
Information is shared between vessels if the other skippers are known/trusted and this can help to avoid unwanted catch.	Whitefish trawlers
"Moving on", i.e. moving away from a location where high catch rates of <MCRS fish, or possibly choke species was mentioned outside the interviews.	All

6.2.3 Interest expressed in additional methods to avoid unwanted catch

Technical (Gear)

Ireland	Sector
Larger meshes are a key to reducing unwanted catch and the minimum mesh size should be raised to at least 100mm across the fleet.	Whitefish trawler and seiner (not prawn fishery)

Use of larger meshes (120mm) should be rewarded with extra quota.	Whitefish trawler and seiner
Need tamper-proof gear technology and this (along with mesh size) needs to be properly inspected and policed.	Whitefish trawler and seiner
Need a fast track system so that changes to fishing gear that can reduce discards can be introduced easily and quickly.	Whitefish trawler

Tactical (Strategies)

Ireland	Sector
Information sharing on where there are lots of unwanted catch could be useful (but reluctant to share information on commercially important catches).	Whitefish/prawn trawler
Respondant would use information/maps on when and where spawning is taking place every year. They feel that although they have good knowledge on spawning areas, this is can vary in timings between years.	Whitefish/prawn trawler

Management

Ireland	Sector
Anything would be better than the current quota system.	Prawn/whitefish trawler
Spreading quotas over a longer time period (bi-monthly or quarterly) would provide useful flexibility and allow for better planning.	Whitefish and prawn trawlers
Local management that was given control to respond to what is on the ground would be useful.	Seiner
Pooled quota may help a little.	Seiner
Days at sea would be better as much harder to cheat the system and lie about amount caught.	Whitefish trawler
Need an effort based management system, or equally a management approach that does not depend on very tight quota restrictions.	Whitefish trawlers and seiners
Rolling area closures to protect spawning and nursery habitats for skates and rays in the Irish and Celtic Seas.	Whitefish Trawlers
Need reallocation of unused quota across Europe to address issues with choking under LO (doesn't have to be on a permanent basis, just when one nation has excess that another country is in need of at that time).	Whitefish trawlers and seiners

6.2.4 No support for the following proposed methods to avoid unwanted catch

Technical (Gear)

Gear-technology often provides little help in a mixed fisheries as can't avoid everything.	Prawn/whitefish trawler
Grids are difficult to use and not very effective.	Nephrops trawlers

Tactical (Strategies)

Ireland	Sector
Information sharing won't work outside of immediate friends/colleagues as there is no belief that people will be honest or willing to share information as there is no real incentive to do so. Also not really needed as they consider themselves to have lots of personal knowledge on where things are, and where best to fish.	Whitefish trawlers and seiners
Real-time closures won't work as there is a lack of decent real-time information to allow these areas to be effectively designed or implemented and fluctuations in fish populations are too short-term and sporadic for them to work.	Whitefish trawlers and seiners
Seasonal closures would likely restrict access to target species too much – but some support from other vessels for the Celtic Sea box closure. Cape ground (near Greencastle) closure for cod has had less evidence of benefit.	Whitefish trawler
Pooled co-op or community based quota management wouldn't be effective as not enough quota available to share out.	Whitefish and prawn trawlers

6.3 Adaptation of gear technology

Gear selectivity catalogue

A total of 14 different factsheets on gear trials were prepared for the DiscardLess selectivity catalogue (http://www.discardless.eu/selectivity_manual), and contributed also to the selectivity manual (O'Neill and Mutch, 2017). These factsheets provide a brief description of catch comparison and selectivity trials that have been carried out in the Celtic Sea. These comprise 7 factsheets provided by CEFAS (UK) [100mm square mesh panels in the codend to improve size selection and reduce undersized haddock in ICES Area VII (2 sheets); 115 and 155 mm square mesh panels in the body of a trawl (4 sheets) and 200 mm diamond-mesh nettings in the wings, square and back sections of a trawl (1 sheet)]; 4 factsheets provided by BIM (Ireland) [square mesh codend of 45mm, 65 mm and T90, and quad-rig trawl]; and 3 sheets provided by France (IFREMER/Pêcheurs de Bretagne and COBRENORD) [100 mm T90 mesh panel in the extension and in the codend (2 sheets) and a 120 mm square mesh panel].

The factsheets can be downloaded as a pdf from the link above.

Challenge experiments

A number of “challenges experiments” conducted under WP4 have actually dealt with gear technology rather than fishing strategies, and are thus reported here. These results are described in Deliverable D4.2 (Reid, 2017, <http://www.discardless.eu/deliverables/entry/challenge-experiments-in-a-compiled-cluster-report-and-final-avoidance-manu>)

In the Celtic Sea, one of the Irish vessels (the nephrops targeting vessel) decided to use gear changes, and opted for a quad rig nephrops net in the second month of the trial, adopting the use of large mesh square mesh panels in all four extensions. The use of the SMP in the quad rig proved quite successful, and allowed the vessel to keep fishing significantly longer before choking on the cod that were the main choke during the control phase of the study (Figure 6.1).

Figure 6.1: Cumulative catches of key quota species caught by a vessel targeting Nephrops during two months of a challenge trial (July and August, with an SMP adopted in August) based on consecutive hauls in separate quota management areas (species quotas are marked with horizontal dashed lines)

Impact of these for discards reduction in the Celtic Sea

These factsheets were among others used by the STECF in 2018, in a study aiming at identify selectivity options to reduce the risks of choke species in the Western Waters demersal fisheries (STECF 18-02, <https://stecf.jrc.ec.europa.eu/documents/43805/2023188/STECF+18-02+-+TM+improving+selectivity.pdf>). The study concluded for some of the high risk (and several moderate risk) stocks improvements in selectivity are possible.

Looking at the Celtic Sea in more details, STECF 18-02 highlighted that five fisheries were identified where improvements in selectivity were needed. These fisheries are:

- Mixed gadoid TR1
- Nephrops TR2
- Directed whiting and hake trawl and seine TR2
- Mixed demersal (megrim, hake, angler) TR2
- Mixed demersal beam trawl (angler, megrim, sole, plaice) BT2

STECF 18-02 has reviewed different selectivity devices and gear modifications that have been tested and shown to reduce the level of unwanted catches in the fisheries identified. The results are as follows:

Mixed gadoid (TR1) - Based on the results of recent trials the simplest solution in this fishery would be to increase the codend mesh size and maintain the existing 120mm smp. This would bring this fishery in line with the current regulated gears used in the West of Scotland and would make this gear highly selective for haddock. The alternatives would be look at T90 mesh in the codend and extension which

has also been shown to improve selectivity for gadoids. Any increases in selectivity will undoubtedly reduce the marketable catch of whiting, hake and flatfish species.

Nephrops (TR2) – There is a management choice to be made to improve the size selectivity that will maintain the retention of fish bycatch in the fishery and/or to change the profile of these fisheries so that the fish bycatch is excluded, converting them to a single species fisheries. This will depend on quota allocation and uptake at an individual fleet or vessel level. If quota uptake necessitates the exclusion of all large (~ < 40 cm) haddock, whiting and cod from catches then a trawl gear incorporating some type of sorting grid or dual codend trawls should be considered. If it is acceptable to land certain amounts of these fish then square mesh panels (of appropriate mesh size and appropriately positioned) should be considered and if it is the intention to protect the juvenile of these species then measures which modify the codend size selection such as mesh size increase should be considered.

Directed whiting (TR2) – Levels of unwanted catches of haddock and hake are reportedly high in this fishery so consideration should be given to increasing mesh size (i.e. 100mm) and also using square mesh panels of at least 100mm. T90 mesh codends could also be considered as an option although based on the trials carried out the mesh size would need to be in excess of 80mm to improve selectivity for haddock which is the principal choke species in this fishery.

Mixed demersal (TR2) - In mixed demersal fisheries, the mandatory introduction of square-mesh panels should be considered. Increasing codend mesh size (100 mm) in the TR2 mixed demersal fisheries would also help reduce unwanted catches of haddock and hake.

Beam Trawl (TR2) – Reducing unwanted catches of the choke stocks in these fisheries is technically challenging without severely impacting on the retention of marketable sole and megrim. Therefore the options to improve selectivity are limited. In order to achieve meaningful reductions in, the mesh size would need to increase substantially (i.e. 100mm - 110 mm) but based on the results of trials in beam trawl fisheries this would result in losses of sole in excess of 50% rendering the fisheries uneconomic. The existing measures introduced under the NWW discard plan of using 120mm in the extension should be maintained as this will help to reduce unwanted to catches to some degree. Using large mesh panels at the front of the trawl and also incorporating T90 mesh into the codend and extension may help to reduce unwanted catches of gadoids.

6.4 Adaptation of fishing strategies

The largest part of the work performed in the Celtic Sea occurred in WP4, investigating issues in relation to where and when to fish. All results are detailed in Deliverables D4.2 on “Challenges experiments” (Reid, 2017) and D4.3 on “scientists story” (Reid and Fauconnet, 2018).

6.4.1 The Scientists’ story – identification of locations, times and practices to fish to avoid unwanted catch

A great number of different studies for the Celtic Sea were reported as independent chapters in D4.3.

Chapters 1 & 2 report on an analysis approach developed by IFREMER and that has been applied to combined French and Irish discard observer data from **IFREMER & MI**. In **Chapter 1**, the analysis was designed to highlight where different species were being discarded either together or in isolation. The

initial approach is statistical, and looks for clusters that can be discriminated from each other. In Chapter 1, we looked at the results for the combined data from Ireland and France, and then at what the differences were between emergent clusters for the two countries. We also compared the spatial patterns of discard clusters to landings clusters.

Figure 6.2. Clusters maps of international discards (left) and landings (right). The same colour code was assigned to each 3*3' square belonging to the same cluster. Species selection: TAC species.

Table 6.1. The relative abundance for each species in clusters. TAC species and international data set

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
Aphanopus.carbo	0,001	0,000	0,000	0,003	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,018	0,000	0,000	0,978	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
Brosme.brosme	0,001	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,998	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,002	0,000
Caproidae	0,044	0,001	0,002	0,014	0,009	0,808	0,003	0,014	0,026	0,031	0,007	0,000	0,007	0,005	0,027	0,001
Clupea.harengus	0,007	0,003	0,003	0,001	0,099	0,001	0,004	0,001	0,028	0,023	0,000	0,009	0,030	0,000	0,023	0,767
Coryphaenoides.rupestris	0,009	0,000	0,005	0,011	0,000	0,002	0,000	0,011	0,008	0,000	0,951	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,001	0,000
Gadus.morhua	0,028	0,002	0,188	0,016	0,049	0,007	0,012	0,012	0,064	0,106	0,000	0,032	0,007	0,027	0,379	0,071
Lepidorhombus.spp	0,061	0,002	0,035	0,071	0,036	0,056	0,037	0,095	0,390	0,081	0,047	0,025	0,022	0,001	0,028	0,014
Lophiidae	0,036	0,006	0,081	0,438	0,036	0,026	0,019	0,013	0,071	0,035	0,147	0,049	0,007	0,003	0,022	0,012
Melanogrammus.aeglefinus	0,038	0,001	0,048	0,031	0,166	0,042	0,035	0,005	0,040	0,065	0,000	0,037	0,033	0,008	0,299	0,151
Merlangius.merlangus	0,014	0,002	0,021	0,007	0,115	0,011	0,014	0,008	0,017	0,030	0,000	0,062	0,056	0,003	0,085	0,555
Merluccius.merluccius	0,037	0,001	0,187	0,061	0,027	0,006	0,015	0,127	0,095	0,057	0,039	0,017	0,011	0,223	0,074	0,024
Micromesistius.poutassou	0,022	0,002	0,030	0,009	0,008	0,005	0,005	0,712	0,071	0,050	0,017	0,008	0,011	0,000	0,020	0,029
Molva.dypterygia	0,009	0,001	0,002	0,002	0,000	0,004	0,000	0,840	0,005	0,000	0,138	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
Molva.molva	0,011	0,001	0,565	0,050	0,024	0,013	0,049	0,024	0,062	0,006	0,006	0,012	0,005	0,118	0,037	0,017
Nephrops.norvegicus	0,008	0,000	0,004	0,002	0,002	0,000	0,000	0,001	0,037	0,896	0,000	0,029	0,000	0,000	0,011	0,009
OTH	0,103	0,141	0,055	0,052	0,068	0,043	0,048	0,090	0,049	0,042	0,085	0,067	0,051	0,035	0,031	0,039
Pleuronectes.platessa	0,009	0,001	0,012	0,015	0,158	0,004	0,030	0,001	0,030	0,010	0,000	0,619	0,012	0,003	0,039	0,059
Pollachius.pollachius	0,010	0,001	0,105	0,006	0,001	0,000	0,001	0,001	0,002	0,000	0,000	0,009	0,000	0,860	0,003	0,000
Pollachius.virens	0,001	0,000	0,010	0,004	0,001	0,008	0,001	0,002	0,006	0,001	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,964	0,002	0,000
Rajiformes	0,045	0,005	0,085	0,023	0,040	0,049	0,494	0,006	0,065	0,013	0,008	0,116	0,020	0,003	0,012	0,016
Scomber.scombrus	0,024	0,003	0,021	0,006	0,009	0,020	0,006	0,003	0,013	0,004	0,012	0,004	0,802	0,048	0,006	0,020
Solea.spp	0,013	0,001	0,001	0,002	0,021	0,000	0,005	0,000	0,000	0,008	0,000	0,928	0,012	0,000	0,001	0,007
Sprattus.sprattus	0,004	0,000	0,001	0,000	0,005	0,000	0,000	0,001	0,007	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,949	0,000	0,002	0,031
Squalus.acanthias	0,013	0,000	0,008	0,008	0,007	0,007	0,008	0,003	0,055	0,835	0,000	0,000	0,012	0,014	0,021	0,010

This asks the question can we predict discards on the basis of the spatial structure of the landings. While some discard clusters corresponded well to landings clusters this was more unusual than cases where no obvious common pattern was found. So high landings of a species may not predicate high discards of that species.

We also looked more closely at the Irish cluster patterns alone in **Chapter 2** to find out if this would provide useful information for Irish fishermen, working under specific quota arrangements and often with unique métiers. In this case we also looked at clustering of discards for fish that were either above or below MCRS. The second step was to look for discard clusters that were also clustered spatially.

Figure 6.3. Discard cluster map of <MCRS (left) and >MCRS (right) fish based on Irish observer at sea data between 2010 and 2014.

Table 6.2. Under Size discard clusters based on Irish data by cluster

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Gadus.morhua	0,015	0,071	0,563	0,005	0,149	0,028	0,023	0,075	0,042	0,010	0,018
Lepidorhombus.whiffiagonis	0,726	0,007	0,039	0,007	0,199	0,002	0,006	0,001	0,004	0,005	0,003
Melanogrammus.aeglefinus	0,005	0,182	0,050	0,006	0,071	0,261	0,044	0,145	0,103	0,026	0,106
Merlangius.merlangus	0,009	0,097	0,045	0,024	0,014	0,016	0,010	0,018	0,559	0,043	0,165
Merluccius.merluccius	0,084	0,041	0,020	0,519	0,173	0,006	0,043	0,015	0,041	0,034	0,025
Molva.molva	0,000	0,012	0,009	0,004	0,000	0,004	0,613	0,253	0,005	0,003	0,097
Pleuronectes.platessa	0,003	0,073	0,029	0,015	0,027	0,012	0,015	0,049	0,021	0,577	0,179
Solea.solea	0,000	0,001	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,012	0,006	0,981

Table 6.3. >MCRS discard clusters based on Irish data

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Gadus.morhua	0,020	0,021	0,500	0,079	0,040	0,036	0,038	0,015	0,024	0,006	0,221
Lepidorhombus.whiffiagonis	0,441	0,197	0,034	0,031	0,094	0,040	0,041	0,017	0,008	0,036	0,060
Melanogrammus.aeglefinus	0,021	0,162	0,034	0,012	0,093	0,251	0,111	0,148	0,040	0,020	0,109
Merlangius.merlangus	0,007	0,019	0,031	0,012	0,083	0,033	0,098	0,227	0,381	0,030	0,080
Merluccius.merluccius	0,041	0,042	0,082	0,425	0,171	0,026	0,056	0,013	0,022	0,055	0,067
Molva.molva	0,055	0,008	0,754	0,002	0,005	0,019	0,008	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,149
Pleuronectes.platessa	0,031	0,022	0,010	0,008	0,023	0,019	0,219	0,017	0,009	0,614	0,028
Solea.solea	0,004	0,005	0,023	0,000	0,001	0,000	0,011	0,007	0,083	0,082	0,784

Many of the clusters could be seen scattered across the Celtic Sea, but some such as >MCRS megrim discards were aggregated in the south, while > MCRS hake discards were concentrated in the Nephrops fishery areas. Hake discards < MCRS were in similar locations to the adults, but <MCRS megrim discards were concentrated in one small part of the adult discard area.

Chapter 7 by MI in the Celtic Sea case study (also published as Calderwood and Reid, 2018), explores a different aspect of discarding behaviour that could help understand and reduce drivers for discarding. In most countries quotas are assigned on an annual basis, and it has long been speculated that discarding would tend to increase towards the end of the year as quota runs out. In Ireland, quota is assigned on a monthly basis. This allowed us to examine what happens with discarding as quota is exhausted 12 times a year, as opposed to once, as in most jurisdictions. The study focused on the mixed demersal fishery, and on the key species of cod, haddock and whiting. Cod and haddock represent strong choke problems. The “Challenge” trials reported in D4.2 showed that the boats studied were choking on cod and haddock with 4 days in the month. The findings showed that there was little evidence of an increase in cod or haddock discarding as the month progressed, presumably as they had no available quota over most of each month. However, whiting, which had a much less restrictive TAC, did show an increase towards the end of the month.

Figure 6.4: Relationship between the proportion of discards of >MLS whiting in relation to total whiting caught per haul on varying days of the month. The shaded area represents the confidence interval based on standard error.

What this suggests is that increased flexibility in when a TAC can be used, might help reduce the overall discarding bulk in some fisheries, and particularly whiting in the Celtic Sea. For those more quota restricted species changes in gear selectivity and fishing strategies are also likely to be required to overcome quota restrictions, as current quotas have little influence on fishing behaviour.

In **Chapter 8 (MI, IFREMER & CEFAS in the Celtic Sea case study)**, we present the results from a detailed analysis of observer data from Ireland, France and the UK used as an ensemble of the catches taken in the Celtic Sea. The analysis focuses on mapping hot spots of CPUE, and catch proportion for three key species; cod, haddock and whiting, and over and under MCRS. The analysis can be extended to any species, both commercial and non-commercial. The maps are based on consistent observations of particular catch rates, so only those locations where one would consistently (over 5 years) see high or low levels for these categories. The data are then interpolated to provide regional coverage.

Figure 6.5. Interpolated maps identifying areas with consistent levels of the proportion of above MCRS A. Haddock and B. Whiting in the catch over multiple years (2010-2015)

The maps are then drawn together into a web based app, where the fishermen can choose the species (or size class) of interest, and then map CPUE or catch proportion at the selected level of intensity. They can also map a number of species or sizes together on one map, and change the levels to show, to help choose likely places to avoid or find particular species or sizes.

Figure 6.6. A screenshot of the shiny app developed to allow stakeholders to select the size, species and quantity of fish they would like to target and/or avoid during different seasons. The resultant map displays layers representing where to target or avoid fishing operations to optimise catch composition.

The app represents a DST for fishermen. We plan to incorporate additional species, as well as discarding hotspots. The app is a prototype under further development, currently available at https://sirs.agrocampus-ouest.fr/discardless_wp4/index.php?action=fiche&code=1&type_code=IN&atl_version=0&idlang=UK and soon directly available from the DiscardLess website.

The main thrust for **Chapter 9** by **IFREMER in the Celtic Sea case study** (Also published as Pointin et al., 2018), is to find an appropriate way to map discard observer data to help fishermen choose where and when to fish, to reduce the capture of unwanted fish. Such spatio-temporal reallocations of fishing effort are part of adaptation strategies that could help mitigate the impact of the landing obligation. If the primary objective is to reduce discards while maintaining commercial catches, maps of landings and discards can provide fishers with insights on appropriate fishing grounds and/or periods. When using on-board observer programme data to explore spatial and/or temporal patterns of landings and discards, one common problem is the non-random spatial distribution of the data. To overcome this issue, a non-parametric mapping method based on nested grids was developed using the French on-board observer data. The method relies on an iterative process of cell division where the size of the cells varies according to the number of observations. Landings and discards are then estimated in each grid cell. Two contrasting fishing métiers, trawlers and netters, are examined to illustrate the advantages and issues of the nested grid method, and discuss how it can be applied to any fishing métier.

Figure 6.7: Top: Map of the (left) LPUE and (right) DPUE of haddock ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) between 2010 and 2015 for the trawling métier. Mean LPUE = $23 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$; Mean DPUE = $6.2 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$. No. FOs = 7,619. No. fishing trips (FT) = 212. Size of the observed vessels = 18 - 42 m. Bottom: Map of the (left) LPUE and (right) DPUE of the 5 most important target and non-target species subject to quotas ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{km}^{-1}$) between 2010 and 2015 for the netting métier. Mean LPUE = $18.5 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{km}^{-1}$; Mean DPUE = $1.7 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{km}^{-1}$. No. FOs = 2,008. No. fishing trips = 587. Size of the observed vessels = 5 - 15 m.

Spatial reallocation strategies could be found for the trawling métier, but not for the netting one. Accurate effort data are required to verify that the on-board observed data spatial coverage is sufficient

to produce meaningful maps. A potential application of this study is to create an atlas of landings and discards for each métier observed by on-board observer programmes.

6.5 The managers story

The following is edited from Deliverable 4.4. The Managers story – incentives for discard mitigation and Landing Obligation compliance, and for those components relevant to the Celtic Sea from Ireland and France.

Summary of management measures references in the Irish response to the Commissions 2016 request for information on LO implementation.

- A range of gear based technical measures to improve selectivity and uptake. Funding has been provided for 9 projects to invest in more selective gears with a relevance to the LO
- LO related changes to quota management regime. “A number of changes have been made to the Irish quota management system with significant amendments to the Monkfish notifications & fishery management notifications as well as the monthly whitefish data. In addition to this a significant IT project has been initiated to look at a new quota management system capable of dealing with quota management once the landing obligation is fully phased in. An additional catch-limit is made available each month for obligated vessels for obligated species over and above the catch limits in place to mitigate the potential choke effect”.
- Analysis process of choke problems is described which was conducted in collaboration with the NWWAC. The report mentions possible measures to mitigate chokes including improved selectivity, *de minimis* and high survivability exemptions, inter species quota flexibility.
- 3 *de minimis* exemptions relevant to Ireland were established (for whiting caught with bottom trawls and seines ≥ 100 mm in ICES divisions VIIb-VIIj, for whiting caught with bottom trawls and seines < 100 mm in ICES subarea VII (excluding VIIa, VIId and VIIe) and for Nephrops in ICES subarea VII.
- 1 high survival exemption relevant to Ireland was established (Norway lobster caught by pots, traps or creels in ICES division VI and subarea VII)
- Inter annual or inter specific flexibility provisions were not used.
- LO related communication initiatives with industry from both the fisheries department and control authorities were described.
- 2 projects to improve port infrastructure to handle unwanted catches were assessed in 2016 with an estimated funding of €500k.
- Some difficulties with LO implementation were noted including demersal bycatch in pelagic fisheries, lack of funding to adapt fishing gears, vessels or port infrastructure, difficulties implementing and monitoring *de minimis* or high survivability exemptions, increased incidence of refusal to carry observers.

Summary of meeting with Irish Fisheries Department (DAFM) staff responsible for administration of LO, November 2017.

A change to the pelagic quota management regime, labelled the Pilot Quota Balancing scheme, was discussed. This scheme creates a mechanism whereby catches of species for which a vessel did not have an allocation or catches over the vessels allocated quota could be repaid in a subsequent fishing period. The scheme in part was intended to deal with opportunistic behaviour whereby some fishers were landing accidental catches of pelagic fish as obligated under the LO. The possibility of the scheme being used in order to provide some flexibility to deal with chokes in the context of a non-tradeable quota regime was uncertain and DAFM staff emphasised that it was a learning process. It is intended that the scheme although initially only applying to the pelagic fishery would be expanded to include demersal fisheries also.

The general thrust of the Quota Balancing system is that fishers will pay for overshooting their quota with the repayment (in the next fishing period whatever that might be) being ramped up depending on the degree of overfishing. Currently the repayment/overfishing set up is:

Up to 10% of allocation - Overfishing repayment 1.0

Over 10% up to 20% of allocation - Overfishing repayment 1.2

Over 20% up to 40% of allocation - Overfishing repayment 1.4

Over 40% up to 50% of allocation - Overfishing repayment 1.8

Any further overfishing greater than 50% of allocation - Overfishing repayment 2.0.

Although the quota balancing scheme was intended to be in place for the start of 2018 some uncertainty existed regarding how the overfishing events that the scheme is designed to address would be dealt with by the fisheries control agency.

It was also emphasised that the scheme was only a partial solution to LO issues and that further (unspecified) measures were expected to likely follow in 2018.

In relation to other management measures DAFM staff were of the opinion that international swaps had not been affected by the LO, or at least not yet. In fact all of the traditional swaps utilized by Ireland had continued in the past few years and a few new ones (e.g. Boarfish) had taken place also.

Haddock in the Celtic Sea was mentioned as a case study where significant choke problems would occur. DAFM opinion was that a combination of available measures would help to mitigate but would most likely not entirely solve the problem. Measures mentioned which would collectively contribute were:

- International swaps (but limited by the fact that quota for this stock is limited for all countries)
- Quota top-up
- Inter species flexibility
- End of year quota banking and borrowing mechanism

- Use of TAC ranges
- Technical measures – in particular larger mesh sizes, which are already being examined for a number of species.
- Bycatch limits in place of target species quotas – an example was given of Rockall Haddock for vessels targeting Megrim. (details of scheme in Annex 1) Bluefin tuna was also given as an example of a bycatch quota.
- The use of more focused subgroups within the general monthly quota regime – e.g. the existing Monkfish scheme whereby vessels who wished to receive additional allocation of Monkfish quota had to forfeit quota for certain other species and also commit to an annual tie-up period.

A pilot scheme introduced in 2017 to promote the use of selective gears in the Nephrops fishery was also discussed (see Annex 1 for details). Unfortunately the scheme was only introduced very late in the year so only 1 vessel applied but it is intended that the scheme will be reintroduced in 2018. A similar approach may also be applied with vessels targeting Whiting in 2018.

A difficulty mentioned with all of these management adaptations is that there is a lot of work involved in setting them up and managing them and personnel numbers are limited.

The possibility of withdrawing a stock from the TAC process was discussed and DAFM staff felt that before that could happen it would have to be demonstrated that everything else possible has been tried. In the case of Irish Sea Whiting, which was an example of a stock where derogation from TAC was proposed, a lot of selectivity trials have been done already including with a SELTRA trawl.

Area closures would only be possible on an industry voluntary basis. This may work but it would not be possible for DAFM to administer a real time system.

DAFM staff mentioned that bycatch allowances and LO measures in general were difficult to enforce but that such bycatch schemes promote avoidance at least.

They also felt that eventually market pressures will push the responsibility for compliance on to fishers. They mentioned changes in the buying practices of large French and Spanish supermarket chains and major seafood companies in terms of responsibility.

There was no appetite for ITQs as DAFM staff felt that ITQs in other countries had high social costs in terms of reduced numbers of smaller vessels and an adverse impact on smaller ports.

Onboard cameras were not greatly supported, as there was a feeling that it takes more than the allocation of some extra quota to change underlying fishing practices. Camera usage could be appropriate on large pelagic vessels but not on smaller vessels.

Alterations to relative stability keys in the case of quota uplift were not seen as a realistic possibility.

French case studies

The following reporting covers both the English Channel and the Celtic Sea.

The French administration and fisheries industry created in 2014 a specific working group “MOOD” to discuss LO related implementation issues and impacts in France. This working Group was composed of members of the National fisheries administration (DPMA), scientists, PO's and Regional Fisheries Committees. During MOOD meetings members jointly discussed the positioning of France during intergovernmental meetings for the preparation of discard plans in regional Seas where French fleets are operating. The results of each intergovernmental meeting were also presented and discussed within the WG. From physical meeting organized in Paris the WG currently holds virtual meetings every month.

It is within this group that LO exemptions requested by France were discussed with the agreement of all participants. Additionally this WG sees one of its responsibilities as the increased awareness of the LO and its impact on the French fleet, harbours and territories. Fisheries industry representatives and in particular PO's understand that adaptation to the LO requires an improvement of fishing gear selectivity. Since the first meetings of the WG until today many fishing gear selectivity projects were undertaken by PO's or other industry organisations and scientists with the objective to improve selectivity and limit discards in almost all regional seas (North Sea and East English Channel, West English Channel, Celtic Sea, Bay of Biscay, Mediterranean). The majority of these projects were financed by France Filière Pêche, a joint organization representing all sectors of the French Fishing Industry from production to marketing.

Once the exemptions requested by France were granted other projects have been financed. This time the objective was to obtain data about the survival of some species (eg. nephrops or sole) and increase the rate of survival. For example to increase the survival rate of nephrops a new sorting table was introduced. So, crew members could put the undersize nephrops directly into water to wait until the end of sorting out process. This new sorting table was easily accepted by the crew members because it improved their working conditions as they are standing up to sort fish instead of sitting down.

In total the number of these projects is around 12 with the first starting in 2011 and ending in 2016. These projects have shown the impacts of the use of more selective gears on discard reduction and also the losses of commercial species. Some of the trials were positive regarding discard reduction and also have been supported by fishers. An example is the case of the use of bigger mesh for trawlers operating in the Western Channel, which has decreased considerably their catches of choke species, in particular boarfish, for which France does not have quota while at the same time not losing too many commercially valuable fish.

Despite this positive work undertaken by the French industry the French Fisheries Administration didn't mention it in the note addressed to DG MARE in February 2017. This note gave an overview of the general situation without detailing the effort undertaken by the industry on selectivity but this may be a result of the specific questions asked by DG MARE. The note mentions the difficulties encountered by vessel owners in recording discards in the logbook and distinguishing which category they belong in (predator damage, resulting from contamination, or if they are undersize, etc). The note also mentions efforts taken by the administration in terms of communication about the LO and its implementation towards fisher's representatives or directly to vessels owners through the production of informative

notes found on the website of DPMA and the exemptions granted in national law through the publication of bylaws.

In addition to this general vision DiscardLess partners have conducted meetings and interviews with PO's, Fisheries Committees, large fishing companies and Administration managers.

For the French administration, the French fleet does not face a particular problem relating to LO implementation because quotas for the main commercial species are high enough. In the case of a choke species problem, e.g. with boarfish in the Western Channel, for which France doesn't have any quotas, it is possible to exchange with one of the countries having quotas.

Regarding the issue of reporting discards in the logbook for the moment not many vessels have done it. The incentive of a quota uplift was not enough to encourage fishers to register discards. It seems that one PO registered discards and asked to uplift quotas in West English Channel. According to another PO, the other reason that boat owners and skippers don't report discards is because first they don't understand why they should do it and second technical difficulties don't make it easy for them. They should declare the weight on a species-specific basis and not the total amount of discards. All managers agree that recording of discards is necessary to justify the *de minimis* exemptions granted. Otherwise nobody could understand why we claim such exemptions if our recorded discards don't show it. For all of them if discards are not recorded yet is because the rule is not yet controlled as the emphasis during this transition period is on communication about the LO rather than implementation.

Some PO's consider that it is important to quantify precisely all the catches and to record total catches including discards, but fishers "*are afraid about the impact of such records*".

Quota uplifts are seen as a solution to discard problems by some but there remains an issue regarding understanding that the uplift quota is not the commercial quota.

Choke species are perceived as the main problem especially for species with restrictive quotas. These species should be classified in the same category as protected species (e.g. Undulate ray), which are forbidden to be landed.

Swaps are seen as a partial solution to restrictive quota or zero quota species but "*finding an interesting exchange*" is the key particularly for species with little community quota.

Regarding *de minimis* exemptions some seek flexibility by combining species. If exempted species were combined e.g. monkfish, skipjack and rays, then the calculation of percentages is bigger than only one as it is now. In Brittany there is room for manoeuvre on species such as monkfish but this is not necessarily the case for other French regions. For such regions, the establishment of a combined or global *de minimis* is a possible solution.

All parties consider that the implementation of article 15 is difficult which leads them to delay the process of implementation.

6.6 Valorisation of unwanted catches, especially below MCRS fish

This chapter is based on a report prepared for BIM under the EMFF exploring the potential for commercial use of <MCRS fish in Ireland. Potential volumes of unwanted catches could be significant. The table below shows a total estimate of unwanted catches (i.e. catches below the Minimum Conservation Reference Size: MCRS) of 6 key species of 4571 tonnes which could be landed by the Irish fleet. This table is restricted to key species for which significant quantities of unwanted catch may be landed.

* It must be stressed that due to the numerous uncertainties which could affect implementation of the LO as well as uncertainties within the estimation process, the figures reported here should be treated only as indicators of potential volumes of below MCRS fish which may be landed.

Table 6.4. Discards estimates for the Irish vessels

Irish vessels, All fishing gears, ICES Areas VI & VII (excl VIId)			
Annual average 2014-16			
Species	Discards (tonnes)	% discards <MCRS	Discards <MCRS (tonnes)
Whiting	3,686	39	1,438
Haddock	2,898	49	1,420
Nephrops	1,573	48	752
Hake	1,016	46	467
Plaice	612	44	269
Cod	336	67	225
Total	10,121	45	4,571

There are no “magic bullet” solutions that can produce high economic returns to fishermen for size classes of fish that previously had no economic value. Returns will be in most cases a fraction of the value that smaller grades of above minimum size fish can achieve.

One of the implications of this finding of low economic value is that concerns are unfounded that the LO will result in the targeting of undersize and juvenile fish by requiring fishermen to land small fish. At least in the case of Ireland there is no possibility of this occurring under current conditions. The second implication is that there is a huge incentive to fish more selectively and, as far as possible to utilise the quota available in the most economically rational manner. The landing of below MCRS fish will lead to the loss of a large part of the future economic value in those fish. The values we have calculated for currently available options show that 1 tonne of above MCRS fish is worth at least 6 times the value of 1 tonne of below MCRS fish.

Selectivity improvements alone cannot resolve all LO issues however and some residual unwanted catches will always be an issue in most demersal fisheries. In such cases the best current utilisation option appears to be the pot fishery bait market. When averaging between fresh and frozen supplies to this market a value of €100 to €120 per tonne could be returned to the fisherman for below MCRS fish landed. While significant investment in advanced equipment is not required for this option the main

infrastructural constraint here is access to refrigerated and frozen storage. This issue has been successfully addressed by a number of co-ops and sales agents who have received EMFF funding from BIM to improve storage infrastructure. Even in upgraded facilities at certain times when large volumes of commercial landings are present there would still be competition for space in refrigerated storage.

The next best currently available utilisation options are fishmeal, which can essentially take an unlimited supply, and pet food that can take more limited quantities. Both options would deliver a price per tonne to fishermen of approximately €50 per tonne. This highlights the fact that the price differential in demersal fish between small size grades of fish sold on the fresh market and fishmeal is far higher than it is for pelagic fish which is why the fishmeal option is only used occasionally for demersal fish. The prices achievable in the fishmeal option are essentially fixed as fishmeal is a global commodity and significant improvements on that price are highly unlikely.

In the pet food option there may be opportunities to improve prices to a level above that outlined in our initial analysis. Conversations with pet food company operators and Enterprise Ireland experts in the area have highlighted that there is a growing market for high quality niche pet food products from whole fish or fish-based ingredients. In common with any other potentially promising options the requirement would be for a reasonably stable and significant supply of good quality fish with as little mixing of species as possible. The high value pet food market is an option that is worth exploring further.

A potential option, which is being discussed throughout Europe as a potential utilisation solution, is the use of small silage units to stabilise unwanted catches either at sea or ashore before distributing the product to fishmeal plants or other buyers. The difficulty with this option is that it does not add significant value to the product without further concentration and concentration requires more significant investment in equipment. The main advantage of the basic silage process is that it prevents further degradation of the product and allows for the accumulation of silage until a full transport load is ready and thereby reduces transport costs. A network of regional silage units, partly funded by EMFF or other funding, with a partnership arrangement for transport with a fishmeal plant or other buyer and fed by a significant supply of raw material would have some potential to reduce costs and deliver a reasonable return to fishermen.

In the medium term there are a number of options that would require more significant investment but could potentially deliver higher value products. A common problem across almost all of these options is that there is a conflict between the investments required, their high supply volume nature, and the policy goal of the LO, which is to reduce the supply of undersized fish. The fact that to date only very small volumes of below MCRS catches have been landed throughout Europe adds to the unattractive nature of these options for investors, at least currently. One exception to this is the possibility that a supply of gadoid fish could potentially be block frozen and processed through the new fish protein plant in the North West of the country. The technical details and economic viability of this would have to be worked out but it is an option worth exploring as potentially there could be a high value market available for the products of this process.

In the long term what should be aimed at, in line with the desired goal of the LO to reduce unwanted catches, is high value uses of smaller volumes of below MCRS fish which cannot be avoided. This calls into question any business plans and large infrastructural investments based solely on discards. Viable

options would have to be established in conjunction with existing processing operations and existing supply lines of processing waste or low value commercial grades of fish.

6.7 Summary – conclusions

The mixed nature of the species targeted by demersal fisheries in the Celtic Sea results in numerous challenges with the introduction of the Landing Obligation. It is likely that a combination of improved gear selectivity and the adoption of alternative fishing strategies will be required to avoid some of the unwanted catches, and to maximise on fishing opportunities under the LO. There is certainly no one-size fits all solution, and it is likely that gear and behaviour adaptations will mitigate some, but not all problems with choke species and <MCRS fish. The resources provided in the selectivity manual and mapping apps for the Celtic Sea should, however, provide information of great use and interest to industry to help better avoid unwanted catches. Further collaborations with industry will be required to ensure that future developments of mapping applications meet the needs of interested stakeholders in appropriate formats, and getting feedback on the apps that have currently been developed is the first step in this process. Whilst analysing fish distributions from the past to provide advice on where may be best to fish in the future, to avoid unwanted catches, is very useful the next steps are to look at integrating such maps with near real time information. By sharing information on occurrences of undersize fish or spawning aggregations for example, coupled with the information provided in the maps developed in this project, fishers should be much better equipped to avoid choke species and juvenile fish.

A major problem in the Celtic Sea remains that due to quota allocation rules as well as stock status, all Member States encounter choke issues, with the concomitant <MCRS catch issues as well. Table 1 illustrates these issues. All four major players (Ireland, France, Belgium and UK) caught above or close to their quota for haddock, France, Belgium and UK for plaice, France and Belgium for sole. In addition Ireland had choke issues with cod, whiting and hake in addition to haddock. The UK had issues with megrim. It is probably worth noting that TAC is undershot globally for cod, whiting and megrim, which may open a route to mitigating choke for Ireland for cod and possibly whiting, although the over quota catches are minor, and the UK for megrim.

Table 6.5. Mean percentage of TAC uptake by stock and countries between 2010 and 2014. Data comes from both ICES advice sheets for each stocks (<http://www.ices.dk/community/advisory-process/Pages/Latest-Advice.aspx>) and EU legislation on fishing opportunities (https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/cfp/fishing_rules/tacs).

Stock (ICES area)	Cod (7ek)		Haddock (7bk)		Whiting (7bk)		Plaice (7fg)		Plaice (7hjk)		Sole (7fg)		Sole (7hjk)		Hake (6-7)		Megrim (7)	
	mean	sd	mean	sd	mean	sd	mean	sd	mean	sd	mean	sd	mean	sd	mean	sd	mean	sd
Belgium	47.5	12.3	120.7	18.9	88.8	20.9	352.7	78.1	57.3	34.7	110.7	11.7	54.4	45.8	7.6	1.1	79.1	39.2
Spain															141.5	15.3	68.5	10.9
France	63.0	15.1	94.3	9.8	38.0	7.5	122.8	20.1	301.0	54.9	74.8	11.1	113.1	14.2	93.2	22.9	45.3	10.1
Ireland	114.5	12.7	102.1	10.8	106.6	13.9	33.8	6.3	97.0	38.5	95.6	17.7	40.9	7.6	109.4	7.0	90.0	16.1
Netherlands	0.0	0.0							0.0	0.0			0.0	0.0	94.6	65.1		
UK	87.7	12.2	99.6	21.2	43.9	8.8	80.6	25.4	183.1	62.2	65.4	15.2	71.1	8.6	83.5	11.1	104.9	14.6
Average discard rate	14.0	13.0	37.8	19.6	20.3	4.0	70.7	6.0			2.3	0.6			13.5	6.1	19.6	5.7
Total uptake based on landings only	72.5	13.3	97.6	8.7	58.6	7.1	104.5	12.6	100.8	16.9	95.8	9.7	53.7	5.8	105.9	13.7	69.1	10.8
Total uptake based on catches	87.0	28.1	169.6	50.9	73.9	11.6	368.4	82.0	100.8	16.9	97.2	11.0	53.7	5.8	113.3	23.1	85.8	10.0

There is some potential for management measures to help mitigate the impacts of the LO. Member states have naturally focused on the use of the measures included in the legislations such as de minimis, high survival or inter species flexibility. But there would also seem to be scope for other adaptations of management to help. For example, the Irish managers are looking at Quota Balancing, allowing catches above quota to be transferred to the next month, albeit with a penalty. Both France and Ireland continue to use international quota swaps, but these are limited in their potential when the same species e.g. haddock, represent a choke for both MS. Other possibilities e.g. derogation from TAC for difficult choke species have also been considered. There appears to be little appetite for more substantial management changes e.g. the introduction of ITQs or similar.

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7 Discards Mitigation Strategies in the Eastern Channel case study

7.1 Overview of the case study and initial work objectives

In the **Eastern English Channel case**, *DiscardLess* focuses on mobile and fixed gear fleets targeting demersal species in this area. The mixed nature of these fisheries leads to high discards ratios, especially in the mixed demersal trawl fishery. The constraints exerted on fishers due to the combination of resource management measures, diverse fish communities and competition for space make the reduction of unwanted catches particularly challenging. The identification of the status of the ecosystem and resulting modelling exercise have encompassed all fishing fleets operating in the Channel as is required to make system level impact assessments. The current status of ecosystem knowledge as well as the potential knowledge gaps have been identified and ecosystem and economic criteria and indicators will be defined in relation to available data (WP1-2). A selection of the existing parameterized simulation models (ATLANTIS, ISIS-Fish, OSMOSE, EwE) have been used to assess the outcomes of scenarios depending on their ability to reproduce targeted processes and changes. The combination of models ensures the coverage of expected impacts at every level of the English Channel ecosystem, including selected socio-economic impacts (WP2). Changes in fish stocks and sensitive components of the marine ecosystems have been monitored through analyses of routinely collected data and changes in the perception and perceived changed during and after the implementation of the landing obligation (WP1-2). Results of existing selective experiments in this area have been made available for the project (WP3) and the experience of fishers on avoidance of unwanted catches will be collected. (WP3-4). On this basis, the modelled fishing behaviour included in operating models have been adapted. Fisheries independent and dependent data have been used to create maps that show zones of high discard likelihood in space and time (i.e. seasonal patterns). This type of information has been cross validated and improved by the experience and knowledge of fishers and finally used as inputs to adapt modelling tools. Challenge experiments with fishers have allowed testing some DMS at sea, evaluating their socio-economic impact and defining their technological requirements. A range of management measures have been discussed with fishers and related incentives will be identified.

This deliverable reports thus on the outcomes of WP3 and WP4 for this case study.

7.2 The Fishers story – documenting discard reduction practices suggested by stakeholders

Fisheries stakeholders from France/Eastern Channel were interviewed, regarding their own ideas of why they discard and what they currently do and think about it. The results are described in Deliverable D4.1, finalised in April 2017 (Reid et al., 2017). The results of this task have also been brought online into a visual display on http://www.discardless.eu/fishermen_story.

The answers received from the Irish stakeholders were as follows:

7.2.1 Causes and levels of discarding:

France-Eastern Channel	Sector
Protected species are being discarded (e.g. Undulate Ray (<i>Raja undulata</i>) and “skate”.	Trawlers and netters

Regulations related to catch composition (e.g. cod or sole management plans). Fishers usually keep quota of species without commercial value to adjust landings.	Trawlers and netters
PO's decision didn't allow them to bring ashore small sizes of non-commercial species, even if they are of the legal size leading to high-grading.	All Trawlers (12m and up and pelagic)
Don't bring ashore species without good prices (plaice, horse mackerel, dab, etc.)	all trawlers and netters
Undersized and damaged fish are also discarded.	Bottom Trawlers
Not enough quota (e.g. mackerel, skate)	All trawlers
Discard herring because no quota, "national quota is OK but it was given to the Franco-Dutch boats"	Pelagic trawler
We are not allowed to land whiting when we use mesh of 80mm.	Pelagic trawl
We discard species that have a high survival (e.g. plaice, dab)	Bottom trawlers

7.2.2 Current methods used to avoid unwanted catch

Technical (Gear)

France-Eastern Channel	Sector
For French fishers trawl mesh is okay and "cannot make more effort".	
Individual fishers consider that they cannot improve their selectivity, but see next row.	
Tested square mesh panel (80, 100 and 115mm) of different length (1 or 2m) and also a selective grid were tested.	Artisanal trawlers via Selecfish project

Tactical (Strategies)

France-Eastern Channel	
Fishers moved to another fishing ground when <u>unwanted</u> species are present (unwanted means species without quotas or without commercial value).	All Trawlers
Keep our quota of whiting to be used when we are targeting cod (regulation about the composition of captures).	Trawlers
Use their knowledge about seasonality of the species, "when herring is here, horse mackerel is not here".	
Fisheries activity based on the seasonality of the species "we caught less small sole between March and May. It is just after the end of scallop season. "We know that the period before Christmas whiting has the best size".	

7.2.3 Interest expressed in additional methods to avoid unwanted catch

Technical (Gear)

France-Eastern Channel	Sector
Fishers organisations are conducting programs to improve selectivity.	Bottom trawlers
Agree to test more selective gears if compensate.	Netters (Boulogne)

Tactical (Strategies)

France-Eastern Channel	Sector
They know the areas producing more discards. They are able to explain the reasons of high discards in these areas (estuary, near the coast,)	Trawlers and netters

Management

France-Eastern Channel	Sector
Fisheries activity should follow the seasonality of the species.	Bottom trawlers
Biological rest (closure) was also mentioned by Dieppe fishers but only if they get a compensation	Bottom Trawlers

7.2.4 No support for the following proposed methods to avoid unwanted catch

Technical (Gear)

France-Eastern Channel	Sector
Fishers consider that they cannot do more efforts to improve trawl selectivity.	Bottom Trawlers

Tactical (Strategies)

France-Eastern Channel	Sector
Fishers said "we avoid already areas with small fish or unwanted species" and that they would inform friends or family members.	Trawlers
Already know areas having more juvenile species (estuary areas).	Trawlers
Fisheries activity is based on the seasonality of big species	Trawlers

7.3 Adaptation of gear technology

Many selectivity programm were run and are still running in the Eastern English Channel in the last years. A report was made available by the fishermen organization in 2014 (https://www.comitedespeches-hautsdefrance.fr/wp-content/uploads/2016/01/R%C3%A9sum%C3%A9_SELECTFISH_SUP_18m.pdf, https://www.comitedespeches-hautsdefrance.fr/wp-content/uploads/2016/01/R%C3%A9sum%C3%A9_SELECTFISH_INF_18m.pdf).

Few of the developed selective devices have then been used in the English Eastern Channel. The conclusion of previous experiments showed that the losses in commercial catches and reglementations linked to the former “cod management plan” and technical measures (mesh sizes restrictions and catch composition i.e. percentages of targeted species in the landings) were the main obstacles with the developpement of adaptive gear technology.

7.4 Adaptation of fishing strategies

A great number of different studies for the Eastern English Channel were reported as independent chapters in D4.3. The different studies have in common the objective of finely describing species and fishing activities distribution compiling and merging all available data (scientific surveys, onboard observation of the fishing activities and fishing activities collected from logbooks and Vessel Monitoring Systems).

In **chapter 3 by IFREMER for the English Channel case study**, the analysis makes use of landings and VMS data to help fishermen define the spatial distribution of the species or sizes of fish that they would wish to avoid, or indeed to concentrate upon while limiting the losses on other species. The work is focused on the development of a web based app that fishermen can use interactively to choose their precise area of operation. This may be to avoid catching <MCRS fish, or to avoid excessive catches of a “choke species”.

Using the tool to identify potential avoidance areas (quarterly scale)

Figure 7.1. Display of the Eastern Chanel app

This type of app has been developed as a Decision Support Tool (DST) in a number of other case studies as reported in Deliverable D4.3. Fishermen can then define a maximum or minimum proportion of a given species in the landings that he is willing to accept depending on the objective i.e. avoiding or targeting the species. The time scale over which the maps are presented can also be controlled, either for a year, quarter or month.

The app is a prototype under further development, currently available at https://sirs.agrocampus-ouest.fr/discardless_wp4/index.php?action=fiche&code=1&type_code=IN&atl_version=0&idlang=UK and soon directly available from the DiscardLess website

The objective of the study presented in **Chapter 10 (IFREMER in the English Channel case study)** (Also published as Bourdaud et al., 2017) was to analyse, at fine scale, the annual, seasonal and spatial distributions of several species in the Eastern English Channel (EEC). Data from scientific surveys are not available for all times of the year, but do provide consistent yearly and spatially resolved abundance indices. On-board commercial data do cover the whole year, but generally provide a biased perception of stock abundance. The combination of scientific and commercial catches per unit of effort (CPUEs), standardized using a delta-generalized linear model, allowed us to infer spatial and monthly dynamics of fish distributions in the EEC, which could be compared with previous knowledge on their life cycles.

Figure 7.2. Monthly spatial abundance distribution estimated from OBSMER and CGFS for cuttlefish. 'X' represents areas where no cuttlefish was ever fished during a month in the database.

The approach allowed a more representative mapping of the spatial temporal abundance distribution pattern of a number of species throughout the year. The information can then be used in both targeting, and avoidance in the context of the LO.

7.5 Summary – conclusions

The mixed nature of the species targeted by demersal fisheries in the Eastern English Channel results in numerous challenges with the introduction of the Landing Obligation. One of the main obstacle to the

gear selectivity improvement is this diversity of species (different in size, shape and management, i.e. with or without MCRS, with or without TAC) caught together by the demersal fleet. This diversity in the catches made the previous attempt to improve gear selectivity less conclusive than in other areas.

Some challenge experiments to test in real conditions the Landing Obligation shown the main problem of the trawlers in this area. The workload caused by an increased sorting time was seen as incompatible with the fishing activity. The storage capacity was also seen as a constraint and might reduce by 20% the trip duration and cause safety problem if the unwanted catches are not reduced and have to be stored to be landed.

The interviews, workshop and resources provided in mapping apps and the modeling exercises to assess the impact of the Landing Obligation for the Eastern English Channel shown the gain and interest of collaboration. Selectivity manual, mapping apps and model provided synthetic information where stakeholders provided ground truth information. Stakeholder feedback is essential to build apps that meet their needs as well as developing scenarios that are realistic given their limitation in changing their fishing activities (limitation from regulation and/or competition with other fleets or other activities).

Fine scale maps of fish/discards distributions might help fishermen to avoid choke species but in the Eastern English Channel all activities have to be taken into account when assessing the potential of effort reallocation to mitigate the effect of the Landing Obligation. In fact the Eastern English Channel is the busiest shipping route in the world and the development of marine renewable energy, gravel extraction and fishing activities, space is very limited to effort reallocation without creating conflicts.

7.6 Published references and presentations in conferences

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8 Discards Mitigation Strategies in the North Sea and West of Scotland

8.1 Overview of the case study and initial work objectives

The **North Sea and West of Scotland case study** will focus mainly on the Scottish and Danish demersal fisheries in Subareas IV-IIIa (North Sea, including Skagerrak and Kattegat) and VI (West of Scotland and Rockall). These areas support two large demersal fisheries: the demersal whitefish fishery (mostly larger offshore larger trawlers), and the *Nephrops* fishery (mostly smaller trawlers) in more discrete sandy or muddy grounds. The mixed whitefish fishery catches a variety of groundfish and demersal species. Some of these species are severely depleted and subject to very restrictive TACs, and there are currently substantial discards of commercial-sized fish of some species. More widely, there are problems of spatial stock heterogeneity and broad-scale quota regulations which lead to localised discarding of commercial valued “choke” species such as cod, hake and saithe. In the *Nephrops* fishery, the main problems are the capture and discarding of undersized small gadoids (particularly haddock and whiting in periods of higher recruitment), along with the discarding of small *Nephrops*.

All WPs were covered in specific activities for this case: identification of the current status of ecosystem and fishery knowledge and data, innovative approaches to addressing knowledge gaps through underwater video monitoring and statistical estimation of discards for poorly sampled species, and estimation through simulation of the outcomes of selected scenarios (WP1); development of discard mitigation strategy scenarios and parameterisation of operational economic models (WP2); meta-analyses on gear-based selectivity processes and information exchange of the technological solutions available which have the potential to optimise catch profiles under a landings obligation (WP3); identification and testing of policy mechanisms to encourage and incentivise the best strategies and tactics to minimise unwanted catches (WP4); demonstration and validation of efficient tools to support monitoring, control, surveillance and science observation (including *inter alia* REM (such as CCTV) and DNA technologies, building on previous advancements in this area) (WP5); and evaluation and demonstration of the practical use of the unavoidable unwanted catches for fish meal and fish oil, fish feed/pet food or for human consumption, including cost/benefit calculations of the different product types (WP6).

This deliverable reports thus on the outcomes of WP3 to WP6 for this case study.

8.2 Fishers story – documenting stakeholders view on the landing obligation

Interviews with fishers from Denmark regarding their opinion towards the landing obligation have been conducted using face-to-face interviews and telephone interviews in a semi-structured manner.

Fishers did not only fear the economic feasibility of their sector with the landing obligation, they were also to a large extent confused and felt harassed by the bureaucracy of the regulation, although some of the responders were less worried of the impact of the regulation. This was highlighted by the responses on fishers' preparations for the landing obligation. Half of the responders had not made any preparations for the landing obligation, but the reasoning behind ranged from responders not being worried, to responders who were so frustrated that they had given up on adapting to the regulation (Table 8.1).

Table 8.1 Expectations, concerns and preparations for the landing obligation

Questions	Answers	Fishers (n=22)	
		n	%
How do you think it will be to live with the landing obligation? (open ended question)	Do not know since regulations are confusing or non-existing	5	22.7
	Probably not a problem but unsure due to confusing regulations which might still be altered	2	9.1
	Already subject to the landing obligation. It is manageable but a pragmatic approach is necessary	2	9.1
	It will be difficult and need to adjust storage and handling capacity on board and ashore	6	27.3
	Will severely hamper the fishery and the landing obligation is a folly	4	18.2
	Very difficult in practice unless quotas are enlarged	2	9.1
	Need quota enlargement to follow and the situation is made worse by the bureaucratic introduction of the landing obligation	1	4.5
What do you believe will be the biggest issue for you with the landing obligation? (open ended question)	Do not know since regulations are confusing or non-existing	5	22.7
	Storage of bycatch on-board	9	40.9
	Choke species	5	2.7
	Lack of buyers for the bycatch	2	9.1
	Combination of storage, choke species and lack of quota will undermine the economic feasibility of the fisheries	2	9.1
	Extra time needed to sort the catch	1	4.5
	Bureaucracy to document compliance with the landing obligation	1	4.5
What preparations have you done or considered in order to handle the landing obligation? (open ended question)	None	11	50.0
	Participation in project related to gear selectivity	3	13.6
	Increasing storage capacity on-board	4	18.2
	Investigating possibilities for ensilage of bycatch	3	13.6
	Participation in project on sampling procedures	1	4.5
	Lack of quota	1	4.5

¹A responder could state more than one answer to the questions.

Roughly 2/3 of the interviewed fishers believed the landing obligation will have a negative effect on the Danish fisheries and more than 80% believed the landing obligation will have no positive effect on the marine environment. More than 2/3 of the fishers even believed the effect of the landing obligation will be negative for the marine environment. This negative effect on the marine environment is believed to occur due to the increased mortality for fish that would have survived discarding (but will be taken ashore with the landing obligation) and the decreased food availability for organisms that feed on discards, be it seabirds, other fish or benthic organisms.

Table 9.2.2. Expected effect of the landing obligation on the marine environment, Danish fishers

Questions	Answers	Fishers (n=22)	
		n	%
Do you believe that the landing obligation will have a <i>positive</i> effect on the marine environment?	Yes	1	4.5
	No	19	86.4
	Do not know	2	9.1
Do you believe that the landing obligation will have a <i>negative</i> effect on the marine environment?	Yes	15	68.2
	No	6	27.3
	Do not know	1	4.5

While the overall attitude toward the landing obligation was antagonistic, roughly 2/5 of interviewed fishers believed the landing obligation could improve the industry's image or that profits might rise from utilizing previously discarded catches.

Table 9.2.3. Positive and negative regarding the landing obligation, Danish fishers

Questions	Answers	Fishers (n=22)	
		n	%
Can you say something <i>positive</i> about the landing obligation? (open ended question)	No	13	59.1
	Improved image for the commercial fisheries	5	22.7
	Possible profit from catches that would have been discarded previously	4	18.2
Can you say something <i>negative</i> about the landing obligation? (open ended question)	Increased bureaucracy and regulations	7	31.8
	Economically unsustainable for the fisheries	8	36.4
	Loss of food source for the benthic environment	5	22.7
	It is pointless. The landing obligation does not matter	2	9.1

8.3 Managers story - documenting stakeholders view on the landing obligation

A questionnaire was sent by email to all fisheries inspectors in Denmark, with similar questions on the landing obligation as had been used for interviews with fishers, although certain questions were changed to suit the control and enforcement background of fishery inspectors.

Danish fishery inspectors' opinion on the main challenges for the fishers with the landing obligation were much in line with the concerns raised by the fishers, that is difficulties in catch handling, storage issues, quota settings, bureaucracy and ultimately the economic feasibility of the fisheries.

Table 8.2 Primary expected challenges for the fishers with the landing obligation, Danish fishery inspectors.

Questions	Answers	Fishery inspectors (n=30)	
		n	%
What do you see as the primary challenge regarding the landing obligation, for the fishers? (open ended question)	Economic feasibility	9	30.0
	Storage issues	4	13.3
	Accepting the landing obligation at all	4	13.3
	Issues with the marketing of bycatch	3	10.0
	Issues with fitting the quotas	3	10.0
	Increasing gear selectivity to a sufficient level	3	10.0
	Keeping track with the messy and complicated implementations of the landing obligation and difference between Norway and the EU	2	6.7
	Extra handling time of the catch	1	3.3
	Did not answer	1	3.3

As for their own work, by far the largest concern among fishery inspectors was that they saw it as a major challenge to enforce the landing obligation.

Table 8.3 Challenges for the fishery control with the landing obligation, Danish fishery inspectors.

Questions	Answers	Fishery inspectors (n=30)	
		n	%
"What do you see as the primary challenge regarding the landing obligation, for the	Actually enforcing the landing obligation	25	83.3
	Getting the fishers to see why the landing obligation is meaningful	3	10.0

fisheries control?"	No new challenges	1	3.3
(open ended question)	Did not answer	1	3.3

A majority of fishery inspectors either stated that the intention with the regulation is good or that it should end discarding. At the same time, more than 80% of fishery inspectors stated that they could not see how the regulation could be enforced.

The attitude towards the landing obligation was more positive for fisheries inspectors than fishers and more nuances were given to the positive and negative of the regulation. However, while the intention with the landing obligation was viewed as positive by the majority, concerns were raised regarding the practical implementation and enforcement of the regulation.

Table 8.4 Positive and negative regarding the landing obligation, Danish fishery inspectors.

Questions	Answers	Fishery inspectors (n=30)	
		n	%
Can you say something <i>positive</i> about the landing obligation? (open ended question) ¹	Should end discarding	9	30.0
	The intention is good in theory	8	26.7
	Creates incentives for more sustainable and selective fisheries	7	23.3
	Should give a better idea of the real fishery	5	16.7
	Gives more responsibility to the fishers since it is results-based management	2	6.7
	No. Don't think it will be followed and is not possible to enforce	2	6.7
	Better stock assessment	1	3.3
	Did not answer	1	3.3
Can you say something <i>negative</i> about the landing obligation? (open ended question) ¹	Virtually impossible to enforce for the fisheries control	9	30.0
	It will not be complied with/ only works in theory	6	20.0
	Discards that would have survived will die with the landing obligation	5	16.7
	No	4	13.3
	Is it economically viable for the fishers?	3	10.0
	Gives an extra work load to the fishers	2	6.7
	Is it possible to market the bycatch?	1	3.3
	Can create a market for undersized fish	1	3.3
	Will cost extra energy to bring in the extra fish. How is the net CO2 impact?	1	3.3
	No one knows the environmental impact of reduced discards	1	3.3

¹ A responder could state more than one answer to the questions

8.4 Adaptation of gear technology

8.4.1 Gear selectivity catalogue

A total of 25 different factsheets on gear trials were prepared for the DiscardLess selectivity catalogue (http://www.discardless.eu/selectivity_manual), and contributed also to the selectivity manual (O'Neill and Mutch, 2017). These factsheets provide a brief description of catch comparison and selectivity trials that have been carried out in the North Sea (21 sheets) and West of Scotland (5 sheets). These comprise sheets prepared by DiscardLess partners (MSS and DTU Aqua), but also sheets prepared by other institutes from the North Sea not partners in DiscardLess but invited to contribute during a dedicated workshop held in Denmark in June 2016.

The factsheets can be downloaded as a pdf from the link above.

8.4.2 Challenge experiments and industry-led gear selectivity initiatives

The “challenges experiments” conducted in Denmark under WP4 have actually dealt with gear technology rather than fishing strategies, and are thus reported here. These results are described in the Chapter 2 of Deliverable D4.2 (Reid, 2017, <http://www.discardless.eu/deliverables/entry/challenge-experiments-in-a-compiled-cluster-report-and-final-avoidance-manu>).

The MINIDISC free gear choice experiment was performed prior to DiscardLess under EMFF funding, but its results were further analysed and published during DiscardLess (Mortensen et al., 2017a). 12 vessels participated, mainly fishing cod and saithe, with three nephrops targeting vessels. The vessels towed a mix of single and twin rigs, and were distributed between the North Sea, the Skagerrak, and the Baltic Sea. the data were mostly collected by the fishers themselves, supplemented with Fully Documented Fishery (FDF) methods (Mortensen et al., 2017a). Here the fishers experimented with a range of different approaches.

- Seven of the vessels used some form of changed mesh size in the cod end of the net. Usually this involved larger mesh size, but in the Baltic vessels they also trialled reduced mesh sizes
- Three vessels inserted escape panels into the net
- Two vessels trialled separator panels with two cod ends
- One vessel used a toplless trawl and one used a modified mesh in the Bacoma panel

The outcomes of these trials were somewhat mixed. In the Danish trials, nine vessels were able to reduce the discard ratio in the test fisheries (three in the North Sea, three in Skagerrak and three in the Baltic Sea), while two vessels (from the North Sea) actually increased their discard ratio and one North Sea vessel showed no difference in discard ratio. The improvements ranged from less than 2% for four of the vessels, 2-7% for four others, and, in one case, a 17.6% improvement.

Figure 8.1. Barchart showing the average overall landings per haul (Left) and Discards per haul (right) from each area and the average per haul of individual species in each area. Error-bars signify standard error. Note that y-axis differs between areas.

These positive experiences in bottom-up initiatives have fed into a reflection on what are the required incentive mechanisms and what are the barriers in the current legislative framework, as a contribution to the ongoing reform of the technical measure regulation (Eliassen et al., 2018). The paper concludes that a more flexible system of gear development and evaluation is possible by a) involvement of fishers in proposing gear adjustments, self-sampling and documenting results following scientific protocols and evaluation, testing a range of designs before scientific testing, and b) open for faster approval of gear use under a regionalised technical regulation regime with yearly adjustments of management plans containing the technical regulation.

On this basis, Denmark established a more formal platform for the testing and validation of industry-led gear development initiative, the Fast-Track initiative. An initial review of similar initiatives were first conducted in Deliverable D3.1 (O' Neill and Feekings, 2016). This was extended during an ICES Working Group in 2018, ICES WKMSIGD⁴³, where different initiatives established throughout Europe were presented. Different stakeholder groups (fishing industry, scientists and managers) were asked to a) identify the roles of the different stakeholder groups and b) define the risks and problems associated with a more inclusive framework.

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<http://www.ices.dk/sites/pub/Publication%20Reports/Expert%20Group%20Report/EOSG/2018/WKMSIGD/WKMSIGD%20report%202018.pdf>

Key recommendations include:

- Stronger leadership from the regional groups is warranted.
- Greater coordination of all ongoing national science-industry gear development initiatives is needed, especially those initiatives that have common fisheries or face similar problems.
- More effort needs to be devoted towards having effective gear solutions implemented into legislation/encouraging their uptake.
- The relaxed implementation and uncertainty surrounding the implementation of the landing obligation has reduced the drive by the industry to develop and test gears. If more clarity were made around the regulation, the exceptions, its implementation and workability of the whole landing obligation, the situation may be different.

Another initiative was developed in the UK, where an Excel toolkit was developed to provide best practice guidance on collecting the required data and methods to evaluate economic implications of trial fishing gear. This work is described in Deliverable D3.2 (O'Neill and Struble 2017⁴⁴), and in the presentation at the Copenhagen conference⁴⁵. Trials have been ongoing in Scotland and Northern Ireland.

8.4.3 Meta-analyses of the factors influencing selection in the trawl and the vertical separation of fish

Selection by the codend has been the subject of much research over the past thirty years, with trials in artisanal and industrial fisheries around the world. These studies typically test only a few gears, partly for logistic and/or economic reasons and partly to ensure there are sufficient hauls to estimate the selection of each gear with reasonable precision. To explore a broad range of selective gear options for use in a fishery, and to understand better the relative influence of the important variables related to gear design, it is necessary to develop models that predict selection across all of these variables. Such empirical models are best constructed in meta-analyses that combine the data from many trials.

In Deliverable D3.2 (O'Neill and Noble 2017, <http://www.discardless.eu/deliverables/entry/report-on-meta-analyses-of-gear-selectivity-data-in-terms-of-gear-design-pa>), existing meta-analyses were reviewed and new analyses were conducted to investigate the vertical distribution of fish at the mouth of trawl to estimate selectivity for data poor species.

⁴⁴ <http://www.discardless.eu/deliverables/entry/report-on-meta-analyses-of-gear-selectivity-data-in-terms-of-gear-design-pa>

⁴⁵ http://www.discardless.eu/media/results/SessionII_3_Witteveen_EconomicsOfGearTrials.pdf

Figure 8.2. Demersal trawl fitted with a horizontal separator panel that directs fish that go above the panel to the upper codend and fish that go below the panel to the lower codend.

Existing horizontal separator panel data combined from 20 trials conducted in the North Sea and north east Atlantic between 1972 and 2015 were analysed. These trials have used trawl gears with horizontal separator which are fitted across the width of a trawl and direct fish that go above the panel to an upper codend and those that go below to a lower one. The factors considered included the height of the panel, the distance of the panel from the ground gear, and the time of day at which trawling took place on the separation and vertical distribution of fish at the leading edge of the panel. Results are presented for eight species (**Error! Reference source not found.**): the gadoids cod (*Gadus morhua*), haddock (*Melanogrammus aeglefinus*), saithe (*Pollachius virens*) and whiting (*Merlangius merlangus*), the flatfish lemon sole (*Microstomus kitt*) and plaice (*Pleuronectes platessa*), and monkfish (*Lophius piscatorius*) and Nephrops (*Nephrops norvegicus*).

The results show that for six of the eight species, the proportion of fish that rise above the separator panel decreases as the height of the leading edge of the panel increases. Only monkfish and Nephrops do not exhibit a dependency on panel height.

The main results of Deliverable D3.2 can be summarised as follows:

- codend selection depends on codend mesh size, the number of open meshes around the circumference and twine diameter
- panel selection depends on panel mesh size
- For gadoids, panel contact probability depends on where the panel is positioned and the time of year when fishing takes place

- the relationship of L50 with number of meshes in circumference and twine thickness can be opposite between roundfish and flatfish
- it should be possible to separate the three categories of (i) haddock, whiting and saithe, (ii) cod, plaice and lemon sole and (iii) monkfish and Nephrops using vertical separation

8.4.4 Use of underwater light

Extensive analyses of the effect of underwater light on selectivity were performed in the North Sea. These have been reported in Deliverable D3.4 (O'Neill, Watson and Fauconnet, 2018).

Some examples of devices are displayed below

a) Programmable Light Emitting Unit for Fibre Optics

b) Fibre-Threaded Square Mesh Panel

c) LED Light Lines

d) Matrix.

Figure 8.3. LED-based devices developed in WP3 (SNTech pictures)

Figure 8.4 Experimental trials with a fibre optic cable illuminating the bottom half of the grid. (MSS pictures)

In addition, a series of laboratory based experiments were conducted to better understand how light parameter such as intensity, wavelength and flashing rate may affect escape behaviour of haddock and cod.

Figure 8.5. The LED light panel tested when illuminated in green, red and blue.

These experiments demonstrate how fibre optic cables can supply continuous lines of light or illuminate grids on a trawl net and which to direct fish to different parts or out of the fishing gear. These results are likely to be very useful, in the context of a landing obligation (or discard ban), as they demonstrate the possibility of developing gears whose selectivity can be modified easily between tows (eg by switching on a light cable or adjusting headline height) in response to the population on the ground and a vessels individual quota allocation. However, they also demonstrate that we must not have an over-simplified view, as fish reactions will be species specific and are likely to have seasonal and environmental dependencies

The trials which hold most promise from the point of view of the landing obligation are those where a grid was fitted horizontally in the upper panel of the codend. Haddock and whiting behaved differently, with more haddock and fewer whiting passing through when the grid was illuminated. Results like these

which exhibit marked species differences are of particular interest as they indicate how species selective gears can be developed.

8.4.5 Underwater cameras for real-time decisions

Some specific analyses were performed in Denmark on the feasibility of using Real-Time Monitoring (RTM) and delayed cameras systems to improve decisions on hauling the catch onboard or not. This is described in Deliverable D3.3 (Feelings, 2019).

RTM camera systems allow skippers to modify their short term fishing tactics in response to (i) the availability of target species, (ii) the relative abundance of target and non-target species being caught and (iii) the habitat being fished. Under the Landing Obligation, vessel operators will therefore be able to make informed decisions that will improve the efficiency of fishing (i.e employ behavioural tactics to reduce catches of unwanted species or sizes) while reducing its impacts. RTM camera systems also allow for monitoring of the seabed and associated benthic fauna and enable improved and more efficient fishery independent monitoring of demersal species. Furthermore, RTM camera systems can be used to monitor the performance of the gear (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HUe2sWFBgyU>) and observe how small changes affect the selectivity of the gear, as well as observe when the codend is full.

Extensive background research was performed to identify how many companies are developing real-time monitoring (RTM) and delayed camera systems. 8 existing systems were identified. The different companies working specifically with camera systems for fishing were contacted. An information leaflet and a questionnaire was subsequently developed and sent to the national fisheries organisations in Scotland and Denmark to disseminate amongst its members. Despite these being widely disseminated, no completed questionnaires were received from either country. Instead a workshop was then organised by DTU Aqua and the Danish fishermen organisation in Hirtshals, Denmark on the 1st June 2017.

The general consensus was that these RTM camera systems are currently far too expensive for the average fisherman, with a system costing typically around 100 000 euros and up. Despite those present agreeing that the added benefits these systems could bring was substantial, they all felt that the risk currently does not outweigh the return. I.e. that their needs to be done more to document the actual return such systems can bring to the fishermen. By having an estimate on what extent these RTM camera systems can increase catch rates, reduce time spent searching for target species etc. the fishermen could gauge the systems potential in their fishery.

One of the limiting factors regarding the applicability of RTM camera systems in demersal fisheries is that they typically take place under low light conditions and in murky waters due to the resuspension of sediment by the trawl doors and ground gear.

However, several of the fishermen present mentioned that they were playing around with mounting delayed camera systems (e.g. GoPro) on their gear to observe its performance and modifications they had made. This helps to reaffirm that there is an interest amongst fishermen to better understand what is occurring before and during the capture process but the technologies current available, their associated costs, as well as knowledge around their benefits is currently lacking.

Further development of RTM systems is now taking place within the H2020 SMARTFISH project (www.smartfishh2020.eu). One work package aims to design and build an affordable RTM camera system which can be mounted on trawls, autonomous underwater vehicles (AUV) and towed sledges and apply it to fish-finding, catching, management, stock assessment and habitat mapping. Additionally, the work package incorporates new 3D camera technology (e.g. time of flight) to improve image quality in turbid waters, one of the shortcomings of current RTM camera systems.

8.5 Adaptation of fishing strategies. The Scientists' story – identification of locations, times and practices to fish to avoid unwanted catch

Different studies for the North Sea were reported as independent chapters in Deliverable D4.3 (Reid et al., 2018).

A likely side-effect of introducing the landing obligation of the 2013 Common Fisheries Policy into mixed fisheries is the occurrence of the “choke species” problem. When discarding no longer is an option, leasing quota or changing fishing practices remain important tools to avoid choke species. In **Chapter 4**, the scale and tactics linked to using avoidance behaviour to reduce choke species is investigated by analysing the fishing behaviour of a single demersal trawler in the North Sea. Analysis combined qualitative information collected through interviews with the vessel owner and skipper, along with quantitative analysis on fisheries data. From the interviews, saithe and cod were identified as potential choke species and subsequent analysis focused on these two species. The analysis of catch and quota composition showed that cod would choke the fishery early if no catch-quota balancing options were available, resulting in a 87% reduction in revenue, while saithe could choke the fishery later, resulting in a 43% reduction in revenue. Avoidance behaviour was difficult to detect from fisheries data, which was explained by avoidance primarily taking place through very fine-scale tactical choices rather than large displacements. Catch composition showed that saithe is distributed more patchily than cod, with most hauls containing small amounts of saithe and a few hauls containing large amounts. This chapter shows the choke species problem seen from the perspective of an individual fisher and highlights the amount of real-time tactical decisions and trade-offs that need to be made when operating in mixed-fisheries. It also illustrates how solutions and mitigation can be very local and specific, and this will probably more often be the case than we can identify global or generic mitigation.

Figure 8.6 Spatial distribution of catches per haul, along with a density analysis. Blue dots represent a haul with a catch of cod, saithe or other species, while black lines represent depth curves. Red/yellow represents weighted density estimates of catches per haul, with level as a probability estimate.

Generally fisheries science and management advice use both scientific (e.g. observers and surveys) and standard commercially derived data (e.g. landings and VMS) to estimate the distribution and abundance of marine species. In **Chapter 5**, the emphasis is on a new type of commercial data with high resolution and coverage that has not previously used for scientific purposes. While currently used datasets (called DFAD dataset) include the total weight by species on per hauls basis, the new data, primarily developed for traceability purposes (SIF data), also include the commercial size class for the species landed, recorded directly by fishers on a haul-by-haul basis. Thus, this dataset has the potential to provide knowledge on landed fish with as high spatio-temporal resolution as when coupling logbooks and sales slips but with the addition of detailed knowledge on the size distribution. This chapter describes the coverage and completeness of the dataset, and explores the reliability of the data available. It is concluded that the main limitation here is the small number of fishing vessels covered by the dataset, but that the data from those vessels are accurate, detailed and reliable. There is therefore, clear scope to develop this type of data across more vessels. This type of data could provide knowledge on detailed spatial patterns of fishing effort and commercial species distributions as well as serve as a reference fleet. Because these vessels provide direct observations at the haul level it could also be used for analysis at a vessel or métier level, for instance on catchability, spatial selectivity, seasonal patterns or to compare and verify outcomes of spatial fishery models.

Figure 8.7. Landings per trip according to DFAD and SIF for the 10 most landed species in 2015 and 2016 by species and commercial size class. Points: The aggregated weight of the species and size class for a fishing trip. The x-axis represent the weight according to DFAD, the y-axis represent the weight according to SIF. Black line: The 1:1 ratio between DFAD and SIF. Size class 9 is unsorted.

8.6 Optimal use of unwanted catches

Most of the work performed in this case study has been concerning the optimal use of unavoidable unwanted catches (UUC), performed in WP5 and 6.

8.6.1 From deck to first sale

Work package 5 in the DiscardLess project has focused on providing stakeholders, such as fishermen and fishing vessel owners, with alternatives for on-board handling of the previously discarded catches.

Deliverables D5.2 (Viðarsson *et al.*, 2016, <http://www.discardless.eu/deliverables/entry/report-containing-identification-and-recommendations>), D5.4 (Viðarsson *et al.*, 2017, http://www.discardless.eu/adapting_fishing_vessels_and) and D5.5 (Viðarsson *et al.*, 2019). have analysed solutions on on-board handling of unwanted, unavoidable catches for four different fleet segments, of which a typical medium-size Danish seiner from the North Sea.

Bottom trawlers and Danish seiners ranging between 18 and 30 meters are a large and important part of the European fleet, especially in NE-Atlantic, North Sea and adjacent waters. These vessels typically target roundfish and flatfish species, as well as Nephrops. Figure 8.8 shows two vessels that represent this fleet type well (photos: Willem Harlaar to the left and Ally 1903 to the right)

Figure 8.8: Small bottom trawlers and Danish seiners represent a big part of the North Sea fleet

To demonstrate current on-board handling procedures in this fleet section and available alternatives for how to handle UUC, a typical Danish bottom trawler has been selected. It is a 23-meter-long, 6-meter-wide, 165 GT, steel boat with a 500 hp engine. The boat has two decks i.e. the upper deck where the catch is bled, gutted and washed and the lower deck where the hold, cabins and engine are. The boat targets mainly cod, plaice and lemon sole in the North Sea, which have accounted for around 85% of its annual landings in the past. The annual catch volume is around 900 tonnes and the vessel is active for approximately 250 days a year. Each fishing trip takes 3-4 days on average and the usual landing volume is 8-14 tons. The average number of hauls per day is 3-4 where each haul takes 3-5 hours. There are four people in the crew and when the catch is being handled there are two crewmembers on the upper deck attending to bleeding, gutting and cleaning; one in the hold arranging the catch into boxes, icing and stacking the boxes; and the skipper is in the wheelhouse.

After the fish has been lifted on-board and placed in the reception tank (1), it goes to the bleeding and gutting table (2), where the viscera are removed. The viscera and UUC are then thrown back into the ocean through the chute at the end of the table. The targeted fish is placed in a bleeding/cleaning tank after gutting (3), which has a bucket conveyor belt that sends the fish down to the hold. When the fish comes down to the hold a crewmember sorts the catch according to species and size, places it in 30 kg boxes with ice and then stacks the boxes. Approximately 700 boxes can be stored in the hold, which gives a storage capacity of about 21 tons. The hold is refrigerated and the ice is produced with an ice-machine that are installed in the hold. Figure 8.9 shows the setup on the upper deck of the vessel. The bleeding, cleaning and cooling of the catch is variable as there is generally no control on how long time

each fish is in the bleeding/cleaning tank, there is no mechanisms for ensuring first-in-first-out from the tank, overfilling of the tank is common and water replacement is often insufficient. There is also no pre-chilling available, in order to get the temperature down to 0°C as fast as possible.

Figure 8.9: Setup of the on-board handling on the upper deck of a Danish bottom trawler, (1. Reception - 2. Bleeding and gutting - 3. Bleeding / cleaning tank)

It is of the utmost importance to bleed, clean and chill all catches as fast and efficiently as possible. This applies to target and by-catches alike, including UUC. It would therefore be an improvement to replace the bleeding/cleaning tank with a tank that has controllable throughput rate that ensures first-in-first-out. Sufficient time in a bleeding tank with good circulation and water replacement should be around 10-15 minutes (Aðalbjörnsson & Viðarsson, 2013). There are a number of such solutions available with for example special bucket conveyer belts or snails. One such solution is the RoteX system that 3X Technology has developed, which comes in different sizes and can be purpose-built for each vessel. A RoteX system for the Danish trawler would cost around 60.000 EUR (Högnason, 2016). It can also be turned into a pre-cooling tank, by connecting it to an ice machine that can easily be fitted in the lower deck of the boat. There are a number of suppliers of such Ice machines available. One of which is ThorIce, but the S800 slurry ice machine from them produces up to 4 tons/hour of 20% slurry, which would be sufficient for the Danish trawler (Víglandsson, 2016). The S800 cost around 40.000 EUR and the required space it needs is (150/40/60 cm). However, if the vessel owners would like to use the machine to produce slurry ice for the hold, and be prepared for extraordinary good catches they should invest in a reservoir tank. That way they would make sure never to run out of ice.

An interesting option would be to collect the viscera in addition to the UUC and produce silage from it. The raw material supplies for the silage production would include around 100 tonnes of viscera (i.e. roe would be utilised, but all the rest of the viscera and offal would go to silage production, which is around

10% of total wet weight of the catches). The average volume of raw materials going to silage production would therefore be around 400 kg per fishing trip.

Due to lack of available space on-board the Danish bottom trawler the production of fully processed silage is not an option. The solution suggested here is therefore aimed at preserving the material by means of the most economically feasible option for further processing on-land. What is needed for the silage production is a mincer and a tank where the acid can be added to the mix (see more detailed description of silage production processes in Deliverable D5.2). The silage tanks that are recommended for this process are IBC Food Certified storage units. These units are available at a reasonable price due to their frequent disposal.

Figure 8.10: Suggested setup of the on-board handling on the upper deck of a Danish bottom trawler if offal and UUC is used for producing silage, (1. Reception - 2. Bleeding and gutting- 3. Bleeding, cleaning and pre-chilling in a RoteX tank with slurry Ice - 4. IBC digestion tank for silage, connected to a mincer with an acid dispenser)

The analyses above were further refined and detailed in Deliverable D5.4, including more advanced design on the deck and in the storage room.

Figure 8.11: The setup in the storage hold, the slurry ice tank is at the right side, the IBC silage tank in the middle, the fish tubs indented for UUC and fish under MCRS on left.

8.6.2 Valorisation

Work package 6 in the DiscardLess project has focused on looking into the actual potential processing uses of UUC fish for stakeholders, such as fishermen and fish product. Deliverables D6.4 (Larsen et al, 2019) and D6.5 (Iñarra et al., 2019) have analysed the potential market for UUC fish and the product this raw material may be used for.

The Landing Obligation was introduced to the North Sea and Skagerrak in 2016, but only for a few fish species. Among them plaice caught with large mesh size trawl (TR1).

The biggest Danish harbor for fish for human consumption is Hanstholm in the North-west of Denmark. The fish auction are selling fish landed by Danish fishermen, but also fish caught by fishermen from Norway, Scotland, Holland and France. The Port of Hanstholm that owns all the buildings for the auction and the cooling facilities etc. was very keen of making the best possible solutions for the fishing vessels landing UUC. Because it was impossible to have reliable information from the authorities regarding storage methods, cooling, icing, separation from fish for human consumption, the construction work was postponed. This was an economical wise decision, because the landed UUC fish in 2017 has been negligible. There has now been constructed a separate room back to back to the fish auction, but is at the moment only function as a interim storage room for the few boxes that have to be picked up by the lorry that transport offal from the processing industries to the mink feed factories. The facilities are there and waiting to be used.

In a project affiliated to DiscardLess, a trawler from the harbor of Hanstholm was involved in a series of observed fishing trips for catching plaice. The trawler was HM 120 Astoria of Hanstholm .

HM 120 Astoria

The original plan of the project was to rebuild the processing deck, so that all the new amount of UUC could be handled in an ergonomically way and to store this fraction of the catch in a proper manner. The first fishing trips with observer onboard were done in 2016, when plaice under the reference measurement had to be landed accordingly with the Landing Obligation. The result was 24 kg of undersized plaice out of a total catch of 11 tons. This result stopped all activities to rebuild the vessels, because it would have been an “overkill” action in investment. In 2017 the fishing trips were repeated, but no changes were observed in the plaice catches that could justify an investment of 500.000 DKK.

There were a slightly higher bycatch of small cod, but not much. So it has been decided to repeat the fishing trips with observer in 2018.

HM 120 Astoria fishing activities in 2016. The red ring is where the fishing trips with observer onboard took place. Fishing activities in the Baltic Sea are targeted at cod and were not included in the case study.

8.6.3 UUC species handling at Port of Hanstholm

In 2017, the Port of Hanstholm established facilities for storage and delivery of fish which would have been discarded. The storage facility was established in a separate area not connected to the area used for fish auction.

UUC storage facility marked in red and fish auction facility market in blue, Port of Hanstholm. Courtesy of Port of Hanstholm.

UUC storage room layout and current usage

The room is located separately from the auction halls and the logistic services moving from there. The intention is that fish stored in the room are to be collected early in the day, allowing for the fish to be processed in the beginning of production. During this time, the auction will typically have begun and the

handover of fish to companies and vehicles commenced, which makes it necessary for UUC species not to be handled in the auction building. The current use of the UUC storage room as of 2018 is the storing of fishing boxes in need of cleaning. The reasons for this is that no need has yet been necessary for the original intend with the room.

8.6.4 Usage of UUC at Port of Hanstholm

UUC fish are currently handled by the company E. Grønkjær Fiskeeksport A/S. The company typically collect the fish in tubs at the ports two fish collectors⁴⁶. Forklifts are used for collection and transport of crates as the amount of UUC is relatively minute.

Together with fish wastage from fish processor's in the area, the UUC fish is transported to the company Dansk Pelsdyr Foder A/S in Holstebro. Just like the fishers, this company has an interest in an increased usage of the UUC fish, as the payment for UUC fish is at the same level as industrial fish. It should be noted that the production facilities for feed production to the fur industry can take up UUC fish for production all year, unlike the fishmeal production facilities in Hanstholm which only operate from April to October. The rest of the year the industrial fish is transported to Skagen in lorries, approx. 180 km.

8.6.5 Possible usage of UUC catches

There is a whole suite of possible usages of UUC species but not all are feasible from from an economic perspective.

UUC catches cannot be used directly as human consumption but has to be treated according to a number of regulations in order to suffice as part of products intended for human consumption. Such applications are if UUC were to be used for dietary supplements e.g. as protein or fish oil. Such processing and treatment will allow for the UUC material to be used as human consumption in specific products although not directly as whole or parted fish.

Using UUC catches for non-human consumption is likely to be the most widespread usage and covers several possible applications such as animal feed, fishmeal, bait, feed for the fur industry and even cosmetics, fertilizer and biogas production.

It is still unresolved how high a level of treatment is required by regulation before UUC catches can be used for human consumption. Accordingly it cannot be said for sure whether usage of UUC catches for soups or broth will be acceptable.

Possible usages of fish resources

⁴⁶ A fish collector is a specific Danish activity which receive the landed fish and then sort these according to size and quality.

Non-human consumption <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feed and nutrients 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fishmeal for aquaculture and other animal feeds • Fish oil for animal feed, including pet food • Feed for fur (mainly mink) • Bait • Silage and compost •
Non-human consumption <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non nutrient usages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extration of chitin and chitosan • Pigments • Enzymes • Pharmaceuticals: cosmetics and chemicals •
Indirect human consumption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dietary supplements such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fish oil (OMEGA 3 and 6) ○ Proteins
Others	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collagen • Gelatin
Source: Inspiration from SeaFish 2001: Fish Waste Production in the UK	

Using UUC for silage offers the possibility of production on the actual fishing vessels as well as ashore. Silage production ashore require icing of the UUC on the fishing vessels in order to decrease decay before the beginning of the silage process. Production is done by chopping the fish into smaller bits and adding hydrochloric acid or formic acid to preserve the fish. Production facilities for fishmeal would typically be able to take in silage and process the product further in order to produce fishmeal or fish oil. Companies like TripleNine produce a range of fishmeal products which are used as animal feed for pigs, aquaculture or mink in the fur industry. Additionally, silage may be bought directly by the consumer, for instance a mink farm, who then mix the silage with other feed products on site.

8.6.6 The most likely usage of UUC

The actual potential usage of UUC is governed by the circumstances under which the fish is landed and processed. Several aspects influence the potential usage of UUC:

- Geographical placement of landing site
- Food processing industry available in the area
- Distance to potential users such as up takers of animal feed
- Necessary logistics and the facilities available for handling of UUC

Additionally, the potential price any consumers are willing to pay and what other alternative sources they have is of great importance. Using UUC as fishmeal or fish oil as well as for fur feed result in specific price ranges which cannot be exceeded. This mean the UUC catch must have very specific qualities in if it is to exceed the price possible to obtain for industrial fish.

The above figure shows that a certain amount of fluctuation in price can be expected for industrial fish. These mainly relate to supply and demand and range from roughly 1 DKK/kg to 2 DKK/kg in the investigated period. The price settings are global and are mainly influenced by Peruvian and Chilean catches of small fatty fish species.

Feed for the fur industry require a higher level of quality and can be expected to set the price level at roughly 0.2 DKK/kg higher than the regular price set for industrial fish.

8.6.7 Conclusion and perspective

- There are buyers ready to process the landed UUC fish, if they have the right quality and amount.
- The most likely consumers of UUC catches can be expected to be fishmeal and fish oil producers, the fur production industry and pet food producers.
- Lack of knowledge of the amount of landed UUC fish makes the buyers uncertain and block for further investments-
- The level of expenditures to logistic, handling and processing are a challenge that have no strait forward answer.

8.7 Improving monitoring tools in results-based management

In Denmark in particular, but also in other North Sea countries such as in UK and the Netherlands, there has been some move towards the ide of results-based management in a catch-quota management system, where fishers would be fully accountable for their catches in echange of more flexibility in a number of rules regulating fishing effort and technical specifications. This idea has been going on for a

decade since the early days of the Aalborg declaration in 2008 and the cod catch-quota trials implemented in many countries.

Results-based management with Fully Documented Fisheries require all catches to be documented, and verification means being available. Two main avenues have been developed in DiscardLess : Electronic Monitoring and DNA technologies.

8.7.1 Electronic Monitoring

This topic is developing rapidly, and is receiving increasing attention also largely outside of DiscardLess. The contribution of DiscardLess has been to document, synthesise and publish knowledge on Electronic Monitoring collected within various sources and projects, allowing a much larger knowledge base on the pros and cons of the systems.

A number of important documents have as such been produced during the course of the project:

- Analysis of the outcomes of the Danish “free gear choice with EM” trial (MINIDISC trial) in two papers (Mortensen et al., 2017a,b)
- Review of worldwide and European experiences with Electronic monitoring, in a wide international collaboration (van Helmond et al., currently still under review for publication). In particular, much interest has been given to what is going on in Chile, which is about to implement a full EM monitoring program. The leader of this program, Luis Cocas, was invited to present the ongoing developments in this country at the mid-term (in 2017) and final (in 2019) DiscardLess conferences.
- Analysis and publication of the outcomes of the Danish catch quota trials with emphasis on the technological challenges and an estimation of the costs (Plet-Hansen et al., accepted for publication)
- A survey of fishers’ opinion on electronic monitoring (Plet-Hansen et al., 2017)
- An opinion paper on the need for a more flexible technical regulation (Eliassen et al., 2018)
- A comparative analysis of Electronic Monitoring with other tools and technologies for the monitoring and control of the landing obligation (James et al., 2019)
- The organising of a specific theme session on the added value of EM data for scientific purpose in the ICES Annual Science Conference in 2018

All these documents have demonstrated that EM is technologically reliable and in rapid progresses, and represents the most cost-efficient option for controlling and monitoring the LO, and there is scope for getting this accepted by the fishing industry if it is integrated in a flexible management system where those who fully document their catches can be exempted from a number of rules (Ulrich, 2018). The most recent estimation of costs according to the Danish trials sums up to an investment of around 8300 euros/vessel for the installation costs, and 4800 euros per vessel and year for running of operations and the viewing of 10% of all video footage. In addition, automatic image recognition is undergoing great progresses, which will contribute to significantly reduce the operating costs further.

Figure 8.12. Screenshot of AnchorLab electronic monitoring system with automatic image recognition

8.7.2 DNA Technology

Important progresses have been achieved by DiscardLess partners in the development of genetic tools with direct use in the context of the landing obligation. These approaches are described in Deliverable D5.3 (Nielsen et al., 2019) and published in the book chapter by Magnusen et al. (2019).

The key objective was to develop and validate novel genetic methods for the authentication of catches that would be mixed onboard. State-of-art genetic and genomic techniques were used to identify products that have lost all other identifying features e.g. silage, mince, skinless fillets, fishmeal etc. A major progress was to demonstrate that various species could be characterised not only qualitatively (presence/absence), but also quantitatively (proportion of biomass). We showed that for samples of silage and frozen fish blocks, all species included could be detected using DNA based approaches. Furthermore, for species mixtures consisting of gadoids, the estimates of species proportions were highly accurate. For other species mixtures, the DNA proportions were consistent, but needed a calibration factor in order to compensate for different DNA content per weight among species. A direct implication for these results is that DNA based methods should be recognised as a legally valid MCS tool in the reform of the Control and IUU Regulation legislation, and that some of the current legislative constraints regarding e.g. the bulk landing of unwanted catches could be relaxed and replaced by genetic-based biomass estimation methods.

Figure 8.13: Expected proportions of DNA copies among gadoid species based on wet weight compared to estimated proportions of DNA copies from qPCR. Samples were collected at intervals from day 1 to 21.

8.8 Summary – conclusions

In the **North Sea/West of Scotland case study**, many different DMS analyses were thus conducted, but mainly involving desk studies and laboratory experiments rather than actual trials at sea. Major progresses in knowledge on gear selectivity was brought together and shared, including the publication of numerous factsheets on selective devices and some in-depth analyses of how and why the various elements of a trawls modify selectivity by affecting fish behaviour. Extensive experiments of the use of light were conducted, in order to test the avoidance/attraction reactions of fish to different types of light (color, intensity, flash etc). The results demonstrate some differences in behaviour between different species of fish, which could be a promising avenue for improving catch composition. Several studies were published advancing knowledge on the spatial distribution of choke species and unwanted catches, not least using fine-scale fisheries data coming from different previous Danish pilot trials involving Electronic Monitoring and weighting-packing at sea. Regarding the valoriation of unwanted catches in the value chain, a project was run in collaboration with the harbour of Hanstholm (DK), which established new facilities for the storage and delivery of fish in 2017. At present, most unwanted catches and rest raw products are used for feed in the mink farms. The project also foresaw initially the rebuilding of the processing deck of a trawler, but the discard levels in that fishery remain limited and not worth the investment. Finally, a large part of the work performed by DiscardLess in this case study

related to the issue of Monitoring, Control and Surveillance. This included both the publication of various studies on experiences and progresses with Fully Documented Fisheries and Electronic Monitoring, and major progresses achieved on the use of DNA technology for the characterisation of species in a mix (e.g. bulk or silage) and the quantification of the relative biomass of each species. This represents a promising break-through for the control and traceability of unwanted catches in the value chain.

8.9 References

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9 Discussion

This deliverable has provided an overview of the work performed in WP3 (gear technology), WP4 (fishing strategies), WP5 (onboard handling) and WP6 (products to the value chain) in the various case studies. The main outcomes have been presented, and the details are available in the corresponding deliverables and scientific publications, most of which are already available online at <http://www.discardless.eu/>.

The work has been diverse, and not all tasks / work package have been performed in each case study. But in every case studies, significant amounts of new knowledge have been developed about the possible technical and tactical approaches to reduce discards and/or to best utilise them in the value chain. A number of approaches are specific to a given issue in a given case study, but there are also many commonalities and some developments are of interest at a much wider scale than the case study (Figure 9.1)

Figure 9.1. Overview of the discard mitigation strategies by case study investigated in DiscardLess

The main highlights for each of the topical work packages are as follows:

Work Package	Achievement	Purpose
Selectivity and Gear technology (WP3)	Selectivity catalogue, census of >90 previous trials	<i>Sharing knowledge on existing solutions</i>
	Factors influencing fish behaviour in a trawl	<i>enhancing the escapement of unwanted catches</i>
	Analyses of the effects of light underwater	<i>Rethinking selectivity with new innovations</i>
Avoidance and Fishing strategies (WP4)	The fisher's story (challenges experiments)	<i>Try it by yourself</i>
	The scientist's story	<i>Maps and Apps from comprehensive data sources</i>
Uses in value chain (WP6)	Valorisation catalogue, 30 options	<i>Technical and market assessment</i>
	Prioritisation methodology	<i>Where to invest best? Trade-offs and cost-benefits analyses</i>
Onboard handling (WP5)	Simulated onboard handling	<i>Adapting fishing vessels</i>
	Electronic monitoring	<i>Recording of ALL catches</i>
	Genetic characterisation and quantification of species in bulk	<i>Control and traceability of unwanted catches</i>

Important efforts have been made to make all this new knowledge easily available, easily understandable and easily shareable, through the public sharing of information via the DiscardLess website, including popular documents such as Discard Mitigation Toolbox (<http://www.discardless.eu/tools>), short reports, videos and powerpoint presentations. In particular, a selection of these results have been presented at the Conference closing conference (30-31 January 2019), and the presentations are available at <http://www.discardless.eu/home/presentation/landing-obligation-2019-what-have-we-learned-what-are-the-next-steps-update>

Achieving this has required progressing scientific knowledge on a number of topics, including e.g. fish behaviour (swimming, escapement and reaction to light), fish mortality and survival, fine-scale spatial distribution of key species, handling and flesh properties of a number of different fish species, DNA characterisation etc. As such, it must be recognised that the landing Obligation has triggered significant advances in fundamental biological, ecological and technological knowledge, way beyond the state of the art at the time of the reform of the Common Fishery Policy in 2013. It is certain that this research activity would not have taken place without the political pressure to reduce discards. A large part of these studies have also been conducted in collaboration with fishermen and other stakeholders, and live up to our transversal objectives of „stakeholders involvement“, „technological innovation“, „cost-effectiveness“, „control and monitoring“ and „dissemination and outreach“.

However, in spite of these intense scientific and technical analyses, it is obvious that the discarding issue has not been solved yet. As has been described in details in several deliverables from Work Package 2

and Work package 7 as well as several chapters in the Landing Obligation Book ⁴⁷, the complexity of the issue is immense, and there are still many technical, economic, social, cultural, psychological, institutional and political barriers that hinder the achievement of the objectives of the landing obligation. There are thus no simple and unique „one-size-fits-all“ technical solutions that would solve all issues and without economic impact. But there are many small steps that can be taken, which individually can contribute to reducing discards. In 2019, the Landing Obligation is entering a new era, where the article 15 is to be fully implemented after the 4 years of implementation period. Time will tell how the results produced and shared by the Discardless project are going to be used and exploited.

⁴⁷ <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007%2F978-3-030-03308-8>